

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378036804>

Renormalizable interconnectedness of gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses

Preprint · February 2024

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23495.47525

CITATIONS

0

READS

144

1 author:

Jay Yablon

Independent

44 PUBLICATIONS 43 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Renormalizable interconnectedness of gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses

Contents

1. Introduction and overview	1
PART I: INTERCONNECTEDNESS OF GRAVITATIONAL WEAKNESS WITH SMALL NEUTRINO MASSES.....	
2. The Gatto, Sartori, and Tonin (GST) relation: a pedagogic, heuristic starting point.....	2
3. Absence of any simple GST match for charged leptons.....	3
4. An energy shift ΔE which produces two GST matches for charged leptons	4
5. Hypothesis: gravitational weakness is a direct consequence of small neutrino masses	6
6. Neutrino mass variance, and an approximate, preliminary connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses	7
7. Neutrino normal ordering square-mass sums and differences.....	9
8. Formal connection of gravitational weakness with small neutrino masses	10
PART II: GRAVITATIONAL INTERACTIONS OF ELEMENTARY PARTICLES	
9. Lagrangian for long range gravitational interactions of elementary particle quanta	12
10. Long range gravitational interactions of elementary particle quanta via gravitinos, neutrinos and gravitons	15
11. Rest energies of the gravitino superpartners for the massive elementary particles.....	17
12. Full widths of the W , Z and Higgs boson and top quark gravitino superpartners.....	17
13. Two gravitational interaction variants: long range and weak; short range and strong	18
14. Might the $f_0(500)$ a.k.a. sigma meson be a conflation of W , Z , h and t gravitinos?	20
PART III: NEUTRINO MASSES AND MIXING ANGLES.....	
15. Calculation of nine candidate normal ordered neutrino square mass averages	21
16. Calculation of nine candidate normal ordered neutrino mass triplets	22
17. Normal ordered neutrino masses.....	24
18. Tightening of normal ordered neutrino masses.....	25
19. Analytic representation of neutrino masses and mixing angles	26
20. Direct connection of neutrino mass and mixing data with the gravitational constant.....	28
PART IV: DARK ENERGY AND MATTER.....	
21. Gravitational Lagrangian with cosmological constant, for a perfect fluid tensor.....	29
22. Gravitational Lagrangian for dark energy, dark matter, and ordinary matter.....	31
23. Proof using general covariance, of a flat Euclidean spatial curvature for the universe	32
24. Attractive, neutral and repulsive gravitation: The gravitational strength parameter	34
25. Dark energy gravitons and dark matter neutrino loops	35
26. Dark particle energies and densities.....	36
27. Quadratic relations among dark energy and matter, and ordinary matter.....	38
28. Neutral $P=0$ and repulsive $P=-2$ gravitation in the Lagrangian vacuum and subvacuum, and a tighter cosmological constant	39
29. Attractive $P=+2$ ordinary gravitation	41
PART V: CONCLUSION.....	
30. The connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is genuine new physics, not a numeric accident.....	43
31. Summary and conclusion.....	45
References.....	47

Renormalizable interconnectedness of gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses

Jay R. Yablon

Niskayuna, New York 12309

yablon@alum.mit.edu

Abstract: The gravitational interaction is very weak in relation to other interactions, because the neutrino masses are very small in relation to the masses of all other massive elementary particles. To start, the Newton / Einstein gravitational constants are disassembled into particle energies and couplings including neutrino eigenstate masses that are all renormalizable, yielding a renormalizable theory of gravitation. At quantum level, each massive elementary particle is seen to gravitate by first emitting a massive gravitino supersymmetry partner, which then decays onto a neutrino loop which creates a “cliff” responsible for gravitational weakness, which then decays into a massless graviton that is the long-range carrier of gravitation. To interact with a second elementary particle, this graviton decays into a second neutrino loop, which then decays into a second gravitino, which is finally absorbed by its elementary particle superpartner. Because elementary particles can only gravitate through the “interface” of their gravitino superpartners, these neutrino loops and gravitons cannot be directly observed. Consequently, gravitons are identified as the elementary particles of dark energy, and neutrinos forming these loops as the elementary particles of dark matter. These dark densities also reveal a repulsive gravitational variant which may underlie the cosmological redshift. Several predictions are made that can be experimentally tested, including gravitino masses, a narrowed 3σ spread down to 0.0745 eV to 0.0828 eV for the neutrino mass sum, and real PMNS angles, dark density parameters and a cosmological constant also substantially narrowed from present reporting.

1. Introduction and overview

In this article, using the Gatto, Sartori, and Tonin (GST) [1] relation as a pedagogic starting point, we shall set out to prove the following hypothesis and its corollaries, and provide supporting experimental tests:

Hypothesis: The extreme weakness of the gravitational interaction relative to all other interactions, is directly interconnected with, and caused by, the extreme smallness of the neutrino masses in relation to all the other elementary particle masses.

Corollary 1: If the neutrinos were massless rather than massive as was believed possible prior to 1998 [2], then Newton’s constant would become zero and gravitation would not exist. This means the predating evidence for neutrinos being massive was the very existence of Newtonian gravitation itself.

Corollary 2: If one starts with neutrino masses that are zero prior to spontaneous symmetry breaking whereby gravitation does not yet exist, and thereafter spontaneously breaks the symmetry to give neutrinos small but finite masses similarly to how one gives masses to other elementary particles using the Higgs mechanism, then because of **Corollary 1**, gravitation can be made to arise from spontaneous symmetry breaking.

Corollary 3: Because it is well-established that Yang-Mills gauge theories with spontaneously-broken local gauge symmetry are renormalizable [3], the theory of gravitation which would arise because of **Corollary 2**, would be renormalizable.

Corollary 4: If the foregoing **Hypothesis** and **Corollaries** can be formalized in relation to reported experimental data, then Newton’s constant would, for the first time, take its place as the twenty sixth (26) parameter of the standard model of particle physics, alongside the twenty-five (25) parameters which presently constitute this model. It would also lead to a reduction in the number of actually-independent standard model parameters.

The possibility that such foundational new physics would emerge from establishing a definitive interconnection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses, provides strong motivation to explore whether such an interconnection can be properly uncovered, grounded and solidified.

In **PART I** we establish a numeric connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses which can be regarded as a real connection and not just a numeric accident, with better than six sigma statistical confidence. This leads at (8.3) and (9.1) to being able to write the Newton and Einstein constants

entirely in terms of the conversion constant $\hbar c$ times an expression containing only particle energies and couplings including neutrino eigenstate masses, that are all renormalizable.

In **PART II**, as a result of this interconnection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses, we find that the long-range gravitational interaction with which we are very familiar, is indeed carried at the quantum particle level by gravitons, as is widely believed. But, these gravitons cannot and do not ever interact directly with elementary particles engaged in gravitational interactions. Rather, when a massive elementary particle gravitates, it first emits a gravitino superpartner which has its mass determined by the mass of that elementary particle. That gravitino then decays into a neutrino / antineutrino loop, which in turn decays into a massless gravitation that carries the interaction over unlimited distances. To interact with a second elementary particle, that graviton must first decay into a second neutrino loop, which then decays into a second gravitino, which then decays into its elementary particle superpartner to complete the gravitational interaction between those two elementary particles. These neutrino loops which always intercede in long range gravitational interactions, operate as a “cliff” by which the strength of gravitation is vastly diminished in relation to other interactions. But, because this weakness relates the Newton / Einstein constants to $\hbar c$ times an expression that exclusively contains renormalizable particle masses and couplings, again see (9.1) which thereafter feeds into (9.9) and its Feynman diagram **Figure 1**, the result is a renormalizable theory of gravitation. A short range and strong variant of the gravitational interaction which may be observable in hadron experiments is also uncovered at (13.1) to (13.3) and **Figure 2**.

PART III uses the **PART I** interconnections between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses to uncover additional information about the neutrino eigenstate masses and their oscillations via the PMNS mixing angles. This includes tightening the neutrino mass sum by a factor of about 7 in relation to presently-reported data, see (18.2), (20.2) and (30.1), a substantial tightening of the real PMNS angles, including by over a full order of magnitude for θ_{p12} and θ_{p23} , see (20.4) and (30.2), and predictions (18.1) of individual normal ordered neutrino masses. Because the gravitons and the neutrino loops which render gravitation very weak in relation to other interactions never interact directly with elementary particles but are always shielded by the interaction “interface” of gravitino superpartners, **PART IV** shows how and why gravitons are the elementary field quantum particle of dark energy, and neutrinos in the neutrino loops which greatly weaken gravitation in relation to other interactions are the elementary particle excitations of dark matter. This leads to a deeper understanding of dark energy and matter, including identifying a repulsive variant of gravitation illustrated in **Figure 3** that arises when the dark densities and ordinary densities have characteristics shown in **Figure 4**, and how this compares to the attractive gravitation we always experience, which transpires amidst the densities plotted in **Figure 5**.

Finally, in anticipation that one might conclude that the numeric connections first established in **PART I** between the very small neutrino masses and the extreme weakness of gravitation is a numeric accident, the concluding **PART V** reviews the many reasons, in addition to six sigma confidence, why this connection constitutes genuine new physics, not a numeric accident. These include the demonstrated renormalizability of gravitation, the connection of an energy shift ΔE first obtained at (4.7) to other physically-meaningful quantities, and in keeping with the foundational pillar of scientific inquiry, several predictions which afford direct opportunities for experimental contradiction and, absent contradiction, support.

PART I: INTERCONNECTEDNESS OF GRAVITATIONAL WEAKNESS WITH SMALL NEUTRINO MASSES

2. The Gatto, Sartori, and Tonin (GST) relation: a pedagogic, heuristic starting point

Over half a century ago, Gatto, Sartori, and Tonin (GST) [1] found that the CKM mixing angle θ_{C12} which at the time was simply known as the Cabibbo angle θ_C , can be related within experimental errors to the down-to-strange quark mass ratio by $\tan^2 \theta_{C12} = m_d / m_s$. This relation continues to hold for present-day experimental data [4]. The 2023 PDG review of quark masses [5] points out how, although the “mass parameters in the QCD Lagrangian...depend on the renormalization scheme used to define the theory, and also on the scale parameter μ ...issues surrounding the renormalization of quark masses disappear when considering pairwise ratios of these masses in QCD alone. Indeed, if the same renormalization scheme and scale are implemented...QCD renormalization factors are identical for all quark flavors, and these factors

therefore cancel exactly in quark-mass ratio. The same remains true in the presence of QED if the two quarks in the ratio have the same electric charge. In particular, this means that these ratios are scheme and scale independent [“SS independent”] up to possible QED corrections.” Using this scheme and scale independence with present-day experimental data from, e.g., [4] and page 5 of [6], a second GST relation $\tan^2 \theta_{C23} = m_u / m_c$ can be seen to exist between the CKM angle θ_{C23} and the up-to-charm quark mass ratio.

The standard model (SM) of particle physics contains twenty-five independent parameters. But these two GST relations raise the possibility (not the certainty) that two of these parameters, namely θ_{C12} and θ_{C23} , are not really independent, but are functions of particular fermion (quark) masses. To be clear, this observation does *not* elevate the GST relation to the rank of first principle. It simply highlights a question of whether the CKM angles can be fully specified as a function of quark masses, whereby the number of independent SM would be reduced, and a deeper understanding of the fermion masses might perhaps be obtained.

The CKM matrix used for quarks is formed by taking the product $V_{\text{CKM}} = U_{23}U_{13}U_{12}$ of three 3x3 unitary matrices each of which only rotates in the 2,3, the 1,3 and the 1,2 rows and columns respectively, with a phase included in U_{31} , see [7]. The PMNS matrix used for leptons is identically constructed. Of course, these two matrices *operate differently* on their subject particles, because quarks only change generations during weak beta decay and do not oscillate, while leptons do not change generations during weak beta decay, and rather, oscillate among generations only when in a neutrino state. Also, while the quarks and the charged leptons all have masses on the order of MeV or GeV, the neutrino eigenstate masses sum to no less than 0.06 eV and no more than about 0.12 eV [8], making the neutrinos millions or billions of times less-massive than all the other elementary fermions and the many hadrons observed in particle physics.

But because the structures of the CKM and PMNS matrices in terms of their mixing angles are identical, it is appropriate and sensible to inquire (not to conclude) whether GST relations similar to those that do fit the quark mass data, might also apply in some manner to the lepton mass data and the PMNS mixing angles, at least as a heuristic tool to gain deeper physical understandings, and to consider whether such analysis can also illuminate these important generational transition differences between quarks and leptons.

To avoid misunderstanding, let us be clear: The above observations do not elevate the GST relation to the rank of first principle. They simply highlight a question of whether the CKM angles, and identically-constructed PMNS angles for leptons, using the GST relation as a pedagogic, heuristic tool, can perhaps be specified in terms of fermion masses, whereby the number of independent SM parameters can be reduced, and a deeper understanding of the fermion masses and their physical effects, can perhaps be obtained.

3. Absence of any simple GST match for charged leptons

Comparing the two GST relations $\tan^2 \theta_{C12} = m_d / m_s$ and $\tan^2 \theta_{C23} = m_u / m_c$, it is seen that the former, original GST relation, contains the ratio of first-to-second generation (1-to-2) isospin-down quarks and also contains a 12 index. Because of this correspondence, we shall refer to this as a “native” GST relation. In contrast, the latter contains the ratio of first-to-second generation (1-to-2) isospin-up quarks, but contains a 23 index. Because these do not match, we shall refer to this as a “crossover” GST relation.

To explore the possible applicability of GST relations to leptons, we define angles of the general form $\tan^2 \vartheta_{jk}^l \equiv m_j / m_k$ where $j, k = 1, 2, 3$ and $j < k$, where we regard both leptons in any given ratio to have the same weak isospin and electric charge. That is, any ratio so-defined must contain only charged leptons, or only neutrinos. From [5], particularly because SS independence hold for particles of like charge in both QCD and QED, this means that any GST angle so defined will be SS independent. Based on the quark GST relations, it will prudent to consider both native and crossover relations.

We start with the charged leptons, reported by the latest PDG data [9] to have the following rest masses:

$$m_e c^2 = 1776.86(12)\text{MeV}; m_\mu c^2 = 105.6583755(23)\text{MeV}; m_\tau c^2 = 0.51099895000(15)\text{MeV}. \quad (3.1)$$

The sum of these charged lepton (l) masses / rest energies, is defined and easily calculated to be:

$$\Sigma E_l \equiv \Sigma m_l c^2 \equiv (m_e + m_\mu + m_\tau) c^2 = 1883.029(120)\text{MeV}. \quad (3.2)$$

So, we now simply define $\tan^2 \vartheta_{jk}^l \equiv m_j / m_k$ as stated above, then calculate that:

$$\begin{aligned}\vartheta_{12} &\equiv \arctan \sqrt{m_e / m_\mu} = 3.978157780(43)^\circ; & \vartheta_{13} &\equiv \arctan \sqrt{m_e / m_\tau} = 0.971548(33)^\circ; \\ \vartheta_{23} &\equiv \arctan \sqrt{m_\mu / m_\tau} = 13.70420(45)^\circ.\end{aligned}\tag{3.3}$$

Then, we compare the angles in (3.3) with the latest data including SK atmospheric data, for the real PMNS angles (P), given in [10] for normal ordering best fits at 1-sigma and 3-sigma, by:

$$\begin{aligned}1\sigma : \theta_{p12} &= 33.41_{-0.72}^{+0.75}{}^\circ; & 3\sigma : 31.31^\circ &\rightarrow 35.74^\circ; \\ 1\sigma : \theta_{p13} &= 8.58_{-0.11}^{+0.11}{}^\circ; & 3\sigma : 8.23^\circ &\rightarrow 8.91^\circ; \\ 1\sigma : \theta_{p23} &= 42.2_{-0.9}^{+1.1}{}^\circ; & 3\sigma : 39.7^\circ &\rightarrow 51.0^\circ.\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

Unlike the CKM for quarks angles, the angles in (3.3) are nowhere near any of the PMNS angles (3.4). But this ought not be the end of the inquiry; rather, it is only the start.

Specifically, although the PMNS and CKM matrices are identically constructed, the CKM operation on quarks permits generational transitions during weak beta decay but does not permit oscillations in either the isospin-up or isospin-down quark sectors, while the PMNS operation on leptons bars transitions during beta decay and causes all transitions to occur through oscillations of the isospin-up neutrinos. This restriction of PMNS operation to the neutrinos alone, while CKM operation applies to both isospin-up and down quarks, would explain why there are viable GST relations $\tan^2 \theta_{12C} = m_d / m_s$ and $\tan^2 \theta_{23C} = m_u / m_c$ for up and down quarks, but there do not appear to be similar relations for charged leptons alone as seen when comparing (3.3) with (3.4). Simply put: because the PMNS angles only operate to oscillate neutrinos and do not operate on charged leptons, one should expect that any viable GST relations for leptons would exclusively involve neutrino and not charged lepton masses, or would at least be heavily dominated by the neutrino masses. So, if we are to find any GST relations for leptons, we would have to turn to the neutrino masses.

This view is further strengthened if we consider the real CKM angles obtained from (12.28) of [7], namely:

$$\theta_{C12} = 13.003 \pm 0.039^\circ; \quad \theta_{C13} = 0.211 \pm 0.006^\circ; \quad \theta_{C23} = 2.397_{-0.042}^{+0.049}{}^\circ,\tag{3.5}$$

and compare these with the PMNS angles in (3.4). Because a GST relation of the form $\tan \theta = m_1^{.5} / m_2^{.5}$ describes a right triangle with $m_1^{.5}$ and $m_2^{.5}$ being the legs respectively opposite and adjacent to θ , smaller GST angles indicate larger masses ratios and larger GST angle indicate smaller mass ratios. If we examine the masses of the isospin up quarks, and of the isospin down quarks [4], and of the charged leptons in (3.1), and compare their ratios with one another to similar ratios of neutrino masses which may be inferred from [10], it becomes clear that the ratios of neutrino eigenstate masses to one another are substantially smaller than the mass ratios of identically-charged quarks, and of charged leptons. So, it is possible that – and should at least be explored whether – the larger PMNS angles of (3.4) versus the CKM angles (3.5) arise because of the PMNS angles having GST-type relations that exclusively involve, or are at least heavily dominated by, neutrino eigenstate masses, to see if this explains why (3.3) fails to come anywhere close to the empirical (3.4) and in fact produced much smaller angles precisely because of the larger ratios of the charged lepton masses to one another, versus neutrino masses. So again, the absence of a match between (3.3) and (3.4), and the fact that this mismatch produced much smaller angles than the observed PMNS angles, together with how the PMNS angles govern transitions exclusively among neutrino states in contrast to how quark mixing occurs only during weak beta decay, points our inquiry toward neutrino masses.

4. An energy shift ΔE which produces two GST matches for charged leptons

To proceed following the absence of any simple match between (3.3) and any of the PMNS angles (3.4), using the mass sum defined in (3.2) we apply elementary trigonometry to re-recast (3.3) as:

$$\begin{aligned}\cos^2 \vartheta_{12}^q &= m_\mu / (m_e + m_\mu) = m_\mu / (\Sigma m_l - m_\tau) = 0.9951869458(1); \\ \cos^2 \vartheta_{13}^q &= m_\tau / (m_e + m_\tau) = m_\tau / (\Sigma m_l - m_\mu) = 0.99971250(2); \\ \cos^2 \vartheta_{23}^q &= m_\tau / (m_\tau + m_\mu) = m_\tau / (\Sigma m_l - m_e) = 0.943874(4).\end{aligned}\tag{4.1}$$

We also use $\cos^2 \theta = 1 - \sin^2 \theta$ to rewrite the sine-based PMNS data from [10], indicating successive spreads at 1σ , 2σ and 3σ to the right of each median, as (note, the data in [10] only shows 1σ and 3σ spreads; we estimate 2σ spreads by a linear interpolation using $2/3$ of the difference between the median and 3σ data.):

$$\begin{aligned} \cos^2 \theta_{P12} &= 0.697_{-0.012}^{+0.012} \text{ }_{-0.025}^{+0.022} \text{ }_{-0.038}^{+0.033}, & \cos^2 \theta_{P13} &= 0.97775_{-0.00056}^{+0.00059} \text{ }_{-0.00115}^{+0.00115} \text{ }_{-0.00173}^{+0.00173}, \\ \cos^2 \theta_{P23} &= 0.549_{-0.019}^{+0.016} \text{ }_{-0.101}^{+0.029} \text{ }_{-0.152}^{+0.043}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

As with (3.3) and (3.4), we see that (4.1) is nowhere close to matching (4.2).

The presence of the mass sum (3.2) in the (4.1) denominators, however, reveals a possible way to proceed: For exploratory purposes only, we postulate the existence of some energy difference denoted $\Delta E = \Delta mc^2$ which we shall now add to the mass sum in (4.1) to force a match with the angles in (4.2). That is, we shift ΣE_i by ΔE to obtain an energy-shifted $\Sigma E_i \rightarrow \Sigma E'_i \equiv \Sigma E_i + \Delta E$, then see what it takes to match (4.2).

To begin with, this ΔE is entirely arbitrary. Additionally, one can select definite energies at will to precisely fit each of the PMNS angles in (4.2) at their medians and at each of their σ spreads. So, it proves nothing to match a single angle and its error bars using some selected ΔE . Therefore, the first question is whether there is a *single* ΔE which can be *simultaneously* fitted to *two of the three angles* in (4.2). Then, if these results are affirmative, the second question is whether this two-fit ΔE can be physically explained, independently of this fitting. In other words, is this energy which is seemingly arbitrary, in fact connected in a clear way to other known physics which we can and do observe? Based on the discussion at the end of the last section, the energies that we shall particularly consider for this connection, will be the neutrino rest energies.

So, we first shift (4.1) using $\Sigma m_i \rightarrow \Sigma m'_i = \Sigma m_i + \Delta m$, including 12, 13 and 23 subscripts on the energy shifts and mass sums to correspond with those in $\vartheta_{12} \rightarrow \vartheta'_{12}$ and $\vartheta_{13} \rightarrow \vartheta'_{13}$ and $\vartheta_{23} \rightarrow \vartheta'_{23}$, thus writing:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos^2 \vartheta'_{12} &= m_\mu / (\Sigma m'_{12} - m_\tau) = m_\mu / (\Sigma m_i + \Delta m_{12} - m_\tau); \\ \cos^2 \vartheta'_{13} &= m_\tau / (\Sigma m'_{13} - m_\mu) = m_\tau / (\Sigma m_i + \Delta m_{13} - m_\mu); \\ \cos^2 \vartheta'_{23} &= m_\tau / (\Sigma m'_{23} - m_e) = m_\tau / (\Sigma m_i + \Delta m_{23} - m_e). \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

Then, using (3.2), we restructure each of (4.3) to isolate each of the Δm as follows:

$$\Delta m_{12} = m_\mu \tan^2 \vartheta'_{12} - m_e; \quad \Delta m_{13} = m_\tau \tan^2 \vartheta'_{13} - m_e; \quad \Delta m_{23} = m_\tau \tan^2 \vartheta'_{23} - m_\mu. \quad (4.4)$$

It will be seen that if $\Delta m_{ij} = 0$ and with $\vartheta'_{ij} \rightarrow \vartheta_{ij}$, these revert identically to the simple GST relations (3.3).

Because of the possibility that there may be a ‘‘crossover’’ in the connections between these angles ϑ'_{ij} and the three real PMNS angles θ_{Pij} , and to avoid presupposing which ϑ'_{ij} might end up connecting with which θ_{Pij} , we now insert the data in (4.2) for each of the PMNS angles, into each of the ϑ'_{ij} in (4.4), for a total of $3 \times 3 = 9$ calculations, and use median mass data because this is much tighter than the PMNS data. For the three ‘‘native’’ assignments $\vartheta'_{ij} \equiv \theta_{Pij}$ we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta m_{12}(\theta_{P12}) &= m_\mu \tan^2 \theta_{P12} - m_e = 45.421_{-2.566}^{+2.656} \text{ }_{-4.638}^{+5.718} \text{ }_{-6.853}^{+8.741} \text{ MeV} / c^2; \\ \Delta m_{13}(\theta_{P13}) &= m_\tau \tan^2 \theta_{P13} - m_e = 39.924_{-1.096}^{+1.041} \text{ }_{-2.141}^{+2.146} \text{ }_{-3.210}^{+3.221} \text{ MeV} / c^2; \\ \Delta m_{23}(\theta_{P23}) &= m_\tau \tan^2 \theta_{P23} - m_\mu = 1348.136_{-91.654}^{+116.027} \text{ }_{-160.613}^{+732.619} \text{ }_{-235.086}^{+1239.179} \text{ MeV} / c^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

And for the six ‘‘crossover’’ assignments $\vartheta'_{ij} \equiv \theta_{Pik}$ with $j \neq k$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta m_{12}(\theta_{P13}) &= m_\mu \tan^2 \theta_{P13} - m_e = 1.893_{-0.065}^{+0.062} \text{ }_{-0.127}^{+0.128} \text{ }_{-0.191}^{+0.192} \text{ MeV} / c^2; \\ \Delta m_{12}(\theta_{P23}) &= m_\mu \tan^2 \theta_{P23} - m_e = 86.287_{-5.450}^{+6.899} \text{ }_{-9.551}^{+43.564} \text{ }_{-13.979}^{+73.686} \text{ MeV} / c^2; \\ \Delta m_{13}(\theta_{P12}) &= m_\tau \tan^2 \theta_{P12} - m_e = 771.926_{-43.147}^{+44.659} \text{ }_{-78.004}^{+96.152} \text{ }_{-115.242}^{+147.000} \text{ MeV} / c^2; \\ \Delta m_{13}(\theta_{P23}) &= m_\tau \tan^2 \theta_{P23} - m_e = 1459.168_{-91.654}^{+116.027} \text{ }_{-160.613}^{+732.619} \text{ }_{-235.086}^{+1239.179} \text{ MeV} / c^2; \\ \Delta m_{23}(\theta_{P12}) &= m_\tau \tan^2 \theta_{P12} - m_\mu = 666.779_{-43.147}^{+44.659} \text{ }_{-78.004}^{+96.152} \text{ }_{-115.242}^{+147.000} \text{ MeV} / c^2; \\ \Delta m_{23}(\theta_{P13}) &= m_\tau \tan^2 \theta_{P13} - m_\mu = -65.224_{-1.096}^{+1.041} \text{ }_{-2.141}^{+2.146} \text{ }_{-3.210}^{+3.221} \text{ MeV} / c^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

Now looking for simultaneous fits, although there is some overlap between $\Delta m_{23}(\theta_{p23})$ in (4.5) and $\Delta m_{13}(\theta_{p23})$ in (4.6), and between $\Delta m_{13}(\theta_{p12})$ and $\Delta m_{23}(\theta_{p12})$ in (4.6), these cannot be counted because the PMNS angles are the same in each. The only overlap simultaneously using *two different PMNS angles* is between the native relations for $\Delta m_{12}(\theta_{p12})$ and $\Delta m_{13}(\theta_{p13})$ in (4.5). For these, there is a 3σ overlap from $38.568\text{MeV} < \Delta E < 43.145\text{MeV}$, with the lower ΔE bound coming from the lower 3σ bound of $\Delta m_{12}(\theta_{p12})$ and the upper ΔE bound from the upper 3σ bound of $\Delta m_{13}(\theta_{p13})$. Moreover, a simultaneous 2σ fit occurs over $40.782\text{MeV} < \Delta E < 42.070\text{MeV}$. With the same noted linear interpolations used to obtain (4.2) but now taking the average of the median and 3σ data, we can no longer acquire an overlap at 1.5σ . The tightest-possible spread appears to be near 1.65σ , which is to say that the tightest possible simultaneous match requires one or both of θ_{p12} and θ_{p13} to be at least about 1.65σ from their medians.

One way to formally state this overlap is to average the 3σ high and low error bars of 38.568MeV and 43.145MeV to establish the median, then set the extremes at these 3σ spreads, whereby:

$$\Delta E = \Delta E_{12}(\theta_{p12}) = \Delta E_{13}(\theta_{p13}) = 40.857 \pm 2.288 \text{ MeV}. \quad (4.7)$$

Therefore, using (4.7), the energy-shifted lepton mass sum is:

$$\Sigma m_l \rightarrow \Sigma m'_l = \Sigma m_l + \Delta m = 1923.89 \pm 2.41 \text{ MeV} / c^2. \quad (4.8)$$

Then we can work backwards using (4.8) and (3.1) in (4.3) to find that that the associated angles are:

$$\begin{aligned} \vartheta'_{12} &= \arccos \sqrt{m_\mu / (\Sigma m'_l - m_\tau)} = \arccos \sqrt{m_\mu / (\Sigma m_l + \Delta m - m_\tau)} = 32.03^{+0.70}_{-0.73} \text{ } (= \theta_{p12}); \\ \vartheta'_{13} &= \arccos \sqrt{m_\tau / (\Sigma m'_l - m_\mu)} = \arccos \sqrt{m_\tau / (\Sigma m_l + \Delta m - m_\mu)} = 8.68^{+0.23}_{-0.24} \text{ } (= \theta_{p13}). \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

Comparing (4.9) to the PMNS angles in (3.4), were we to prospectively associate ϑ'_{12} with θ_{p12} as a native relation (which is shown parenthetically), this would lower the θ_{p12} median by about 1.38° , which stays within 2σ . Given the spread of θ_{p12} at 3σ , and because of how we obtained (4.7), this would keep the lower 3σ bound at 31.31° as is, but would tighten the upper bound from 35.74° down to 32.73° . Similarly, were we to prospectively associate ϑ'_{13} with θ_{p13} as a native relation (also shown parenthetically), this would raise the θ_{p13} median by 0.10° , staying within 1σ . Moreover, this would keep the upper 3σ bound at 8.91° as is, but tighten the lower bound from 8.23° up to 8.44° . Using elementary trigonometry, the prospective relations (4.9) can be rewritten in the traditional GST form, with the entire mass shift added to the electron rest mass, as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tan^2 \vartheta'_{12} &= (m_e + \Delta m) / m_\mu \quad (= \tan^2 \theta_{p12}); \\ \tan^2 \vartheta'_{13} &= (m_e + \Delta m) / m_\tau \quad (= \tan^2 \theta_{p13}). \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

Again, we make no equivocation about the energy shift (4.7), at the moment, being an arbitrary energy. If this energy shift is to be regarded as anything other than a numeric ‘‘accident’’ without any additional physical meaning, it now becomes of central importance to answering to the question which will underlie the development in the balance of this article: Independent of the prospective data match obtained in (4.9), *what is the physical meaning of this energy shift ΔE in (4.7)?*

5. Hypothesis: gravitational weakness is a direct consequence of small neutrino masses

At the end of **Section 3**, we reviewed why it is likely that any lepton GST relations would have to be based, exclusively, or at least dominantly, upon the neutrino and not charged lepton masses. Now that we have obtained ΔE with a median on the order of 40.86 MeV in (4.7), it appears that this is the energy that will have to be related in some fashion to the rest energies of the neutrino eigenstates to have the PMNS angles be GST-type or other functions of the various lepton masses. As noted in **Section 2** and reported in [8], the upper bound on the neutrino mass sum, which we denote by $\Sigma m_{\nu i \max}$ with $i = 1, 2, 3$, is about $0.12 \text{ eV}/c^2$. So, for a preliminary estimate of what may be needed to connect the energy shift in (4.7) to neutrino masses, we simply calculate the ratio of this upper bound on mass sum, over ΔE in (4.7), and the inverse ratio, to find that:

$$\Sigma m_{\nu_{i\max}} c^2 / \Delta E = 2.937_{-0.156}^{+0.174} \times 10^{-9}; \quad \Delta E / \Sigma m_{\nu_{i\max}} c^2 = 3.405(191) \times 10^8. \quad (5.1)$$

So, if ΔE is related in some way to the neutrino masses, the connection between the two would have to cross more than eight orders of magnitude. Because $\Delta E \sim 40.86$ MeV is roughly representative of rest energies encountered for elementary particles other than neutrinos – recognizing the broad spread from the electron rest mass at the low end to the top quark mass at the high end – it is helpful to think of (5.1) as a rough statement of how much smaller neutrino masses are, than all the other particle masses. Even the lightest particle, the electron, is over 4 million times more massive than the neutrino mass sum.

Because we are now examining the wide disparity between neutrino masses and all other masses, it seems sensible to examine another wide disparity, namely, that between the strength of the gravitational interaction, and that of all other interactions. Two quantities pertinent in this regard are the Fermi vev $v = \sqrt{\hbar^3 c^3 / \sqrt{2} G_F} = 246.21964(6)$ GeV calculated from $G_F = 1.1663788(6) \times 10^{-5} \hbar^3 c^3 \text{ GeV}^{-2}$, and the Planck energy $E_p = \sqrt{\hbar c^5 / G_N} = 1.220890(14) \times 10^{19}$ GeV calculated from Newton's gravitational constant $G_N = 6.70883(15) \times 10^{-39} \hbar c (c^2 / \text{GeV})^2$, with the foregoing data reported by [11]. We can compare these two energies by taking the ratios:

$$\frac{v}{E_p} = \frac{\hbar}{c} \sqrt{\frac{G_N}{\sqrt{2} G_F}} = 2.01672(2) \times 10^{-17}; \quad \frac{E_p}{v} = \frac{c}{\hbar} \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{2} G_F}{G_N}} = 4.95854(6) \times 10^{16}. \quad (5.2)$$

Noting that GST relations written generally as $\tan \theta = m_1^5 / m_2^5$ equate the square root of a mass ratio to a trigonometric angle, we may also use (5.2) to calculate:

$$\sqrt{v / E_p} = 4.490793(26) \times 10^{-9}; \quad \sqrt{E_p / v} = 2.226778(13) \times 10^8. \quad (5.3)$$

Upon comparing (5.1) and (5.3), we see that these differ by a multiplicative factor of 1.529(86). At the lower end, this is 1.443, which is only slightly larger than the $\sqrt{2}$ which enters the Yukawa couplings of all the elementary fermion masses to the Fermi vev in the relation $E_f = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} G_f v$, and which arises from the spontaneous symmetry breaking of the unbroken Higgs field $\phi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\phi_1 + i\phi_2)$.

Given the closeness of (5.1) and (5.3) especially in view of the square root of 2 factor which we know is pertinent when specifying fermion masses, we now formally introduce the **Hypothesis** and the four **Corollaries** laid out in **Section 1**. Now, we embark upon how to prove this hypothesis beyond doubt.

6. Neutrino mass variance, and an approximate, preliminary connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses

The experimental data for individual neutrino masses, see, e.g., [10], is generally reported as square mass differences Δm_{ij}^2 with $i, j = 1, 2, 3$, and not as linear mass differences or simply linear masses. A good online review of why this is so, and why it is that detecting neutrino oscillations proves that neutrinos are massive, not massless, is provided in [12]. There are of course three generations of fermions, whereby in the case of neutrinos, there are three oscillating flavor and mass eigenstates. To simplify discussion, we shall simply refer to the mass values associated with each mass eigenstate as the "neutrino masses." If we denote the sum of these neutrino masses as $\Sigma m_{\nu_i} \equiv m_{\nu_1} + m_{\nu_2} + m_{\nu_3}$, the square of this sum as $(\Sigma m_{\nu_i})^2 \equiv \Sigma^2 m_{\nu_i}$ and the sum of the square masses as $\Sigma m_{\nu_i}^2 \equiv m_{\nu_1}^2 + m_{\nu_2}^2 + m_{\nu_3}^2$, then the neutrino mass variance is:

$$\sigma^2(m_{\nu_i}) = \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle - \langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle^2 = \frac{1}{3} \Sigma m_{\nu_i}^2 - \frac{1}{9} \Sigma^2 m_{\nu_i}. \quad (6.1)$$

As seen in (6.1), and which is true for any variance, the square mass sum, $\Sigma m_{\nu_i}^2$, and the mass sum squared, $\Sigma^2 m_{\nu_i}$, are mathematically independent of one another, and are connected by the variance $\sigma^2(m_{\nu_i})$. This is important to keep in mind, because it means that if the close relation between (5.1) and (5.3) is to be turned into an exact interconnection, there are two possible mass-dimensioned points of data contact. First is the mass sum, Σm_{ν_i} , second is the square root of the square mass sum, $\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu_i}^2} = \sqrt{3\sigma^2(m_{\nu_i}) + \frac{1}{3}\Sigma^2 m_{\nu_i}}$, which

is related to the former Σm_{ν_i} by the variance. We shall first illustrate the close but still-inexact connection between (5.1) and (5.3) using the mass sum which has its maximum at 0.12 eV. Then, using the neutrino mass data reported by [10], we shall use the square mass sum to uncover a virtually exact connection that has a better than six sigma probability of not being a numeric accident.

First, as a heuristic step to more precisely express the relation between (5.1) and (5.3), let us formalize the square roots used in (5.3) by defining a new GST angle according to $\tan^2 \Theta \equiv v / E_p$, whereby:

$$\Theta = \arctan \sqrt{v / E_p} = 4.490793(26) \times 10^{-9} \text{ rad} \cong \sqrt{v / E_p}; \quad \text{therefore} \quad \Theta^{-1} = 2.226778(18) \times 10^8 \text{ rad}^{-1}. \quad (6.2)$$

Because the Maclaurin series $\tan x = x + \frac{1}{3}x^3 + \dots$, the approximation $\tan \Theta \cong \Theta$ in the above holds to 3.02×10^{-26} , that is, out to the 26th decimal place. In view of (5.2), this means that $\Theta \cong \tan \Theta = \sqrt{v / M_p c^2}$ is effectively equal to the fourth root of the Newton gravitational constant over the Fermi constant, up to the $\sqrt{2}$ factor which is retained by convention in $v = \sqrt{\hbar^3 c^3 / \sqrt{2} G_F}$. This factor is an adjustment to that constant which reflects, historically, that when Fermi first proposed this constant to explain weak interactions by analogy to electromagnetic interactions, it was not yet known that only left-chiral fermions would interact weakly. As to the possible question of why we are using the fourth root of the ratio of these constants and not other roots, the answer is simple: GST angle tangents vary with square roots of mass ratios. So, given that v and M_p in turn vary inversely with the square roots of the Fermi and Newton constants irrespective of conventions, the tangent of any GST-type angle relating a ratio of v to E_p will necessarily vary with the fourth root of the ratio of these natural constants, not any other roots.

Now, let's consider the dimensionless Yukawa coupling G_{ν_i} of a neutrino mass m_{ν_i} to the Fermi vev specified with $c=1$ by $m_{\nu_i} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} G_{\nu_i} v$, whereby the neutrino mass sum will be $\Sigma m_{\nu_i} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \Sigma G_{\nu_i} v$. In view of this and the closeness of (5.1) and (5.3), let us now multiply $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ by ΔE obtained in (4.7) by $\tan \Theta = \sqrt{v / E_p}$ using the numeric value for this square root ratio shown in (6.2), then relate this on an approximate basis to the maximum experimental value $\Sigma m_{\nu_{i\max}} = 0.12 \text{ eV}$ for the neutrino mass sum, to obtain:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \Delta E \sqrt{v / E_p} = 0.130(7) \text{ eV} \cong \Sigma m_{\nu_{i\max}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \Sigma G_{\nu_{i\max}} v = 0.12 \text{ eV}. \quad (6.3)$$

We can then extract the first and third terms from (6.3) and reduce and rearrange, to obtain:

$$\Sigma G_{\nu_{i\max}} \cong \Delta E / \sqrt{v E_p}, \quad (6.4)$$

where, within an order of magnitude of unity:

$$\Sigma G_{\nu_i} \leq \Sigma G_{\nu_{i\max}} < \Delta E / \sqrt{v E_p}. \quad (6.5)$$

This is a more direct restatement of the closeness of (5.1) and (5.3), and in the form of (6.4) we see that the maximum value of the sum of the neutrino Yukawa couplings, is approximately equal to the energy shift ΔE obtained in (4.7), divided by the square root of the product $v E_p$ of the Fermi vev times the Planck energy. In this form, the initially-arbitrary energy shift of (4.7) used to obtain the GST matches in (4.9), is seen to be numerator of the Yukawa coupling (6.4), and so directly determines the approximate maximum value of the neutrino mass sum and is thereby approximately connected to the neutrino masses. Were we to insert $\Delta E \cong \Sigma G_{\nu_{i\max}} \sqrt{v E_p}$ from (6.4) into (4.9), the angles which we are prospectively associating with θ_{p12} and θ_{p13} would indeed be driven by the neutrino masses via the Yukawa coupling sum $\Sigma G_{\nu_{i\max}}$. This provides preliminary encouragement that, indeed, the PMNS angles are at least predominantly driven by the neutrino masses, and that the failure of (3.3) to match (3.4) was indeed caused by the fact that (3.3) did not yet account for the neutrino masses. And, it provides preliminary validation to the possibility that we can find simple GST relations for quarks but not for leptons because of the difference whereby quarks change generations during beta decay and do not oscillate, wherein leptons do not change generations during beta decay and only do so through oscillation when in a neutrino state, meaning that in any GST-type relations, the neutrino masses have to drive the PMNS angles. Finally, this provides an approximate, preliminary connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses.

Now, we are ready to show how to make the approximate connection in (6.3), (6.4) and (6.5), virtually exact, using the other ‘‘prong’’ of the variance (6.1), namely, the square mass sum $\sum m_{\nu_i}^2$.

7. Neutrino normal ordering square-mass sums and differences

For over four decades following their initial detection [13], it was considered possible that neutrinos might be massless fermions. It is only since the 1998 detection of neutrino oscillations at Super-Kamiokande [2], that neutrinos are now confirmed to have very small, but definitely non-zero, masses. How small, exactly, is an important open question. Based on the most recent reporting [8] noted earlier, the sum of the neutrino masses is approximately between 0.06 eV and 0.12 eV, which is six to seven orders of magnitude smaller than the electron rest mass, and almost 9 orders of magnitude smaller than the muon rest mass. Now, let us see if we can advance our understanding of these neutrino masses, and make some testable predictions.

We start with two pertinent pieces of neutrino mass data: First, again, the latest PDG data reports [14] ‘‘an upper limit of around 0.12 eV’’ and a ‘‘current lower bound of ... 0.06 eV’’ for the sum of the neutrino masses. Second, noting that $\Delta m_{3i}^2 = \Delta m_{31}^2$ for normal ordering data, see Table 3 of [15], the best fit normal ordering data with SK atmospheric data reported in [10], for neutrino square-mass differences $\Delta m_{ij}^2 = m_i^2 - m_j^2$, is:

$$\begin{aligned} 1\sigma : \Delta m_{21}^2 / 10^{-5} \text{eV}^2 &= 7.41_{-0.20}^{+0.21}; & 3\sigma : 6.82 \rightarrow 8.03; \\ 1\sigma : \Delta m_{31}^2 / 10^{-3} \text{eV}^2 &= +2.507_{-0.027}^{+0.026}; & 3\sigma : +2.427 \rightarrow +2.590. \end{aligned} \quad (7.1)$$

Next, we solve $\sum m_{\nu_i}^2 = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + m_3^2$ with $\Delta m_{31}^2 = m_3^2 - m_1^2$ and $\Delta m_{21}^2 = m_2^2 - m_1^2$ as simultaneous equations to obtain the individual squared neutrino masses:

$$\begin{aligned} m_{\nu_1}^2 &= \frac{1}{3} (\sum m_{\nu_i}^2 - \Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) = \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle + \frac{1}{3} (-\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2); \\ m_{\nu_2}^2 &= \frac{1}{3} (\sum m_{\nu_i}^2 + 2\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) = \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle + \frac{1}{3} (2\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2); \\ m_{\nu_3}^2 &= \frac{1}{3} (\sum m_{\nu_i}^2 - \Delta m_{21}^2 + 2\Delta m_{31}^2) = \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle + \frac{1}{3} (-\Delta m_{21}^2 + 2\Delta m_{31}^2). \end{aligned} \quad (7.2)$$

Adding all three of the squared masses in (7.2), it is readily confirmed that $m_{\nu_1}^2 + m_{\nu_2}^2 + m_{\nu_3}^2 = \sum m_{\nu_i}^2$.

Next, we turn to GST relations of the general form $\tan^2 \theta_{ij} = m_i / m_j$ with $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ and $i < j$, in which the masses are those of neutrino eigenstates. Because (7.2) contains square masses, and because we are using normal ordering data for which $m_1 < m_2 < m_3$, we define three GST angles less than 45° by $\tan^4 \theta_{ij} \equiv m_i^2 / m_j^2$. We also add a subscript to $\langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{3} \sum m_{\nu_i}^2$ and write this as $\langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{jk}$, where the jk indexes correspond to indexes on the angles, and therefore, to generation numbers of neutrino masses used to define those angles. Thus, using (7.2), we define:

$$\begin{aligned} \tan^4 \theta_{12} &\equiv m_{\nu_1}^2 / m_{\nu_2}^2 = \left\{ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{12} + \frac{1}{3} (-\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) \right\} / \left\{ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{12} + \frac{1}{3} (2\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) \right\}; \\ \tan^4 \theta_{23} &\equiv m_{\nu_2}^2 / m_{\nu_3}^2 = \left\{ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{23} + \frac{1}{3} (2\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) \right\} / \left\{ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{23} + \frac{1}{3} (-\Delta m_{21}^2 + 2\Delta m_{31}^2) \right\}; \\ \tan^4 \theta_{13} &\equiv m_{\nu_1}^2 / m_{\nu_3}^2 = \left\{ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{13} + \frac{1}{3} (-\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) \right\} / \left\{ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{13} + \frac{1}{3} (-\Delta m_{21}^2 + 2\Delta m_{31}^2) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.3)$$

Then, we restructure each of (7.3) to isolate the $\langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{jk}$, obtaining:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{12} &= \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{12}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{12}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{23} &= - \left\{ (2 + \tan^4 \theta_{23}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{23}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{23}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{23}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle_{13} &= \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{13}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{13}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (7.4)$$

Now, similarly to what was discussed prior to (4.5), the angles defined at (7.3) are candidates for connection to the PMNS angles. But to avoid presupposing which θ_{ij} might end up connecting with which

$\theta_{p_{ij}}$, we need to consider both “native” and “crossover” connections. Let us start with the native assignments $\theta_{12} = \theta_{p_{12}}$, $\theta_{23} = \theta_{p_{23}}$ and $\theta_{13} = \theta_{p_{13}}$, from which (7.4) become:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p_{12}}) &= \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{p_{12}}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{12}}) \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p_{23}}) &= - \left\{ (2 + \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}) \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}) \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{p_{13}}) &= \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{p_{13}}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{13}}) \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}} \Delta m_{31}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (7.5)$$

Then, we calculate (7.5) using the PMNS data in (4.2). Specifically, we regard each of Δm_{21}^2 , Δm_{31}^2 and the pertinent $\tan^4 \theta_p$ in (7.5) to be mutually-independent, and so calculate all eight low-to-high combinations of these three data inputs. Then, below, we show the widest 1σ and 3σ extremes arising from any of these combinations, cast in the form of (7.1) taken from [10], as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 1\sigma : \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p_{12}}) / 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2 &= 8.78_{-0.12}^{+0.13}; & 3\sigma : 8.43 \rightarrow 9.19; \\ 1\sigma : \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p_{23}}) / 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2 &= 5.84_{-1.56}^{+4.02}; & 3\sigma : 2.88 \rightarrow -3.63; \\ 1\sigma : \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{p_{13}}) / 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2 &= 8.62_{-0.10}^{+0.09}; & 3\sigma : 8.33 \rightarrow 8.92. \end{aligned} \quad (7.6)$$

The turn of $\langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ from positive to negative in $3\sigma : 2.88 \rightarrow -3.63$ arises because $3\sigma : 39.7^\circ \rightarrow 51.0^\circ$ for $\theta_{p_{23}}$ in (3.4) passes through 45° , and because $1 - \tan^4 \theta_{23} = 0$ at 45° . Thus, $\langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ passes through a singular point at 45° where the sign turns negative and the mass becomes imaginary. Just below 45° , $\langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ is positive but very large in magnitude, and just above 45° it flips to being negative and very large. At (8.7), the best way to approach this singularity will become clear.

As seen in (6.1), the sum of the squared neutrino masses is $\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2 = 3 \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle$. So to examine (7.6) with +1 energy dimensionality, we can calculate $\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2} = \sqrt{3 \langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle}$ for each of (7.6) to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} 1\sigma : \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{12}}) &= 0.0513_{-0.0004}^{+0.0004} \text{ eV}; & 3\sigma : 0.0503 \text{ eV} \rightarrow 0.0525 \text{ eV}; \\ 1\sigma : \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}}) &= 0.132_{-0.019}^{+0.040} \text{ eV}; & 3\sigma : 0.093 \text{ eV} \rightarrow i \cdot 0.104 \text{ eV}; \\ 1\sigma : \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{13}}) &= 0.0508_{-0.0003}^{+0.0003} \text{ eV}; & 3\sigma : 0.0500 \text{ eV} \rightarrow 0.0517 \text{ eV}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.7)$$

Comparing, we see that the 1σ value of $\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ with a median of 0.132 eV, is an extremely close match to $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{v/E_p} \Delta E = 0.130(7) \text{ eV}$ obtained in (6.3). The medians match at the first two digits, and the 0.130(7) eV spread of (6.3) fits entirely within the 1σ spread of $\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ in (7.7).

8. Formal connection of gravitational weakness with small neutrino masses

If this numeric match is indicative of genuine physics and not merely a numeric accident, then we could equate the middle expression from (7.7) with the leftmost equality in (6.3) and use the tighter numeric bound set by (6.3), and use $m_{\nu i} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} G_{\nu i} v$ to fashion $\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} v \sqrt{\Sigma G_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}})$, thus obtaining:

$$\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} v \sqrt{\Sigma G_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \Delta E \tan \Theta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \Delta E \sqrt{v/E_p} = 0.130(7) \text{ eV}. \quad (8.1)$$

Extracting the middle two terms and reducing this would mean that:

$$\sqrt{\Sigma G_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}}) = \Delta E / \sqrt{v E_p}; \quad \text{i.e.,} \quad \Delta E = \sqrt{v E_p} \sqrt{\Sigma G_{\nu i}^2}(\theta_{p_{23}}). \quad (8.2)$$

So in contrast with the approximation (6.4) which obeys the inequality (6.5), we now see that ΔE would have a direct physical interpretation as the square root of the squared neutrino Yukawa coupling sum

$\Sigma G_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23})$ as established by a native relation in (7.5) to θ_{P23} , times the energy $\sqrt{vE_p}$ obtained from the product of the Fermi vev and the Planck energy.

Moreover, the underlying connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses would become clear if we take the fourth power of (8.1), then use $E_p^2 = \hbar c^5 / G_N$, restore c and isolate G_N , to obtain:

$$G_N = \frac{4(\Sigma E_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23}))^2}{v^2(\Delta E)^4} \hbar c^5 = \frac{(v^2 \Sigma G_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23}))^2}{v^2(\Delta E)^4} \hbar c^5 = \frac{4 \times 0.130(7)^4 \text{ eV}^4}{v^2(\Delta E)^4} \hbar c^5 \equiv \frac{4 \Sigma^4 E_{\nu_i}}{K^4 v^2 (\Delta E)^4} \hbar c^5. \quad (8.3)$$

In the final expression above, mindful of the neutrino rest energy sum ΣE_{ν_i} in (6.3), we define a constant:

$$K \equiv \Sigma E_{\nu_i} / \sqrt{\Sigma E_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23})} = \sqrt{3} \langle E_{\nu_i} \rangle / \sqrt{\langle E_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23}) \rangle} = \Sigma E_{\nu_i} / 0.130(7) \text{ eV}. \quad (8.4)$$

to be the ratio of the mass sum $\Sigma E_{\nu_i} = 3 \langle E_{\nu_i} \rangle$ of the neutrino mass eigenstates, over the square root of the square mass sum $\Sigma E_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23}) = 3 \langle E_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23}) \rangle$ defined though the second relation in (7.5). In other words, this is a ratio between the two ‘‘prongs’’ $\langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle$ and $\langle m_{\nu_i}^2 \rangle$ of the variance in (6.1), with the latter defined by the native GST relation involving θ_{P23} in (7.5). Later, at (20.2), we shall find that this $K = 0.6051^{+0.0240}_{-0.0207}$.

What is demonstrated by (8.1) through (8.4), is that the experimental data for neutrinos and for gravitation supports the **Hypothesis** previewed in the introduction and formally made following (5.3), regarding the interconnection of gravitational weakness with smaller neutrino masses, within experimental errors. Moreover, were we to set the neutrino masses and thus the square mass sum $\Sigma E_{\nu_i 23}^2(\theta_{P23})$ in (8.3) to zero, we would actualize **Corollaries 1 and 2**: Newton’s constant would become zero, gravitation would not exist, and by breaking symmetry to reveal massive from massless neutrinos, we would simultaneously give rise to gravitation. Additionally, (8.3) satisfies **Corollary 4**, whereby Newton’s constant would become a formal parameter of the standard model. But, because (8.3) specifies Newton’s constant as a function of other parameters arising in the standard model, this twenty-sixth (26) parameter would not be independent of the other twenty-five (25). Finally, this expression of Newton’s constant as a function of renormalizable parameters from the standard model, and the fact that this constant would arise from spontaneous symmetry breaking, would produce a long-sought renormalizable theory of gravitation, in accord with **Corollary 3**. We shall examine this particular point in further detail, in the next section.

Once we adopt (8.1) through (8.4) as genuine dynamical connections among neutrino masses and mixings and gravitation, we give rise to all of the foundational new physics summarized in the previous paragraph. If we invert this statement to as to assert that this new physics is well-recognized to be desirable, then to implement this desirable new physics, all we need to do is adopt (8.1) through (8.4) as genuine dynamical physical connections, which adaptation would be uncontradicted by known experimental data. Finally, the numerical upshot of (8.1) through (8.4) is to establish an exact connection between $\Delta E \sim 40.587 \text{ MeV}$ in (4.7) and the $\sim 0.130 \text{ eV}$ energy of (8.1) which as we see from (6.3) using (5.3), are interrelated by the ratio $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{v / E_p} = 3.175470(18) \times 10^{-9}$. From a statistical standpoint, the dynamic connection highlighted by the foregoing ratio is exact across almost *nine orders of magnitude*, and as will later be detailed in **Section 30**, it can be stated with confidence well in excess of six-sigma, that this connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is no numeric accident. So when we combine the desirable new physics that results from regarding (8.1) through (8.4) as genuine physical connections with well-beyond six-sigma statistical confidence that these are not numeric accidents, the justification for regarding (8.1) through (8.4) as genuine physical connections is compelling.

Accordingly, we now formally adopt (8.1) as a genuine dynamic physics connection that is no accident, and accordingly adopt (8.2) through (8.4) which are derived therefrom. As we shall now show, in addition to all of the above, once we have adopted (8.1) through (8.4) as genuine physics connections, it becomes possible for the first time to understand the quantum-level gravitational interactions between elementary particles, and to develop a renormalizable theory of gravitation.

Before we conclude **PART I**, however, let us take a few more steps that will later help us to pinpoint the individual neutrino mass eigenstate values much more precisely than these are known at present. First, we square (8.1) and use $\langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{23} = \frac{1}{3} \Sigma m_{\nu i 23}^2$ to obtain:

$$\langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{23} (\theta_{P23}) = \frac{1}{6} (\Delta E)^2 (v / E_p) = \frac{1}{3} (0.130(7) \text{ eV})^2. \quad (8.5)$$

Then, with the native assignment $\theta_{23} = \theta_{P23}$, we use (8.5) in the second line of (7.3) and reduce to write:

$$\tan^4 \theta_{P23} = \frac{m_2^2}{m_3^2} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} (\Delta m)^2 (v / E_p) + 2\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2}{\frac{1}{2} (\Delta m)^2 (v / E_p) - \Delta m_{21}^2 + 2\Delta m_{31}^2}. \quad (8.6)$$

Upon calculating (8.6) using the square of (8.1) and the mass data in (7.1) using the largest spreads from all eight high-to-low combinations of the variables in (8.6), we obtain:

$$1\sigma : \theta_{P23} = 42.08_{-0.37}^{+0.32\circ}; \quad 3\sigma : 41.63^\circ \rightarrow 42.46^\circ. \quad (8.7)$$

Comparing with the PMNS data in (3.4) which is only reported to only the first decimal place, we see that the median of θ_{P23} is slightly raised by about 0.1° , due to the data match obtained at (8.1) and adopted as physically meaningful for the reasons articulated following (8.4). But the 1σ spread has been narrowed from 2.0° down to 0.7° , and the 3σ spread very substantially narrowed by more than tenfold, from 11.3° to about 0.8° . Moreover, the problem identified at (7.6) whereby an imaginary energy appeared on the second line of (7.7), is resolved, because the 3σ upper bound at 42.4° removes the statistical possibility of θ_{P23} reaching 45° . Finally, the 3σ spread in (8.7) fits entirely inside the 1σ spread of (3.4).

Finally, with the adoption of (8.1) we implicitly adopt the prospective PMNS angle connections in (4.9) which were part of how we reached (8.1). So, because we narrowed the spreads of θ_{P12} and θ_{P13} at (4.9), then substantially narrowed the spread of θ_{P23} in (8.7), we now assemble this updated, tightened PMNS data into a consistent form that can be used for calculations going forward. Specifically, following (4.6) we saw that the closest possible simultaneous fits for both θ_{P12} and θ_{P13} occurred at about 1.65σ , which renders obsolete the 1σ spreads in (3.4). In other words, it is simply not possible for both θ_{P12} and θ_{P13} to have actual values inside of their reported 1σ spreads in (3.4). So, the tightened prospective values in (4.9) are based on keeping both these angles simultaneously inside their 3σ spreads from (3.4). At the same time, as noted, (8.7) tightens θ_{P23} by more than tenfold, whereby the 3σ spread of (8.7) fits entirely inside the 1σ spread of (3.4). Therefore, for consistency with (4.9), let us simply use the 3σ spread of (8.7) going forward. Thus, from here, we shall calculate neutrino data using what are now all the 3σ spreads:

$$\theta_{P12} = 32.03_{-0.73}^{+0.70\circ}; \quad \theta_{P13} = 8.68_{-0.24}^{+0.23\circ}; \quad \theta_{P23} = 42.08_{-0.45}^{+0.38\circ}. \quad (8.8)$$

PART II: GRAVITATIONAL INTERACTIONS OF ELEMENTARY PARTICLES

9. Lagrangian for long range gravitational interactions of elementary particle quanta

The Einstein equation with cosmological constant is $-\kappa T^{\mu\nu} = R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} R + g^{\mu\nu} \Lambda$. With $\Lambda = 0$ and in the linear Newtonian approximation this becomes $-\kappa T^{\mu\nu} = \partial_\sigma \partial^\sigma \phi^{\mu\nu}$, where the gravitational field written as $\phi^{\mu\nu} = \mathcal{E}_{L,R}^{\mu\nu}(\mathbf{q}) \exp(-iq_\sigma x^\sigma / \hbar)$ may be understood to represent a massless spin 2 graviton with energy-momentum $cq^\sigma = (E, c\mathbf{q})$ and two helicity states, right and left, represented with a polarization tensor $\mathcal{E}_{L,R}^{\mu\nu}$. The Einstein constant $\kappa = 8\pi G_N / c^4$ contains Newton's constant G_N , which, using (8.3) and (8.4) and $\Sigma E_{\nu i} = 3 \langle E_{\nu i} \rangle$, may be written in terms of $\hbar c$ and several energies as:

$$\kappa = \frac{8\pi G_N}{c^4} = \frac{32\pi \Sigma^4 E_{\nu i}}{K^4 v^2 (\Delta E)^4} \hbar c = \frac{2592\pi \langle E_{\nu i} \rangle^4}{K^4 v^2 (\Delta E)^4} \hbar c. \quad (9.1)$$

The energy tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ has dimensions of energy-per-volume, that is, energy density. And $\kappa T^{\mu\nu}$ has dimensions of 1/area as do $R^{\mu\nu}$ and $\partial_\sigma \partial^\sigma \phi^{\mu\nu}$. Any Lagrangian (density) in spacetime may be written with

+4 energy dimensionality. So, showing all natural constants, with $\hbar c$ having energy-times-length dimension, the scalar constructs $\hbar^3 c^3 T^{\mu\nu} \phi_{\mu\nu}$ and $\hbar^3 c^3 T \phi$ formed from the foregoing two tensors and their traces, will have a +4 energy dimensionality suitable for use in a Lagrangian.

Next, because $\phi^{\mu\nu} = \varepsilon_{L,R}^{\mu\nu} \exp(-iq_\sigma x^\sigma / \hbar)$, we easily find that $\hbar^2 \kappa T^{\mu\nu} = q_\sigma q^\sigma \phi^{\mu\nu}$ is the linear field equation in momentum space, whereby $\phi^{\mu\nu} = \hbar^2 \kappa T^{\mu\nu} / q_\sigma q^\sigma$ and $\phi = \hbar^2 \kappa T / q_\sigma q^\sigma$. So, $\hbar^3 c^3 T^{\mu\nu} \phi_{\mu\nu} = \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 T^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu} / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma$ and the trace product $\hbar^3 c^3 T \phi = \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 T^2 / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma$.

Also, in electrodynamics, the Lagrangian density $\mathcal{L} = -J^\mu A_\mu = -J^\mu g_{\mu\nu} A^\nu$ contains a current density source term J^μ and the electromagnetic field A^ν , each of which is a spacetime four-vector, with a single $g_{\mu\nu}$ used to lower spacetime indexes. But the gravitational energy density source $T^{\mu\nu}$ and field $\phi^{\mu\nu}$ are both symmetric rank-2 tensors. So, in general, any Lagrangian constructed by analogy to electrodynamics will have the form $\mathcal{L} = -\hbar^3 c^3 T^{\mu\nu} (a g_{\mu\nu} g_{\alpha\beta} + b g_{\mu\alpha} g_{\beta\nu} + c g_{\mu\beta} g_{\nu\alpha}) \phi^{\alpha\beta} = -\hbar^3 c^3 [(b+c) T^{\mu\nu} \phi_{\mu\nu} + a T \phi]$, where a , b and c are constants. But it is also known, see, e.g., section 1.5 of [16], that the sum over spin states for a massless graviton is $\sum \mathcal{E}_{\mu\nu}^{(s)} \mathcal{E}_{\alpha\beta}^{(s)} = g_{\mu\alpha} g_{\nu\beta} + g_{\mu\beta} g_{\nu\alpha} - \frac{2}{3} g_{\mu\nu} g_{\alpha\beta}$, whereby $a = -\frac{2}{3}$ and $b = c = 1$, which applies over distances comparatively small with respect to cosmological scales. And as detailed in section VIII.1 of [16], in flat spacetime over distances exceeding the Vainshtein length [17] at which a scalar polarization becomes effective, these become $a = -1$ and $b = c = 1$. Also, in either event, we must include the determinant square root $\sqrt{-g}$ required for taking variations in curved spacetime, though for the Newtonian approximation, $\sqrt{-g} = 1$. So, the most general form of the linear Newtonian approximation Lagrangian below or above the Vainshtein length, is:

$$\mathcal{L} = -2\hbar^3 c^3 (T^{\mu\nu} \phi_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} a T \phi) = -2\kappa \hbar^5 c^5 (T^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} a T^2) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma. \quad (9.2)$$

Now, consider the perfect fluid tensor $T^{\mu\nu} = (\rho_0 + p) u^\mu u^\nu - p g^{\mu\nu}$ which, for a pressure $p = 0$ reduces to the dust tensor $T^{\mu\nu} = \rho_0 u^\mu u^\nu$. To start out simply, let us use the dust tensor. Viewed at rest in its own frame, the dust $T^{00} = \rho_0$, and all other components are zero. Additionally, in a spacetime that may be approximated via $g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ to flat spacetime, the trace $T = \rho_0 \eta_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu = \rho_0$. So for sub-cosmological distances where $a = -\frac{2}{3}$, with a cosmological constant $\Lambda = 0$, in a spacetime that is approximately flat, and in the rest frame of an energy tensor for dust, the Lagrangian in (9.2), with an overall minus sign which is what causes gravitation to be an attractive interaction, again see section 1.5 of [16], simplifies to:

$$\mathcal{L} = -2(1 + \frac{1}{2} a) \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \rho_0^2 / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma = -\frac{4}{3} \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \rho_0^2 / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma = -\frac{4}{3} \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \rho_{0(1)} \rho_{0(2)} / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma. \quad (9.3)$$

In the final expression we have set $\rho_0^2 = \rho_{0(1)} \rho_{0(2)}$ to distinguish the interacting energy tensor sources as with $G_N m_1 m_2$ in the numerator of Newton's law.

Now, we substitute the Einstein constant (9.1) into (9.3) for $a = -\frac{2}{3}$, and define $g_K \equiv 12/K$, to obtain:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\hbar^6 c^6 \frac{3456\pi \langle E_{vi} \rangle^4}{K^4 v^2 (\Delta E)^4} \frac{\rho_{0(1)} \rho_{0(2)}}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma} = -\pi \hbar^6 c^6 \frac{g_K^4 \langle E_{vi} \rangle^4}{6v^2 (\Delta E)^4} \frac{\rho_{0(1)} \rho_{0(2)}}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma}. \quad (9.4)$$

By simple algebraic restructuring, we may then rewrite (9.4) as:

$$\frac{6\mathcal{L}}{\pi \hbar^6 c^6} = - \left[\rho_{0(1)} \frac{1}{v (\Delta E)^2} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{v (\Delta E)^2} \rho_{0(2)} \right] \right]. \quad (9.5)$$

In the standard model, the rest energies $E = mc^2$ of all massive elementary particles can be specified in relation to the Fermi vev v which sits in the denominators of the first and third bracketed terms, by constant factors times their couplings. Specifically, for the W and Z and Higgs bosons, and the fermions:

$$\frac{1}{v} = \frac{g_w}{2E_w} = \frac{g_z}{2E_z} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\lambda_h}}{E_h} = \frac{G_f}{\sqrt{2}E_f} \equiv \frac{g_p}{K_p E_p}. \quad (9.6)$$

For any massive elementary particle p , (9.6) includes a generic definition of that particle's coupling g_p , its rest energy $E_p = m_p c^2$, and a constant K_p seen in (9.6) by which that particle's coupling-to-mass ratio is linked with the Fermi vev v . We may then use (9.6) to write (9.5) as:

$$\frac{6K_{(1)}K_{(2)}\mathcal{L}}{\pi\hbar^6 c^6} = - \left[\rho_{0(1)} g_{(1)} \frac{1}{(\Delta E)^2 E_{(1)}} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{(\Delta E)^2 E_{(2)}} g_{(2)} \rho_{0(2)} \right], \quad (9.7)$$

which includes migrating p in (9.6) to $p \rightarrow (1)$ or $p \rightarrow (2)$ for the two interacting energy densities.

The next step involves taking a close look in (9.7) at the $1/(\Delta E)^2 E_{(p)}$ terms in the first and third brackets, which have energy dimensions of -3 . Recall that the Dirac equation $(i\partial - m)\psi = 0$ for spin-half fermions leads to these fermions having propagator lines with energy dimension of -1 , and that the free-particle Klein-Gordon-Proca equation $(g^{\mu\nu}(\partial_\sigma \partial^\sigma + m^2) - \partial^\mu \partial^\nu)B_\mu = 0$ for massive spin 1 vector bosons leads to these bosons having propagator lines with energy dimension of -2 . These dimensions are determined by the inverse of the momentum space operators in the field equations. As detailed in **PART I** of [18], it is possible to develop a field equation $(g^{\mu\nu}(i\partial \partial_\sigma \partial^\sigma + m^3) - i\partial \partial^\mu \partial^\nu)\Psi_\nu = 0$ for a spin 3/2 gravitino Ψ_ν , which equation is a composite of the Dirac and Klein-Gordon equations for spin $1/2$ and spin 1. And, for gravitinos, because the momentum space operator has mass dimensionality of $+3$, the propagator lines have energy dimension of -3 , just like the terms $1/(\Delta E)^2 E_{(1)}$ in (9.7). As a result, the terms $1/(\Delta E)^2 E_{(p)}$ above can be associated with massive gravitinos having a rest energy given by:

$$E_{\Psi(p)} = (\Delta E)^{2/3} E_{(p)}^{1/3}. \quad (9.8)$$

What this means, in addition to $1/(\Delta E)^2 E_{(p)}$ in (9.7) corresponding to propagator lines for gravitinos, is that *there is a distinct gravitino with a distinct rest energy given by (9.8) associated with each and every massive elementary particle p* . In this way, we uncover from the empirical connection of (8.3), a supersymmetry between massive elementary particles and massive gravitinos, whereby the elementary particles p each have gravitino superpartners $\Psi_{\nu(p)}$ with masses determined by their own particle masses, and by ΔE . Note also, that this advances the significance of the energy shift ΔE in (4.7): Not only does ΔE work to fit the PMNS angles seen in (4.9) and to interconnect gravitational weakness with small neutrino masses by directly establishing the Yukawa couplings for neutrinos via (8.2). Now, by revealing a supersymmetry between gravitinos and all other massive elementary particles which emerges from empirical data, not theoretical conjecture, this ΔE is seen in (9.8) to operate as a $2/3$ -power ‘‘anchor energy’’ which interconnects the energy of each gravitino type to the mass of its elementary particle superpartner. So with (9.8) we can advance (9.7) to:

$$\frac{6K_{(1)}K_{(2)}\mathcal{L}}{\pi\hbar^6 c^6} = - \left[\rho_{0(1)} g_{(1)} \frac{1}{E_{\Psi(1)}^3} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{E_{\Psi(2)}^3} g_{(2)} \rho_{0(2)} \right]. \quad (9.9)$$

Finally, neutrinos themselves oscillate between their three eigenstates under the operation of the PMNS matrix and its three real angles and one complex phase. So, if one is to talk about the rest mass of a neutrino, the average / expectation value $\langle E_{vi} \rangle$ of all three mass eigenstates provides the best way to represent the ‘‘gravitational charge’’ a.k.a. mass of that neutrino. Accordingly, we may use the $\langle E_{vi} \rangle$ in (9.7) to draw propagator lines for neutrinos, while $g_K = 12/K$ based on (8.4) which is the ratio of the two prongs of the variance for the neutrino masses, may be regarded as a dimensionless coupling for these neutrinos.

10. Long range gravitational interactions of elementary particle quanta via gravitinos, neutrinos and gravitons

Now, we have all the information necessary to convert (9.9) into a Feynman diagram for the gravitational interaction between two massive elementary particles with energy densities given by $\rho_0 = E\psi^\dagger\psi$ in accordance with their quantum mechanical wavefunctions ψ . On first impression, (9.9) looks like a product of three distinct Feynman diagrams, one for each of the bracketed interaction terms. The first bracket houses the source energy density $\rho_{0(1)}$ and its coupling $g_{(1)}$ to its own gravitino superpartner $\Psi_{\mu(1)}$, followed by the coupling for this gravitino via the coupling g_K to the neutrino represented by $\langle E_{\nu i} \rangle$. The third bracket houses the same entities as the first, but in reverse order, and for particles and couplings (2) rather than (1). And the middle bracket houses the propagator $(c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma)^{-1}$ for a graviton, $\phi^{\mu\nu}$ which is seen to be mediating the interaction between two neutrinos with expectation masses $\langle E_{\nu i} \rangle$, coupled again by g_K .

However, the three Feynman diagrams that seem to be multiplied together in (9.9) can actually be combined into a single diagram, because the last term in the first bracket and the first term in the second bracket are identical terms combined to form $g_K \langle E_{\nu i} \rangle \langle E_{\nu i} \rangle g_K$. Likewise for the last term in the second and the first term in the third. So, these can each be drawn as neutrino loops. As a result, the three bracketed terms can all be connected together, and we can draw (9.9) with the Feynman diagram of **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Feynman diagram illustrating (9.7) for the gravitational interaction between two massive elementary particle energy densities

Working from left to right in **Figure 1**, the energy density $\rho_0 = E\psi^\dagger\psi$ for elementary particle (1) begins its gravitational interaction with that of elementary particle (2) by first emitting its superpartner gravitino $\Psi_{\mu(1)}$ with a rest energy given by (9.8), to which it couples at the vertex by the dimensionless Yukawa coupling $g_{(1)}$. This gravitino then decays into a neutrino loop containing a neutrino / antineutrino pair. This loop then decays into a graviton. Because the graviton is massless and so propagates at the speed of light, there is no limit to the range over which this graviton can travel, which is illustrated by the break in the graviton line in the middle of **Figure 1**. But eventually, as it prepares to interact with the energy density on the very right, the graviton decays into a second neutrino loop with the same coupling properties as the first, and this particle / antiparticle pair annihilates into another massive gravitino, now the superpartner of particle (2). Finally, this gravitino interacts with the particle (2) energy density, here, with the coupling strength $g_{(2)}$.

What we learn from **Figure 1** is that elementary particles can never interact directly with gravitons. Rather, at the quantum particle level, a first particle begins its gravitational interaction by emitting its superpartner gravitino, which then decays into a neutrino loop, which then decays into a graviton that can carry the gravitational interaction over unlimited distances. As it approaches the second particle and before it can interact therewith, the graviton must first decay into another neutrino loop, which in turn decays into the superpartner gravitino for the second particle, which finally interacts with the second particle. In this way, the gravitinos and the neutrino loops act as “guards” for the graviton, while the gravitino is the “interface” particle through which energies directly gravitate. Because the neutrinos have such small masses, and *because they always intercede* along with gravitinos as part of graviton “guard” at the quantum level, the

neutrino loops create a “cliff” which greatly diminishes the strength of gravitation simply because the neutrino masses are so small. In other words, if neutrinos always intercede in all gravitational interactions between elementary particle field quanta, then given the small masses of the neutrinos relative to all other elementary particles, it is no wonder that gravitation is very weak in relation to all other interactions. *This is how the interconnection of gravitational weakness with small neutrino masses first made at (8.1) through (8.4), actually works at the quantum / particle level.*

As was also noted following (6.2), it was the use of the GST variant $\tan^2 \Theta \equiv \nu / E_p$ which resulted in our employing a ratio of these two energies that varies with the *fourth root* of the Newton and Fermi constants to connect ΔE with the neutrino mass scale. When this was inverted to isolate the Newton constant at (8.3), this caused the *fourth power* term $\Sigma^4 E_{\nu_i}$ to appear in the denominator, and $\langle E_{\nu_i} \rangle^4$ to appear in (9.4). This in turn brought about the two neutrino loop cliffs in **Figure 1** which weaken the gravitational interaction based on the small neutrino masses. So, in a very direct way, these neutrino loops and their weakening of gravitational interactions, are a direct consequence of having used the GST variant $\tan^2 \Theta \equiv \nu / E_p$ to uncover the relationship between ΔE and the neutrino mass scale.

To facilitate compact discussion, let us drop the $\psi^\dagger \psi$, with the understanding that this density establishes the quantum uncertainty probability for where the rest energy E in $(E\psi^\dagger\psi)_{(p)}$ is located. Because this interaction is gravitational, neither $E_{(1)}$ nor $E_{(2)}$ changes its character at its vertex with a gravitino in the manner that, e.g., a particle would change from an isospin-up or down fermion into an isospin-down or up fermion at a beta decay vertex. So, the overall interaction of **Figure 1** may be concisely represented as $E_{(1)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}E_{(2)}$. The distinct sequence of interactions in **Figure 1** may then be concisely stated by:

$$E_{(1)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(1)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\nu\bar{\nu}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\phi^{\mu\nu}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\nu\bar{\nu}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(2)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}E_{(2)}. \quad (10.1)$$

In the first step, $E_{(1)}$ emits its gravitino partner $\Psi_{(1)}$ via the interaction $E_{(1)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(1)}$, with a vertex coupling $g_{(1)\Psi}$. Next, the $\Psi_{(1)}$ gravitino decays into a neutrino / antineutrino pair via $\Psi_{(1)} \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$. Then, this pair decays into a massless spin 2 graviton via $\nu\bar{\nu} \rightarrow \phi^{\mu\nu}$. Once this occurs, there is no limit to how far the graviton can travel before it approaches $E_{(2)}$; indeed, $E_{(1)}$ and $E_{(2)}$ can be separated by distances on cosmological scales. Then, as the graviton approaches $E_{(2)}$, a direct interaction is not possible. Rather, the graviton must first decay into another neutrino / antineutrino pair via $\phi^{\mu\nu} \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$. Then the pair annihilates into the second gravitino via $\nu\bar{\nu} \rightarrow \Psi_{(2)}$. Finally, this gravitino meets up at a vertex with $E_{(2)}$ via the interaction $E_{(2)}\Psi_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(2)}$ with a coupling $g_{(2)\Psi}$. At all the neutrino vertexes, the coupling is $g_K = 12 / K$ with K as defined in (8.4). Later, at (20.2) we shall determine that $K = 0.6051_{-0.0207}^{+0.0240}$. Importantly, because of the genesis of gravitinos in (9.7) via (9.8) into (9.9), as seen in **Figure 1** and (10.1), *each massive elementary particle can only emit or absorb its own gravitino superpartner.*

Finally, **Figure 1** shows how disassembling the Newton / Einstein constants into the energies and couplings of (9.1) and then placing them into the gravitational Lagrangian of (9.4) and (9.5) in view of the coupling relations (9.6), yields a long-sought *renormalizable theory of gravitation* in accordance with **Corollary 3**. This is because each and every element of Lagrangian in (9.9) contains energies and couplings we can renormalize by applying the renormalization group equations and related principles of the renormalizable standard models of electroweak and strong particle physics interactions. In other words, the dimensional Newton constant is replaced using (8.3) and (9.6) with the conversion constant $\hbar c$ and a set of masses and couplings that are all renormalizable, meaning that the Lagrangian for the gravitational interactions also becomes renormalizable. So, if the foundational new physics we are pursuing includes obtaining a renormalizable theory of gravitation, and if the connections at (8.1) through (8.4) provide the empirical basis for exactly doing

so, this provides extremely strong support for the view that these dynamic connections between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses are genuine connections motivated by widely-desired new physics, not mere accidents.

11. Rest energies of the gravitino superpartners for the massive elementary particles

Because (9.8) predicts the existence of a massive gravitino superpartner for each massive elementary particle which is seen among the interacting particles in **Figure 1**, and because these gravitinos are presumably observable under the right circumstances, let us now use (9.8) including the gravitino “anchor” energy ΔE to calculate the rest energies $E_{\Psi(p)}$ of each of these superpartner gravitinos.

For the gravitinos which obtain their masses from the W and Z bosons, we use $E_W = 80.377 \pm 0.012 \text{ GeV}$ and $E_Z = 91.1876 \pm 0.0021 \text{ GeV}$ [19] and ΔE originally calculated at (4.7) as will later be tightened at (20.3) to $\Delta E = 40.857^{+0.602}_{-0.714} \text{ MeV}$, to find that that these gravitino masses are:

$$E_{\Psi(W)} = \sqrt[3]{E_W (\Delta E)^2} = 511.939^{+5.045}_{-6.006} \text{ MeV}, \quad (11.1)$$

$$E_{\Psi(Z)} = \sqrt[3]{E_Z (\Delta E)^2} = 533.933^{+5.239}_{-6.242} \text{ MeV}. \quad (11.2)$$

In the same vein, for the Higgs boson with $E_h = 125.25 \pm 0.17 \text{ GeV}$, we obtain a gravitino partner with:

$$E_{\Psi(h)} = \sqrt[3]{E_h (\Delta E)^2} = 593.52^{+6.09}_{-7.20} \text{ MeV}. \quad (11.3)$$

Similarly, there is a gravitino mass associated with each of the six quarks and leptons. For quarks, using the data in [20] including the direct measurement data for the top quark, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\Psi(u)} &= 15.33^{+1.24}_{-0.81} \text{ MeV}; & E_{\Psi(c)} &= 128.46^{+1.94}_{-2.17} \text{ MeV}; & E_{\Psi(t)} &= 658.03^{+6.84}_{-8.07} \text{ MeV}; \\ E_{\Psi(d)} &= 19.83^{+0.86}_{-0.47} \text{ MeV}; & E_{\Psi(s)} &= 53.82^{+2.15}_{-1.28} \text{ MeV}; & E_{\Psi(b)} &= 191.09^{+2.33}_{-2.53} \text{ MeV}. \end{aligned} \quad (11.4)$$

For the charged leptons, using the data in [9] reproduced in (3.1), we obtain:

$$E_{\Psi(e)} = 9.484^{+0.093}_{-0.111} \text{ MeV}; \quad E_{\Psi(\mu)} = 56.080^{+0.550}_{-0.655} \text{ MeV}; \quad E_{\Psi(\tau)} = 143.679^{+1.412}_{-1.682} \text{ MeV}. \quad (11.5)$$

As to the neutrinos, using the tightened normal ordered masses which will be calculated at (18.1) we find:

$$E_{\Psi(\nu 1)} = 27.25^{+1.43}_{-1.47} \text{ keV}; \quad E_{\Psi(\nu 2)} = 29.17^{+1.26}_{-1.28} \text{ keV}; \quad E_{\Psi(\nu 3)} = 44.14^{+0.77}_{-0.83} \text{ keV}. \quad (11.6)$$

Much of the PDG data used to obtain these gravitino masses is reported at particular renormalization scales in the $\overline{\text{MS}}$ scheme. So, the gravitino masses would be at the same scale in the same scheme. But, as these vary with the cubed root of the associated particle masses, their scale dependence is much less pronounced. Clearly, as will shortly be discussed, it would be desirable to experimentally test these mass predictions.

12. Full widths of the W , Z and Higgs boson and top quark gravitino superpartners

As seen in (11.1) through (11.6), the gravitino partners of the W , Z and Higgs bosons, and of the top quark, are the four heaviest gravitinos. Moreover, because of the weak equivalence principle whereby all types of energy couple indistinguishably through gravitation, it is to be expected that the gravitino full widths $\Gamma_{\Psi(p)}$ will be related to those $\Gamma_{(p)}$ of their elementary particle superpartners via the “anchor” energy shift ΔE , by a relation identical in form to (9.8), namely:

$$\Gamma_{\Psi(p)} = (\Delta E)^{2/3} \Gamma_{(p)}^{1/3}. \quad (12.1)$$

We can use then $\hbar c = 197.3269804 \text{ MeV fm}$ and $c = 299792458 \text{ m/s}$ [11] to write Planck’s constant as $\hbar = 6.58211956753095 \times 10^{-22} \text{ MeV s}$. Then, using (12.1) and the full width particle data in [19] and [20] (assuming equal on- and off-shell couplings for the Higgs), and $\Delta E = 40.857^{+0.602}_{-0.714} \text{ MeV}$ as later tightened in (20.3), we may calculate that the $\Gamma_{\tau\Psi(p)}$ for these gravitinos, as well as their associated mean lives $\bar{\tau}_{\Psi(p)} = \hbar / \Gamma_{\tau\Psi(p)}$ and maximum ranges $c\bar{\tau}_{\Psi(p)}$ at light speed c , are as follows:

$$\Gamma_{\tau\Psi(W)} = 151.546_{-2.783}^{+2.506} \text{ MeV}; \quad \bar{\tau}_{\Psi(W)} = 4.343_{-0.081}^{+0.071} \times 10^{-24} \text{ s}; \quad c\bar{\tau}_{\Psi(W)} = 1.302_{-0.021}^{+0.024} \text{ fm}, \quad (12.2)$$

$$\Gamma_{\tau\Psi(Z)} = 160.902_{-1.929}^{+1.627} \text{ MeV}; \quad \bar{\tau}_{\Psi(Z)} = 4.091_{-0.041}^{+0.050} \times 10^{-24} \text{ s}; \quad c\bar{\tau}_{\Psi(Z)} = 1.226_{-0.012}^{+0.015} \text{ fm}, \quad (12.3)$$

$$\Gamma_{\tau\Psi(h)} = 17.481_{-4.060}^{+3.791} \text{ MeV}; \quad \bar{\tau}_{\Psi(h)} = 3.765_{-0.671}^{+1.139} \times 10^{-23} \text{ s}; \quad c\bar{\tau}_{\Psi(h)} = 11.288_{-2.012}^{+3.415} \text{ fm}, \quad (12.4)$$

$$\Gamma_{\tau\Psi(t)} = 133.333_{-6.371}^{+7.063} \text{ MeV}; \quad \bar{\tau}_{\Psi(t)} = 4.937_{-0.248}^{+0.248} \times 10^{-24} \text{ s}; \quad c\bar{\tau}_{\Psi(t)} = 1.480_{-0.074}^{+0.074} \text{ fm}. \quad (12.5)$$

Of course, these rather massive gravitinos should be expected to travel well below the speed of light, so their actual median ranges are likely be somewhat shorter than 1 femtometer.

Using (12.2) through (12.5) and the related rest masses (11.1) through (11.4), we also calculate the width-to-rest energy ratio $\gamma \equiv \Gamma / mc^2$ for each:

$$\gamma_{\tau\Psi(W)} = 0.2960 \pm 0.0020, \quad (12.6)$$

$$\gamma_{\tau\Psi(Z)} = 0.3014 \pm 0.0001, \quad (12.7)$$

$$\gamma_{\tau\Psi(h)} = 0.0295_{-0.0066}^{+0.0060}, \quad (12.8)$$

$$\gamma_{\Psi\tau(t)} = 0.2026_{-0.0073}^{+0.0085}. \quad (12.9)$$

Note that these gravitino widths in relation to the median rest mass are much broader than they are for their superpartner bosons and the top quark. This is because the fractional ratios for the gravitinos run with the cubed roots of the same ratios for these superpartners, $\gamma_{\Psi(p)} = \gamma_{(p)}^{1/3}$.

13. Two gravitational interaction variants: long range and weak; short range and strong

It is widely believed, even if experimental observation has not been possible, that gravitation is transmitted through the massless spin 2 field quanta known as gravitons. But what we see in **Figure 1** is that a gravitational interaction begins with the emission of a spin 3/2 gravitino via $E_{(1)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(1)}$ in (10.1), and terminates with the absorption of a second gravitino via $\Psi_{(2)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(2)}$. *The gravitons do not and cannot interact directly with the elementary particle energies. Only gravitinos can interact directly. And the only elementary particle that can interact directly with a graviton, is a neutrino, via the loops in Figure 1.* So, because the long range of gravitational interactions with which are familiar requires transmission of gravitons, and because very-light neutrinos always intercede via the interaction chain $\nu\bar{\nu} \rightarrow \phi^{\mu\nu} \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$ in (10.1), the long range gravitational interactions which are everpresent in our daily life experiences, are always very weak.

But this also points to a different, previously-unknown variant of the gravitational interaction, which is quite strong and conceivably could be detected in particle physics experiments at LHC and other high-energy facilities: Suppose we now probe down to nuclear scales to examine – not the strong or electroweak – but the *gravitational* interactions between two nearby elementary particles. The gravitino partners of the massive elementary particles are also massive as seen as seen in (11.1) through (11.6). And particularly for the W and Z bosons and the top quark, their maximum ranges (12.2), (12.3) and (12.5) at light speed are between 1.2 and 1.5 fm, which means that their typical ranges will be shorter than the ~1 femtometer radius of a baryon.

So, once these gravitinos reach the end of their short lives and traverse their short ranges they can decay via $\Psi_{(1)} \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$ and initiate a long-range gravitational interaction following the next decay $\nu\bar{\nu} \rightarrow \phi^{\mu\nu}$, as seen in (10.1) and **Figure 1**. This lets the graviton “out of the barn” after the interaction strength drops off the neutrino mass-induced “cliff.” But, the final step in (10.1) is $\Psi_{(2)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(2)}$. So, there appear to be three other options for how this interaction can progress in the Newtonian linear approximation:

First, rather than decay into a graviton, the first neutrino loop can decay back into a second gravitino which in turn decays into a second elementary particle via the interaction:

$$E_{(1)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(1)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\nu\bar{\nu}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(2)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}E_{(2)}. \quad (13.1)$$

Here the gravitational interaction between $E_{(1)}$ and $E_{(2)}$ is weakened by the single $\nu\bar{\nu}$ loop, but only half as much as by the two loop interaction of (10.1) and **Figure 1**. This interaction (13.1) will also not have the long range of the familiar gravitational interaction, because there is no graviton involved. Its range will be determined by how far the neutrino / antineutrino loop pair travels before it decays back into a gravitino. This is a form of “semi-weak, semi-short-range” gravitation. Knowing that neutrinos, uniquely among all particles, are an oscillating superposition of eigenstates, note that the core reaction $\Psi_{(1)} \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu} \rightarrow \Psi_{(2)}$ in (13.1) also creates an oscillation of sorts between gravitino states. This may help explain why the neutrinos appear to be the only particle that can interact with all gravitino types, and that can interact directly with gravitons.

Second, as pointed out following (10.1), each massive elementary particle can only emit or absorb its own gravitino superpartner. But, this will only happen if $E_{(2)}$ is very close to $E_{(1)}$ because of the short ranges that emerge from the weak equivalence relation (12.1) exemplified for W, Z, h and t by (12.2) through (12.5). In this event, it would be possible for the gravitino to simply be absorbed by $E_{(2)}$, with a truncated interaction:

$$E_{(1)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(1=2)}E_{(2)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}E_{(2)}. \quad (13.2)$$

This interaction is mediated by a single gravitino Ψ , and so can only occur if $E_{(1)}$ and $E_{(2)}$ are the same type of particle. For example, if both are electrons or both are identical quark flavors, e.g., up, or both are W bosons; which is why we have the subscript 1=2 in (13.2). The key feature of (13.2) is that *because the neutrinos are removed from interceding in the gravitational interaction, this short-range gravitational variant is much stronger*.

Third, because a gravitino can only be emitted or absorbed by its elementary particle superpartner, in a variant of (13.2), an elementary particle should also be able to emit its own gravitino partner, then simply reabsorb that same gravitino an instant later in a gravitational backreaction [21] summarized by:

$$E_{(1)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}\Psi_{(1)} \rightarrow E_{(1)}. \quad (13.3)$$

The two interactions (13.2) and (13.3) are illustrated by the Feynman diagrams of **Figures 2A and 2B** are both gravitational interactions mediated solely by gravitinos. But given the maximum gravitino ranges, for example, in (12.2) through (12.5), the energy densities must be close enough so that the gravitinos never decay into neutrino loops and gravitons. Consequently, these are very short-range variants of the gravitational interaction and, because they have no neutrino “cliffs,” they are much stronger. Indeed, the couplings $g_{(p)}$ between the elementary particles and their gravitino superpartners, which arise from (9.6) and enter into (9.9) and **Figures 1 and 2**, are the very same interaction and Yukawa couplings that the W, Z and h bosons and the fermions have for their electroweak and particle physics vacuum interactions. There is no weak gravitational-strength coupling anywhere to be found. Therefore, this type of gravitational interaction is much stronger than what we are accustomed to when speaking of gravitation. Indeed, not only are the variants (13.2) and (13.3) shown in **Figure 2** much stronger and with much shorter range than the gravitation with which we are familiar, but *the range and strength of these short-range, strong gravitational interaction variants is comparable to the range and strength of the electroweak and strong interactions*.

Figure 2: Feynman diagrams for a) short range, strong gravitational interaction of two elementary particles; and b) gravitational self-interaction backreaction

14. Might the $f_0(500)$ a.k.a. sigma meson be a conflation of W, Z, h and t gravitinos?

If one was not expecting to find any gravitinos in experiments that are observing hadrons and their interactions, and if one came across a gravitino interaction in the form of (13.2) or the backreaction (13.3) of **Figure 2**, one would try to fit this into all the other knowledge that has been acquired from modern nuclear and hadronic physics. For example, because the gravitino in (13.2) is mediating a strong but short range interaction between two elementary particles, one would immediately start from the view that this must be some sort of scalar or vector meson, or pseudo-variants thereof. Proceeding, one would also start to look for the $\bar{q}q$ content of this presumed meson. But because this is really a gravitino, one would have trouble finding such content. Moreover, given that the four gravitino partner masses in (11.1) through (11.3) for W, Z and Higgs and in (11.4) for the top quark all run in the neighborhood of 500 MeV to 700 MeV, one might regard particles observed in this zone to be light mesons related to strong interactions, even though they are really gravitinos related to gravitation. Also, because of the $1/3$ power factor in (12.1), the width-to-rest energy ratio $\gamma \equiv \Gamma / mc^2$ for gravitinos will be much larger than it is for their elementary particle superpartners, as seen in (12.6) through (12.9). So, with insufficient discrimination one might even come to believe that all four of these gravitinos are really a single meson. But in that case, the gravitino distribution of this purported meson would not be the usual Breit-Wigner distribution. It would be unexpectedly wide and – without understanding that these are multiple gravitino types and not one strong interaction meson – inexplicable.

If the foregoing seems reminiscent of one or more of the particles observed and catalogued in the particle reviews, that is because it is: The foregoing sounds like it could describe the sigma meson now known as the $f_0(500)$, which has been observed and catalogued since at least 1964, yet has defied efforts over six decades to obtain a theoretical understanding of what this particle actually is, and is not, see [22], [23]. But now, we see from (13.2) and (13.3) and **Figure 2** that *there is a strong and short-range variant of the gravitational interaction with a set of gravitinos in the zone of 500 to 700 MeV with unusually wide full widths, seen through the prism of what is expected from hadronic not gravitational interactions*, which interaction looks to have certain characteristics – but not others – of hadronic interactions. So, amidst the longstanding and still-unresolved mysteries surrounding the $f_0(500)$ a.k.a. sigma meson, the possibility must be considered that sigma meson, is not a hadronic meson at all. Rather, it may well be a collection of four gravitinos which are the superpartners of the W, Z and Higgs bosons and the top quark, each of which have median masses that, at the center of experimental errors, as seen in (11.1) through (11.4), are 511.939 MeV, 533.933 MeV, 593.52 MeV and 658.03 MeV respectively, with each partner (aside from that of h) having broad widths on the order of 20% to 30% of their masses as calculated in (12.6), (12.7) and (12.9).

More generally, as noted following (11.6), it is desirable to experimentally test the prediction of the gravitino masses in (11.1) through (11.6). What the foregoing suggests is that the closeness of the masses for the W, Z, h and t superpartners, combined with their broad widths and the fact that these gravitinos are identical in all respects except for their masses and widths, and with the expectation that any massive particles observed in hadronic experiments will be hadrons or leptons showing strong and electroweak but certainly not gravitational interactions, *may have created the misconception that these four gravitinos are actually one meson known as the $f_0(500)$ or sigma*. So, the experimental detection of these four gravitinos, may well boil down to carefully reexamining the sigma meson, and determining whether its idiosyncrasies can be explained on the basis of this actually being a set of gravitinos erroneously conflated into a single hadronic meson. **PART IV** of [18] examines how this testing might be undertaken. It also assesses possibilities for detecting some of the other gravitino masses in (11.4) through (11.6), especially for the mu and tau lepton superpartner gravitinos via higher-generation positronium decays.

As to this article, now that we have demonstrated that the numeric connection first made at (8.1) leads to a renormalizable understanding of how gravitation transpires at the level of elementary particle field quanta, and gives rise to each massive elementary particle having a gravitino superpartner with masses predicted at (11.1) through (11.6), we return to a detailed exposition of the neutrino masses and PMNS mixing angles.

PART III: NEUTRINO MASSES AND MIXING ANGLES

15. Calculation of nine candidate normal ordered neutrino square mass averages

We now return to the normal ordered neutrino masses, and undertake to find these directly and precisely. We begin with (7.4) and recalculate the three ‘‘native’’ relations (7.5) along with six ‘‘crossover’’ relations, using the tightened PMNS angles in (8.8). Then, we shall use these to calculate individual neutrino masses from (7.2). The native calculations of $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}$, $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}$ and $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}$ continue to use (7.5), but now with the tightened PMNS data in (8.8). The 3σ result with the extremes from all high/low combination is now:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{P12}) &= 8.74_{-0.31}^{+0.33} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2; & \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{P23}) &= 5.61_{-0.96}^{+1.12} \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{P13}) &= 8.62_{-0.29}^{+0.30} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (15.1)$$

To calculate crossovers, starting with (7.4), see the analogous (4.6), we use:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{P23}) &= \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P23}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{P13}) &= \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P13}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P13}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{P12}) &= -\left\{ (2 + \tan^4 \theta_{P12}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P12}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P12}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P12}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{P13}) &= -\left\{ (2 + \tan^4 \theta_{P13}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P13}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P13}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P13}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{P12}) &= \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P12}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P12}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{P23}) &= \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \left\{ (1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P23}) / (1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}) \right\} \frac{1}{3} \Delta m_{31}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (15.2)$$

Then, we use (15.2) to calculate the crossover square mass averages:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{P23}) &= 1.01_{-0.06}^{+0.07} \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2; & \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{P13}) &= 8.60_{-0.29}^{+0.30} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{P12}) &= 1.23_{-0.10}^{+0.11} \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2; & \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{P13}) &= 7.88_{-0.31}^{+0.32} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2; \\ \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{P12}) &= 1.31_{-0.10}^{+0.11} \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2; & \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{P23}) &= 5.83_{-0.98}^{+1.13} \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (15.3)$$

As with (7.6), to obtain (15.1) and (15.3) we have calculated all eight low-to-high Δm_{21}^2 , Δm_{31}^2 and $\tan^4 \theta_p$ combinations from (7.5) and (15.2), then displayed the widest extremes from any of these combinations.

Next, we use (15.1) via $\sqrt{\Sigma m_\nu^2} = \sqrt{3 \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle}$ to recalculate (7.7), obtaining:

$$\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 12}^2(\theta_{P12})} = 0.051(1) \text{ eV}; \quad \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 23}^2(\theta_{P23})} = 0.130(12) \text{ eV}; \quad \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 13}^2(\theta_{P13})} = 0.051(1) \text{ eV}. \quad (15.4)$$

Note, as a result of what was discussed following for θ_{P23} , that the recalculated $\sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 23}^2(\theta_{P23})}$ in (15.4) likewise has a 3σ spread that is tighter than its previous 1σ spread in (7.7). And, from (15.3), again with

$\sqrt{\Sigma m_\nu^2} = \sqrt{3 \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle}$, we obtain the crossover square-mass sum square roots:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 12}^2(\theta_{P23})} &= 0.055(2) \text{ eV}; & \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 12}^2(\theta_{P13})} &= 0.051(1) \text{ eV}; \\ \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 23}^2(\theta_{P12})} &= 0.061(3) \text{ eV}; & \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 23}^2(\theta_{P13})} &= 0.049(1) \text{ eV}; \\ \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 13}^2(\theta_{P12})} &= 0.063_{-0.002}^{+0.003} \text{ eV}; & \sqrt{\Sigma m_{\nu 13}^2(\theta_{P23})} &= 0.132(12) \text{ eV}. \end{aligned} \quad (15.5)$$

With the foregoing, we are now ready to insert the candidate square mass averages in (15.1) and (15.3) into the square roots of (7.2) to calculate possible values for the individual neutrino rest masses. Then, as among these candidate mass sets, we shall examine which are most likely to be the physical neutrino masses.

16. Calculation of nine candidate normal ordered neutrino mass triplets

The three equations in (7.2) are for squares of the three neutrino masses. Each of these contains an $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$ to which is added, one of three expressions which, using the data in (7.1) reported by [10], and employing the largest possible spread for the first line below which lowers the other spreads, are calculated to be:

$$\begin{aligned} +\frac{1}{3}(-\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) &= -(8.604_{-0.286}^{+0.297} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2); \\ +\frac{1}{3}(2\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2) &= -(7.863_{-0.227}^{+0.235} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2); \\ +\frac{1}{3}(-\Delta m_{21}^2 + 2\Delta m_{31}^2) &= +(1.647_{-0.051}^{+0.053} \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2), \end{aligned} \quad (16.1)$$

and all sum to zero. For $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$, we have now calculated three “native” square mass averages $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{ij}(\theta_{Pij})$ with $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ and $i < j$ in (15.1), as well as six “crossover” averages in (15.3). We denote these generally by $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij})$ with $j = n$ always, with $i = m$ for a native relation, and with $i \neq m$ for a crossover. If we generalize the form of $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$ in (7.2) to expressly show crossover possibilities, then we may rewrite (7.2) as:

$$\begin{aligned} m_1^2 &= \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij}) + \frac{1}{3}(-\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2); \\ m_2^2 &= \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij}) + \frac{1}{3}(2\Delta m_{21}^2 - \Delta m_{31}^2); \\ m_3^2 &= \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij}) + \frac{1}{3}(-\Delta m_{21}^2 + 2\Delta m_{31}^2). \end{aligned} \quad (16.2)$$

So the masses of the individual neutrinos, which are simply the positive square roots of each of (16.2), depend entirely upon which of the nine candidate $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij})$ we use in (16.2). Of course, there are not nine sets of neutrino masses in nature; there is only one. So, we need to select which candidate is the correct one to use.

Because of the manner in which the three angles θ_{12} , θ_{23} and θ_{13} were defined in (7.3), and because we are considering three native associations $\theta_{12} = \theta_{P12}$, $\theta_{23} = \theta_{P23}$ and $\theta_{13} = \theta_{P13}$ and six crossover associations $\theta_{12} = \theta_{P23}$, $\theta_{12} = \theta_{P13}$, $\theta_{23} = \theta_{P12}$, $\theta_{23} = \theta_{P13}$, $\theta_{13} = \theta_{P12}$ and $\theta_{13} = \theta_{P23}$ between these angles defined at (7.3) and the three real PMNS angles, it turns out that the $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij})$ used in (16.2) – whichever one it is – ends up producing a simple GST relation $\tan^2 \theta_{Pij} = m_m / m_n$ for neutrino masses. That is, as we show analytically at (17.7) below and numerically in the interim, (16.2) always produces a GST correspondence given by:

$$\langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij}) \Leftrightarrow \tan^2 \theta_{Pij} = m_m / m_n. \quad (16.3)$$

So, selecting a particular $\langle m_{\nu i}^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij})$ to use in (16.2), is identically equivalent to selecting a GST relation $\tan^2 \theta_{Pij} = m_m / m_n$ between the real PMNS angle θ_{Pij} and the neutrino mass ratio m_m / m_n . And as with quarks, these can be native relations akin to $\tan^2 \theta_{12C} = m_d / m_s$, or crossover relations akin to $\tan^2 \theta_{23C} = m_u / m_c$.

Now, if we knew the individual neutrino masses in the same way that we know the lepton masses and at least know the quark masses at particular energy scales in particular QCD renormalization schemes, then we would be able to quickly identify which of the nine candidate GST relations available from (16.3) ought to be used. But we do not know these individual neutrino masses. Our present task is to find these masses. So, we must use other available information to infer the correct GST relation to implement via (16.3). For this, we employ a process of both empirical and theoretical elimination to identify the likeliest candidates – or even better – the single best candidate, for the actual neutrino masses.

First, note that the first two expressions in (16.1) are negative numbers, and that the sum of all three of these expressions is equal to 0. When these expressions are added in (16.2) to the $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{Pij})$ which have the values calculated in (15.1) and (15.3), the m_1^2 neutrino square mass will become negative – which would

imply an imaginary mass – for any $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle < 8.604_{-0.286}^{+0.297} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2$. And the m_2^2 square mass would become negative for any $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle < 7.863_{-0.227}^{+0.235} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2$. So, if we forbid the square masses from becoming negative, not only at medians but at any 3σ extremes, we can immediately eliminate $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p13})$ because not only will this always produce an imaginary m_1 , it will also give an imaginary mass to m_2 at a 3σ extremum. We also eliminate $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p12})$, $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{p13})$ and $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p13})$ because while some values of these produce a positive mass for all three neutrinos, they do produce an imaginary m_1 within 3σ bounds. Note that this eliminates all the $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mm}(\theta_{p13})$ which are functions of the smallest PMNS angle θ_{p13} . That is, in view of (16.3), θ_{p13} cannot be part of a simple neutrino mass GST relation.

While one may regard the above as an “aesthetic” restraint, there is also a good empirical reason for the foregoing eliminations: If we use $8.604_{-0.286}^{+0.297} \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV}^2$ in (16.1) as the value of $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$ in (7.2) and thereby ensure that the first-generation neutrino mass is exactly equal to zero, $m_1 = 0$, then it turns out that the masses $m_2 = 0.0086_{-0.0003}^{+0.0004} \text{ eV}$ and $m_3 = 0.0501_{-0.0008}^{+0.0008} \text{ eV}$. Thus, the sum of all three neutrino masses for $m_1 = 0$, would be $\Sigma m_\nu = 0.0587(12) \text{ eV}$, which has an upper 3σ bound of 0.0599 eV . Noting again the empirical observation reported in [8] of a “current lower bound of ...0.06 eV” for the sum of the neutrino masses, we see that this 0.06 eV lower bound is the experimental manifestation of the theoretical requirement imposed in the previous paragraph, that none of the neutrino masses can become imaginary. In other words, the empirically-observed lower bound near 0.06 eV for the neutrino mass sum corresponds analytically to requiring the first-generation neutrino rest mass to be real and positive.

Out of the remaining five $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$, let us now consider the native $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p23})$ from (15.1) and the crossover $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{p23})$ from (15.3). Using (16.2), taking all eight low-high combinations for Δm_{21}^2 , Δm_{31}^2 and $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$ which we regard as mutually-independent, we display the widest extrema arising from any of these combinations, and thereby calculate the individual neutrino masses and the mass sums:

$$\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p23}): m_1 = 0.069(7) \text{ eV}; m_2 = 0.069(7) \text{ eV}; m_3 = 0.085(7) \text{ eV}; \Sigma m_{\nu i} = 0.224(21) \text{ eV}; \quad (16.4)$$

$$\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{p23}): m_1 = 0.071_{-0.008}^{+0.007} \text{ eV}; m_2 = 0.071_{-0.007}^{+0.008} \text{ eV}; m_3 = 0.086_{-0.005}^{+0.006} \text{ eV}; \Sigma m_{\nu i} = 0.228_{-0.020}^{+0.022} \text{ eV}. \quad (16.5)$$

These two possibilities are empirically excluded because of the “upper limit of around 0.12 eV” for the neutrino masses sum reported by [8]. This means via (16.3), that $\tan^2 \theta_{p23} = m_2 / m_3$ and $\tan^2 \theta_{p23} = m_1 / m_3$ are empirically ruled out as GST relations. But to see (16.3) in numerical operation, it is worth calculating $\arctan \sqrt{m_2 / m_3} = 42.08^\circ$ using the median masses in the native (16.4), which is exactly equal to the median of θ_{p23} in (8.8). Likewise, with median masses in the crossover (16.5), we find $\arctan \sqrt{m_1 / m_3} = 42.08^\circ$ which likewise equals the median θ_{p23} in (8.8).

So now, the only $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$ candidates left are $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p12})$, $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{p12})$ and $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p23})$, which are all in the crossover averages in the left column of (15.3). The first two, via (16.3), would imply the simple crossover GST relations $\tan^2 \theta_{p12} = m_2 / m_3$ and $\tan^2 \theta_{p12} = m_1 / m_3$ between θ_{p12} and the respective second-to-third and first-to-third generation neutrino mass ratios. The final one would imply the crossover GST relation $\tan^2 \theta_{p23} = m_1 / m_2$ between θ_{p23} and the first-to-second generation neutrino mass ratio.

Before assessing these three remaining $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle$ candidates, let us calculate out the neutrino masses from all three. For $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p12})$ and $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{13}(\theta_{p12})$, from (7.2), as before, we calculate:

$$\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{23}(\theta_{p12}): m_1 = 0.019_{-0.004}^{+0.003} \text{ eV}; m_2 = 0.021_{-0.003}^{+0.003} \text{ eV}; m_3 = 0.054_{-0.001}^{+0.000} \text{ eV}; \Sigma m_{\nu i} = 0.094_{-0.008}^{+0.007} \text{ eV}; \quad (16.6)$$

$$\left\langle m_\nu^2 \right\rangle_{13} (\theta_{P12}): m_1 = 0.021_{-0.003}^{+0.003} \text{ eV}; m_2 = 0.023_{-0.003}^{+0.003} \text{ eV}; m_3 = 0.054_{-0.000}^{+0.001} \text{ eV}; \Sigma m_{\nu_i} = 0.099_{-0.007}^{+0.006} \text{ eV}. \quad (16.7)$$

As at (16.4) and (16.5), from median masses, we can calculate that $\arctan \sqrt{m_2 / m_3} = 32.03^\circ$ from (16.6), which is the same as the median of θ_{P12} in (8.8). And from (16.7) we find $\arctan \sqrt{m_1 / m_3} = 32.03^\circ$, likewise the median of θ_{P12} . So, we again see (16.3) in operation. With their mass sums being in the vicinity of 0.10 eV, well between 0.06 eV and 0.12 eV, there is no empirical reason to disqualify either of (16.6) or (16.7).

Finally, for the remaining $\left\langle m_\nu^2 \right\rangle_{12} (\theta_{P23})$ we calculate:

$$\left\langle m_\nu^2 \right\rangle_{12} (\theta_{P23}): m_1 = 0.012_{-0.005}^{+0.004} \text{ eV}; m_2 = 0.015_{-0.003}^{+0.003} \text{ eV}; m_3 = 0.052_{-0.001}^{+0.000} \text{ eV}; \Sigma m_{\nu_i} = 0.079_{-0.009}^{+0.006} \text{ eV}. \quad (16.8)$$

Here, we may calculate from medians that $\arctan \sqrt{m_1 / m_2} = 42.08^\circ$, equal to the median θ_{P23} in (8.8). The above (16.8) is also well within the $0.06 \text{ eV} < \Sigma m_\nu < 0.12 \text{ eV}$ bounds for the neutrino mass sum, and so is also empirically qualified to represent actual neutrino masses. Now, we must assess (16.6), (16.7) and (16.8) to determine which of these candidate mass sets in fact contains the physical neutrino masses.

17. Normal ordered neutrino masses

Prior to assessing which of (16.6), (16.7) or (16.8) is best suited to tell us the actual individual neutrino eigenstate rest energies, let us first restructure (8.6) to isolate Δm , as follows:

$$\Delta m = \sqrt{2} \frac{E_P}{v} \sqrt{\frac{1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P23} \Delta m_{31}^2}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}} - \frac{2 + \tan^4 \theta_{P23} \Delta m_{21}^2}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}}}. \quad (17.1)$$

Then, let us use (17.1) in (4.10) in view of the prospective PMNS angle associations that were adopted for the reasons reviewed following (8.8), which acquired additional support from our having been able the thereby construct the renormalizable Lagrangian (9.9) drawn with the Feynman diagram of **Figure 1**, to obtain:

$$\tan^2 \theta_{P12} = \frac{m_e}{m_\mu} + \sqrt{2} \frac{E_P}{v} \frac{1}{m_\mu} \sqrt{\frac{1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P23} \Delta m_{31}^2}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}} - \frac{2 + \tan^4 \theta_{P23} \Delta m_{21}^2}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}}}, \quad (17.2)$$

$$\tan^2 \theta_{P13} = \frac{m_e}{m_\tau} + \sqrt{2} \frac{E_P}{v} \frac{1}{m_\tau} \sqrt{\frac{1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{P23} \Delta m_{31}^2}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}} - \frac{2 + \tan^4 \theta_{P23} \Delta m_{21}^2}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{P23}}}. \quad (17.3)$$

Above, were we to set the neutrino masses to zero by setting $\Delta m_{31}^2 = \Delta m_{21}^2 = 0$, (17.2) and (17.3) would reduce to the simple GST relations $\tan^2 \theta_{P12} = m_e / m_\mu$ and $\tan^2 \theta_{P13} = m_e / m_\tau$. This means the non-zero neutrino masses are the root cause of why we needed to shift the lepton mass sum starting at (4.3), to obtain the GST angle matches in (4.9). Moreover, the electron mass which appears in the lepton mass ratios above is much smaller than the mu and tau lepton masses. So, if we were to set $m_e = 0$ and then calculate these two PMNS angles using only the second term that contains the neutrino mass contributions, which is more directly done by calculating $\tan^2 \theta_{P12} (m_e = 0) = \Delta m / m_\mu$ and $\tan^2 \theta_{P13} (m_e = 0) = \Delta m / m_\tau$ using (4.7) and the charged lepton masses in (3.1), we would obtain:

$$\theta_{P12} (m_e = 0) = 31.88_{-0.74}^{+0.70} \cong \theta_{P12} = 32.03_{-0.73}^{+0.70}; \quad \theta_{P13} (m_e = 0) = 8.62_{-0.24}^{+0.23} \cong \theta_{P13} = 8.68_{-0.24}^{+0.23}. \quad (17.4)$$

At median, the former differs from the fully-determined angle in (8.8) by a scant 0.15° and the latter by 0.06° , which validates that neutrino masses, and not the charged lepton masses, are the very dominant determinants of these two PMNS angles. Indeed, these values are indistinguishable within experimental errors. This confirms what we anticipated in the discussion following (3.4) and (3.5), which is that if the PMNS angles were to be functions of the lepton masses, then the fact that the PMNS matrix acts on neutrinos during their oscillations, and that there are no generation changes during weak beta decays between charged leptons and neutrinos (in clear contrast to quark behavior), would suggest that the neutrino masses would be the dominant drivers of the PMNS angles.

Most pertinent to the present discussion, however, we already have analytic relations (17.2) and (17.3) for the two real angles θ_{P12} and θ_{P13} in terms of lepton masses. But we do not yet have an analytic relation for

$\theta_{p_{23}}$ which in fact sits inside the radical in each of (17.2) and (17.3). Were we to adopt (16.6) or (16.7) to tell us the neutrino masses, then we would respectively also have the GST relations $\tan^2 \theta_{p_{12}} = m_2 / m_3$ or $\tan^2 \theta_{p_{12}} = m_1 / m_3$. But we already have the relations (17.2) and (17.3) for $\theta_{p_{12}}$ and $\theta_{p_{13}}$ in terms of lepton masses, but do not yet have a relation which gives us $\theta_{p_{23}}$. Using $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ as is done in (16.8) would provide this third GST relation, in the simple form of $\tan^2 \theta_{p_{23}} = m_1 / m_2$ with only neutrino masses.

Also, for quarks, there is a native relation $\tan^2 \theta_{12C} = m_d / m_s$ and a crossover relation $\tan^2 \theta_{23C} = m_u / m_c$. For leptons, in (17.2) we have a similar native relation $\tan^2 \theta_{p_{12}} = m_e / m_\mu + \dots$ with an energy shift induced by the nonzero neutrino masses. Were we to use $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p_{23}})$, we would then obtain a crossover $\tan^2 \theta_{p_{23}} = m_1 / m_2$ for the remaining PMNS angle in relation to neutrino masses, precisely mirroring $\tan^2 \theta_{23C} = m_u / m_c$ for quarks. So, an angle with 23 indexes would relate the first-to-second-generation mass ratio of isospin-up fermions, and an angle with 12 indexes would relate the first-to-second-generation mass ratio of isospin-down fermions plus the energy shift induced by neutrino masses directly connected to fundamental difference in how leptons change generations versus quarks.

For these two reasons – primarily that using $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ establishes the needed remaining GST relation involving $\theta_{p_{23}}$ and secondarily because this would be a crossover relation precisely mirroring $\tan^2 \theta_{23C} = m_u / m_c$ for quarks up to ΔE – we conclude that is the correct candidate to use for determining neutrino masses, and that the physical neutrino masses and their sum are in fact those given by (16.8).

Having concluded the foregoing, to obtain a direct expression for the square neutrino masses we insert the first line of (15.2) into (16.2) and reduce to obtain:

$$m_1^2 = \frac{\tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}} \Delta m_{21}^2; \quad m_2^2 = \frac{1}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}} \Delta m_{21}^2; \quad m_3^2 = \frac{\tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \Delta m_{31}^2. \quad (17.5)$$

The square mass sum, now written without $_{12}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ because we have now identified this in (16.8) as being the correct association, is easily seen to reproduce the first line of (15.2). With $\Delta m_{ij}^2 = m_i^2 - m_j^2$:

$$\Sigma m_\nu^2 = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + m_3^2 = \frac{1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}} \Delta m_{21}^2 + \Delta m_{31}^2 = m_3^2 + \frac{1 + 2 \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}} m_2^2 - \frac{2 + \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p_{23}}} m_1^2. \quad (17.6)$$

And, from the first two square masses in (17.5) we easily identify what is now the third lepton GST relation:

$$\tan^2 \theta_{p_{23}} = m_1 / m_2 = 42.08_{-0.45}^{+0.38}, \quad (17.7)$$

which includes the numeric value of the tightened $\theta_{p_{23}}$ in (8.8). *Similar calculations inserting any of the native relations (7.5) or any crossover relations (15.2) into (16.2) can be used to directly, analytically prove the correspondence $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{mn}(\theta_{p_{ij}}) \Leftrightarrow \tan^2 \theta_{p_{ij}} = m_m / m_n$ shown in (16.3).*

18. Tightening of normal ordered neutrino masses

Now that we have analytic direct expressions (17.5) for individual neutrino masses, instead of using $\langle m_\nu^2 \rangle_{12}(\theta_{p_{23}})$ as an intermediary, we may tighten the neutrino mass data by inserting the eight low-high combinations of $\tan \theta_{p_{23}}$ from (8.8), and Δm_{21}^2 and Δm_{31}^2 from (7.1), into (17.5), then taking square roots. Calculated to an additional decimal place versus (16.8) because at (8.8) we tightened $\theta_{p_{23}}$ by an order of magnitude, with maximal spreads, we obtain:

$$m_1 = 0.0121_{-0.0015}^{+0.0016} \text{ eV}; \quad m_2 = 0.0149_{-0.0014}^{+0.0015} \text{ eV}; \quad m_3 = 0.0515_{-0.0011}^{+0.0012} \text{ eV}. \quad (18.1)$$

Therefore, the neutrino mass sum:

$$\Sigma m_{\nu_i} = m_1 + m_2 + m_3 = 0.0785_{-0.0040}^{+0.0043} \text{ eV}, \quad (18.2)$$

with an average / expectation value for the mass of a propagating, oscillating neutrino then being:

$$\langle m_{\nu i} \rangle = \frac{1}{3} \Sigma m_{\nu i} = 0.0262_{-0.0013}^{+0.0014} \text{ eV}. \quad (18.3)$$

Although the high-end error bar for m_1 slightly exceeds the low-end for m_2 , because $\theta_{p23} = 42.11_{-0.52}^{+0.42^\circ}$ from (8.8) remains under 45° even at its highest, we ensure via (17.7) which is easily gleaned from (17.5), that it is statistically impossible for the first and second generation neutrino masses to have an inverted ordering.

Finally, we may use (6.1) with (18.1) and (18.2) to calculate the neutrino mass variance:

$$\sigma^2(m_\nu) = \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle - \langle m_\nu \rangle^2 = \frac{1}{3} \Sigma m_\nu^2 - \frac{1}{9} \Sigma^2 m_\nu = (0.0180(2) \text{ eV})^2. \quad (18.4)$$

The two second-order mass sums which contribute to the variance in (18.4) are (also see (18.2) for the latter):

$$\Sigma m_\nu^2 = (0.0550_{-0.0017}^{+0.0019} \text{ eV})^2; \quad \text{and} \quad \Sigma^2 m_\nu = (0.0785_{-0.0040}^{+0.0043} \text{ eV})^2. \quad (18.5)$$

19. Analytic representation of neutrino masses and mixing angles

Let us now review foregoing neutrino mass and mixing angle relations analytically. First, we can use (17.7) and $\Delta m_{31}^2 = m_3^2 - m_1^2$ and $\Delta m_{21}^2 = m_2^2 - m_1^2$ to write (17.1) entirely in terms of neutrino masses and the ratio $\sqrt{E_p / \nu} = 2.22678(1) \times 10^8$ in (6.2), as follows:

$$\Delta m = \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{E_p}{\nu}} \sqrt{\frac{m_2^2 (m_3^2 - 2m_2^2) - m_1^2 (m_1^2 - 2m_3^2)}{m_2^2 - m_1^2}}. \quad (19.1)$$

This is easily rewritten as:

$$\frac{m_2^2 (m_3^2 - 2m_2^2) - m_1^2 (m_1^2 - 2m_3^2)}{m_2^2 - m_1^2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\nu}{E_p} \Delta m^2. \quad (19.2)$$

We may also insert (19.1) into the GST relations in (4.10) for the PMNS angles θ_{p12} and θ_{p13} to obtain:

$$\tan^2 \theta_{p12} = \frac{m_e}{m_\mu} + \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{E_p}{\nu}} \frac{1}{m_\mu} \sqrt{\frac{m_2^2 (m_3^2 - 2m_2^2) - m_1^2 (m_1^2 - 2m_3^2)}{m_2^2 - m_1^2}}; \quad (19.3)$$

$$\tan^2 \theta_{p13} = \frac{m_e}{m_\tau} + \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{E_p}{\nu}} \frac{1}{m_\tau} \sqrt{\frac{m_2^2 (m_3^2 - 2m_2^2) - m_1^2 (m_1^2 - 2m_3^2)}{m_2^2 - m_1^2}}. \quad (19.4)$$

The above re-express these angles entirely in terms of lepton masses and E_p / ν , and again show how the energy shift in these angles from simple GST form results entirely from neutrinos having nonzero masses.

Next, for mathematical convenience, we define one additional GST angle using the first-to-third generation neutrino mass ratio, and calculate this numerically using (18.1), as follows:

$$\tan^2 \phi \equiv m_1 / m_3; \quad \text{therefore} \quad \phi = 25.88_{-1.21}^{+1.15^\circ}. \quad (19.5)$$

As ratios of two like-charged fermion masses, both θ_{p23} in (17.7) and (19.5) are independent of renormalization scheme and scale. A useful relation obtained by combining the angles (17.7) and (19.5), is $\cot^2 \phi \tan^2 \theta_{p23} = m_3 / m_2$.

Now, we return to the individual neutrino square masses in (17.5), apply $\Delta m_{ij}^2 = m_i^2 - m_j^2$, then use the identity $(1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23})^{-1} = \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \cos^4 \theta_{p23}$, to rewrite these as:

$$\begin{aligned} m_1^2 &= \frac{\tan^4 \theta_{p23}}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23}} (m_2^2 - m_1^2) = \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \sin^4 \theta_{p23} (m_2^2 - m_1^2); \\ m_2^2 &= \frac{1}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23}} (m_2^2 - m_1^2) = \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \cos^4 \theta_{p23} (m_2^2 - m_1^2); \\ m_3^2 &= m_3^2 + \frac{\tan^4 \theta_{p23}}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23}} m_2^2 - \frac{1}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23}} m_1^2 = m_3^2 + \sec(2\theta_{p23}) (\sin^4 \theta_{p23} m_2^2 - \cos^4 \theta_{p23} m_1^2). \end{aligned} \quad (19.6)$$

Using the middle expression, one can confirm these relations by taking the sum $\Sigma m_\nu^2 = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + m_3^2$, applying $\tan^4 \theta_{p23} = m_1^2 / m_2^2$ from (17.7), then reducing to the identity $\Sigma m_\nu^2 = \Sigma m_\nu^2$. Then, taking the square roots of the above after multiplying m_3^2 by $\sec(2\theta_{p23})\cos(2\theta_{p23}) = 1$ and using (19.5), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= \sqrt{\sec(2\theta_{p23})} \sin^2 \theta_{p23} \sqrt{m_2^2 - m_1^2}; \\ m_2 &= \sqrt{\sec(2\theta_{p23})} \cos^2 \theta_{p23} \sqrt{m_2^2 - m_1^2}; \\ m_3 &= \sqrt{\sec(2\theta_{p23})} \left(\sqrt{\cos(2\theta_{p23}) m_3^2 + \sin^4 \theta_{p23} m_2^2 - \cos^4 \theta_{p23} m_1^2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (19.7)$$

Next, by adding the square masses in (19.6), and also using the angles (17.7) and (19.5), we may rewrite the square mass sum (17.6) as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma m_\nu^2(\mu) &= \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \left[\cos(2\theta_{p23}) m_3^2 + (\cos^4 \theta_{p23} + 2\sin^4 \theta_{p23}) m_2^2 - (2\cos^4 \theta_{p23} + \sin^4 \theta_{p23}) m_1^2 \right] \\ &= m_2^2 \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \left[(\cos(2\theta_{p23}) \cot^4 \phi - \sin^4 \theta_{p23}) \tan^4 \theta_{p23} + \cos^4 \theta_{p23} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (19.8)$$

Because the angles θ_{p23} and ϕ are both related to mass ratios of like-charged (neutral) neutrinos, the bottom line of (19.8) is seen to be a function of the renormalization-dependent $m_2^2(\mu)$, times a function of angles that are independent of renormalization scheme and scale (SS). In this way, the SS-dependence of this square mass sum is isolated into that of $m_2(\mu)$ (or using (17.7) and (19.5), of any individual neutrino mass, if desired). We have also written this sum as $\Sigma m_\nu^2(\mu)$ to make clear that this is a function of renormalization scale μ and so is not SS-independent. By adding the individual masses in (19.7) and employing (17.7) and (19.5), using $1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23} = \cos(2\theta_{p23}) \sec^4 \theta_{p23}$, we similarly obtain the neutrino mass sum:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma m_\nu(\mu) &= \sqrt{\sec(2\theta_{p23})} \left(\sqrt{\cos(2\theta_{p23}) m_3^2 + \sin^4 \theta_{p23} m_2^2 - \cos^4 \theta_{p23} m_1^2} + \sqrt{m_2^2 - m_1^2} \right) \\ &= m_2 \left(\cot^2 \phi \tan^2 \theta_{p23} + \sec^2 \theta_{p23} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (19.9)$$

It then is possible to combine (19.8) and (19.9) to analytically write the neutrino mass variance of (18.4), as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^2(m_\nu)(\mu) &= \langle m_\nu^2 \rangle - \langle m_\nu \rangle^2 = \frac{1}{3} \Sigma m_\nu^2 - \frac{1}{9} \Sigma^2 m_\nu \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \left(\begin{aligned} &\cos(2\theta_{p23}) m_3^2 + (\cos^4 \theta_{p23} + 2\sin^4 \theta_{p23}) m_2^2 - (2\cos^4 \theta_{p23} + \sin^4 \theta_{p23}) m_1^2 \\ &- \frac{1}{3} \left(\sqrt{\cos(2\theta_{p23}) m_3^2 + \sin^4 \theta_{p23} m_2^2 - \cos^4 \theta_{p23} m_1^2} + \sqrt{m_2^2 - m_1^2} \right)^2 \end{aligned} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{3} m_2^2 \left[\sec(2\theta_{p23}) \left[(\cos(2\theta_{p23}) \cot^4 \phi - \sin^4 \theta_{p23}) \tan^4 \theta_{p23} + \cos^4 \theta_{p23} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{3} (\cot^4 \phi \tan^4 \theta_{p23} + 2\cot^2 \phi \sec^2 \theta_{p23} \tan^2 \theta_{p23} + \sec^4 \theta_{p23}) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (19.10)$$

Next, let us take the ratio of neutrino masses in (19.2), and using $\tan^4 \theta_{p23} = m_1^2 / m_2^2$ from (17.7) and again $(1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23})^{-1} = \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \cos^4 \theta_{p23}$, rewrite this ratio as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{m_2^2 (m_3^2 - 2m_2^2) - m_1^2 (m_1^2 - 2m_3^2)}{m_2^2 - m_1^2} &= \frac{m_3^2 - 2m_2^2}{1 - \tan^4 \theta_{p23}} - \frac{m_1^2 - 2m_3^2}{\cot^4 \theta_{p23} - 1} \\ &= \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \left[(\cos^4 \theta_{p23} + 2\sin^4 \theta_{p23}) m_3^2 - 2\cos^4 \theta_{p23} m_2^2 - \sin^4 \theta_{p23} m_1^2 \right] \\ &= m_2^2 \sec(2\theta_{p23}) \left[(\cot^4 \phi + (2\cot^4 \phi - 1) \tan^4 \theta_{p23}) \sin^4 \theta_{p23} - 2\cos^4 \theta_{p23} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (19.11)$$

Then, mindful that $\sqrt{E_p / \nu} = 2.22678(1) \times 10^8$, see (6.2), we may use (19.11) through (19.4) as:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta m(\mu) &= \sqrt{E_p / v} \sqrt{2 \sec(2\theta_{P23})} \sqrt{(\cos^4 \theta_{P23} + 2 \sin^4 \theta_{P23}) m_3^2 - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23} m_2^2 - \sin^4 \theta_{P23} m_1^2} \\ &= m_2 \sqrt{E_p / v} \sqrt{2 \sec(2\theta_{P23})} \sqrt{\left((2 \cot^4 \phi - 1) \tan^4 \theta_{P23} + \cot^4 \phi \right) \sin^4 \theta_{P23} - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23}};\end{aligned}\quad (19.12)$$

$$\begin{aligned}& \sec(2\theta_{P23}) \left[(\cos^4 \theta_{P23} + 2 \sin^4 \theta_{P23}) m_3^2 - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23} m_2^2 - \sin^4 \theta_{P23} m_1^2 \right] \\ &= m_2^2 \sec(2\theta_{P23}) \left[\left((2 \cot^4 \phi - 1) \tan^4 \theta_{P23} + \cot^4 \phi \right) \sin^4 \theta_{P23} - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23} \right] = \frac{1}{2} (v / E_p) \cdot \Delta m(\mu)^2;\end{aligned}\quad (19.13)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\tan^2 \theta_{P12}(\mu) &= \frac{m_e}{m_\mu} + \frac{\cot \Theta}{m_\mu} \sqrt{2 \sec(2\theta_{P23})} \sqrt{(\cos^4 \theta_{P23} + 2 \sin^4 \theta_{P23}) m_3^2 - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23} m_2^2 - \sin^4 \theta_{P23} m_1^2} \\ &= \frac{m_e}{m_\mu} + \frac{m_2}{m_\mu \tan \Theta} \sqrt{2 \sec(2\theta_{P23})} \left[\left((2 \cot^4 \phi - 1) \tan^4 \theta_{P23} + \cot^4 \phi \right) \sin^4 \theta_{P23} - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23} \right];\end{aligned}\quad (19.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\tan^2 \theta_{P13}(\mu) &= \frac{m_e}{m_\tau} + \frac{\cot \Theta}{m_\tau} \sqrt{2 \sec(2\theta_{P23})} \sqrt{(\cos^4 \theta_{P23} + 2 \sin^4 \theta_{P23}) m_3^2 - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23} m_2^2 - \sin^4 \theta_{P23} m_1^2} \\ &= \frac{m_e}{m_\tau} + \frac{m_2}{m_\tau \tan \Theta} \sqrt{2 \sec(2\theta_{P23})} \left[\left((2 \cot^4 \phi - 1) \tan^4 \theta_{P23} + \cot^4 \phi \right) \sin^4 \theta_{P23} - 2 \cos^4 \theta_{P23} \right].\end{aligned}\quad (19.15)$$

It is especially important to note from the second line in each of (19.14) and (19.15), that although the angles are all SS-independent, the ratios m_2 / m_μ in the former and m_2 / m_τ in the latter are not. This is because m_2 is the mass of a neutrino which is electrically neutral, while m_μ and m_τ are the masses of charged leptons which carry a single unit of electric charge. Therefore, unlike the CKM angles $\tan^2 \theta_{C12} = m_d / m_s$ and $\tan^2 \theta_{C23} = m_u / m_c$, and unlike the SS-independent PMNS angle $\theta_{P23} = \arctan \sqrt{m_1 / m_2}$ in (17.7) and the mathematically helpful angle ϕ of (19.5), the two angles θ_{P12} and θ_{P13} are effective angles which are dependent on the renormalization scheme and scale.

20. Direct connection of neutrino mass and mixing data with the gravitational constant

Let us now isolate m_2^2 using the second and fourth expressions in (19.13), then insert this into the square of the mass sum (19.9). Following trigonometric reduction and taking a final square root, we obtain:

$$\Sigma m_{\nu_i} c^2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \tan \Theta \Delta E \frac{\sqrt{\cos(2\theta_{P23})} (\cot^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta_{P23} + 1)}{\sqrt{\left((2 \cot^4 \phi - 1) \sin^8 \theta_{P23} + \cot^4 \phi \cos^4 \theta_{P23} \sin^4 \theta_{P23} - 2 \cos^8 \theta_{P23} \right)}}. \quad (20.1)$$

The ratio on the right contains only the angles θ_{P23} and ϕ , each of which is independent of the renormalization scheme and scale. Thus, when renormalizing, this ratio may be regarded as a constant. Likewise, $\tan \Theta = \sqrt{v / E_p}$ first introduced at (6.2) is an SS-independent ratio of two constants. As a result, it is helpful to segregate the parts of (20.1) which depend upon the renormalization scale, from those constant parts that do not, and to show the calculation of these constants from the angles in (17.7) and (19.5). We also show the values of $\tan \Theta$, and the neutrino mass sum in (18.2), as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma m_{\nu_i} c^2 &= K \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \tan \Theta \cdot \Delta E = K \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{v / E_p} \cdot \Delta E = 0.0785_{-0.0040}^{+0.0043} \text{ eV}; \\ \tan \Theta &= \sqrt{v / E_p} = \sqrt[4]{(\hbar^2 / c^2) (G_N / \sqrt{2} G_F)} = 4.49079(3) \times 10^{-9}; \\ K &= \frac{\sqrt{\cos(2\theta_{P23})} (\cot^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta_{P23} + 1)}{\sqrt{\left((2 \cot^4 \phi - 1) \sin^8 \theta_{P23} + \cot^4 \phi \cos^4 \theta_{P23} \sin^4 \theta_{P23} - 2 \cos^8 \theta_{P23} \right)}} = 0.6051_{-0.0207}^{+0.0240}.\end{aligned}\quad (20.2)$$

It is important to note based on the mass ratios in (17.7) and (19.5) which determine the two angles it contains, that K above is SS-independent. Because $\theta_{P23} = \arctan \sqrt{m_1 / m_2}$ and $\phi \equiv \arctan \sqrt{m_1 / m_3}$ are related to masses and thus a mass sum Σm_{ν_i} with error bars that are correlated from low to high, see (18.1) and (18.2),

the lowest values of $\theta_{p_{23}}$ can be and have been matched with the lowest values of ϕ when calculating K above. Also, the mass sum in the above was somewhat tightened at (18.2) from its original value in (16.8). This means that we can use this tightened data arising from neutrino masses and mixing, to calculate a tighter value for ΔE . From the top line of (20.2), the lowest Σm_{ν_i} will arise from the lowest K, lowest v/E_p and lowest ΔE , and likewise the highest will correlate to the highest. So, to calculate the tighter spread for ΔE , we maintain these correspondences while using the data in (20.2) to calculate that:

$$\Delta E = \left(\sqrt{2} \Sigma m_{\nu_i} c^2 / K \right) \sqrt{E_p / v} = 40.857_{-0.714}^{+0.602} \text{ MeV}. \quad (20.3)$$

It will be seen that as a result of the neutrino mass data embodied in (20.2), that it has become possible to tighten ΔE by a factor of just under 3.5 in relation to its value in (4.8).

This enables us to use (3.1) and (4.10) to also tighten the other two PMNS angles, so (8.8) now becomes:

$$\theta_{p_{12}} = 32.035_{-0.224}^{+0.186^\circ}, \quad \theta_{p_{13}} = 8.675_{-0.074}^{+0.062^\circ}, \quad \theta_{p_{23}} = 42.081_{-0.453}^{+0.378^\circ}. \quad (20.4)$$

As noted at (8.8), this is 3σ error bar data. When we compare this to the reported data in (3.4), aside from median changes earlier discussed, the 3σ data now computed in (20.4) for each of these respective angles is tighter than the reported 1σ data shown in (3.4) by respective factor of about 3.6, 1.6 and 2.4. And when we do a 3σ -to- 3σ comparison, the improvement factors are 10.8, 5.0 and 13.6. Accordingly, we have now shown these out to three decimal places versus two places reported for the first two angles.

Finally, if we use $E_p = \sqrt{\hbar c^5 / G_N}$ in the top line of (20.2) then isolate G_N , we obtain:

$$G_N = \frac{4\Sigma^4 E_{\nu_i}}{K^4 v^2 (\Delta E)^4} \hbar c^5. \quad (20.5)$$

It will be seen that this is identical to the final expression in (8.3), but with different definition of the identical constant K. So if we equate K as expressed in (20.5) with its expression in (8.4) including the numeric value of K from (20.2), we see that:

$$K = \frac{\Sigma E_{\nu_i}}{\sqrt{\Sigma E_{\nu_{i23}}^2 (\theta_{p_{23}})}} = \frac{\sqrt{\cos(2\theta_{p_{23}})} (\cot^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta_{p_{23}} + 1)}{\sqrt{(2 \cot^4 \phi - 1) \sin^8 \theta_{p_{23}} + \cot^4 \phi \cos^4 \theta_{p_{23}} \sin^4 \theta_{p_{23}} - 2 \cos^8 \theta_{p_{23}}}} = 0.6051_{-0.0207}^{+0.0240}. \quad (20.6)$$

Using the numeric data for both K and ΣE_{ν_i} and the Yukawa coupling $m_{\nu_i}^2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} v G_{\nu_i}$, we can easily obtain:

$$\sqrt{\Sigma E_{\nu_{i23}}^2 (\theta_{p_{23}})} = \Sigma E_{\nu_i} / K = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} v \sqrt{\Sigma G_{\nu_{i23}}^2 (\theta_{p_{23}})} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} v \Sigma G_{\nu_i} / K = 0.1297_{-0.0023}^{+0.0019} \text{ eV}. \quad (20.7)$$

This median at 3 digits is the same as that in (15.4), but the 3σ error bar in (20.7) is tighter than that in (15.4) by a factor of about 5.7, which is why we have shown a fourth digit in (20.7).

There is no difference at all between (20.5) and (8.3). But now, unlike at (8.3), we have definitive predictions at (18.2) for the neutrino mass sum and at (18.1) for the triplet of individual eigenstate masses. So, (20.5) leads to the disassembly of Einstein's constant earlier seen in (9.1) and therefore to the Lagrangian (9.9) and **Figure 1** for the rest frame interaction between the elementary particles of a dust tensor, using the linear approximation of the Einstein equation without cosmological constant. And as pointed out following **Figure 1**, because the Einstein constant in (9.1) using (9.6) is equal to the conversion constant $\hbar c$ times products and ratios of particle energies and interaction couplings all known to be renormalizable – with K itself being independent of renormalization scheme and scale as seen clearly in the direct connection of the neutrino data to the gravitational constant in (20.5) via (20.1) – the gravitational interaction of elementary particle quanta illustrated in **Figure 1**, mediated by interface gravitinos, neutrino loop cliffs, and long-range gravitons, is fully renormalizable. And because of the neutrino loop cliffs, the physics by which gravitational weakness is tied to the very small neutrino masses can be very clearly seen and understood.

PART IV: DARK ENERGY AND MATTER

21. Gravitational Lagrangian with cosmological constant, for a perfect fluid tensor

Now, let us return to and retrace the analysis of **Section 9**, but with two changes: First, we shall include the cosmological constant Λ in the Einstein equation. Second, for the energy tensor, we shall employ the perfect fluid tensor rather than the dust tensor to which the fluid reduces when its pressure is set to zero.

With Λ included the linear Newtonian approximation of the Einstein equation now becomes $-\kappa T^{\mu\nu} = \partial_\sigma \partial^\sigma \phi^{\mu\nu} + g^{\mu\nu} \Lambda$. So by the same calculation which followed (9.1), when we isolate the graviton field we obtain $\phi^{\mu\nu} = \kappa \hbar^2 T^{\mu\nu} / q_\sigma q^\sigma + g^{\mu\nu} \hbar^2 \Lambda / q_\sigma q^\sigma$ and a trace $\phi = \kappa \hbar^2 T / q_\sigma q^\sigma + 4 \hbar^2 \Lambda / q_\sigma q^\sigma$. As a result, the general form of the Lagrangian (9.2) now becomes:

$$\mathcal{L} = -2\hbar^3 c^3 \left(T^{\mu\nu} \phi_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} a T \phi \right) = -2\kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(T^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} a T^2 + (1+2a) T \Lambda / \kappa \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma. \quad (21.1)$$

Before we even insert the perfect fluid tensor into the above, we see that this naturally introduces the ratio $\rho_\Lambda \equiv \Lambda / \kappa$ which has dimensions of energy density. It is reported in in [11] and [24] respectively, that $G_N = 6.70883(15) \times 10^{-39} \hbar c (c^4 / \text{GeV}^2)$ and $\Lambda = 1.088(30) \times 10^{-82} \text{ fm}^{-2}$, the latter being a $\Lambda > 0$. Also, with $\hbar c = 0.1973269804 \text{ GeV fm}$ from [11], and error bars for G_N and Λ taken to be mutually independent, we can calculate that this energy density:

$$\rho_\Lambda \equiv \Lambda / \kappa = c^4 \Lambda / 8\pi G_N = 3.270(90) \times 10^{-36} \text{ eV} / \text{fm}^3 = 5.83(16) \times 10^{-30} \text{ g} / \text{cm}^3, \quad (21.2)$$

which is synonymous with the energy density of dark energy reported in [24]. So, we may rewrite (21.1) as:

$$\mathcal{L} = -2\kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(T_{(1)}^{\mu\nu} T_{(2)\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} a T_{(1)} T_{(2)} + (1+2a) T_{(1)} \rho_\Lambda \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma. \quad (21.3)$$

Above, as at (9.5), similarly to the $G_N m_1 m_2$ numerator of Newton's law, we distinguish the interacting energy tensor sources, while noting that $T_{(1)} \rho_\Lambda$ does not lend itself to this distinction so for now shows $T_{(1)}$ alone.

The positive cosmological constant is the source of the dark energy ρ_Λ , as seen clearly in (21.2).

Now, we turn to $T^{\mu\nu} = (\rho_0 + p) u^\mu u^\nu - p g^{\mu\nu}$ for a perfect fluid, where ρ_0 is the proper energy density, p is a pressure which likewise has dimensions of energy-per-volume, i.e., force per area, and the four-velocity is the dimensionless $u^\mu = \left(1 / \sqrt{1 - v^2 / c^2} \quad (\mathbf{v} / c) / \sqrt{1 - v^2 / c^2} \right)$. When $p=0$, this of course becomes the dust tensor. In the linear approximation, from a metric tensor $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ with a timelike Minkowski signature $\text{diag}(\eta_{\mu\nu}) = (1 \quad -1)$, one easily obtains $u^\mu u_\mu = 1$. So, the contracted $T_{(1)}^{\mu\nu} T_{(2)\mu\nu} = \rho_{01} \rho_{02} + 3 p_1 p_2$, and the trace $T = \rho_0 - 3p$ thus $T_{(1)} T_{(2)} = (\rho_{01} - 3p_1)(\rho_{02} - 3p_2)$. Therefore, using this perfect fluid tensor, the gravitational Lagrangian (21.3) now becomes:

$$\mathcal{L} = -2\kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{2} a\right) \rho_{01} \rho_{02} - \frac{3}{2} a (p_{01} p_2 + p_1 p_{02}) + \left(3 + \frac{9}{2} a\right) p_1 p_2 + (1+2a) (\rho_{01} - 3p_1) \rho_\Lambda \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma. \quad (21.4)$$

Below and above the Vainshtein length, where $a = -\frac{2}{3}$ and $a = -1$ respectively, (21.4) becomes:

$$\mathcal{L} \left(a = -\frac{2}{3} \right) = -\frac{2}{3} \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(2\rho_{01} \rho_{02} + 3(p_{01} p_2 + p_1 p_{02}) - (\rho_{01} - 3p_1) \rho_\Lambda \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma; \quad (21.5)$$

$$\mathcal{L} \left(a = -1 \right) = -\kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(\rho_{01} \rho_{02} + 3(p_{01} p_2 + p_1 p_{02}) - 3p_1 p_2 - 2(\rho_{01} - 3p_1) \rho_\Lambda \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma. \quad (21.6)$$

In the special case of the 1, 2 densities equal, $\rho_{01} = \rho_{02} \equiv \rho_0$ and $p_1 = p_2 \equiv p$, (21.5), (21.6) simplify to:

$$\mathcal{L} \left(a = -\frac{2}{3} \right) = -\frac{2}{3} \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(2\rho_0 (\rho_0 + 3p) - (\rho_0 - 3p) \rho_\Lambda \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma; \quad (21.7)$$

$$\mathcal{L} \left(a = -1 \right) = -\kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(\rho_0^2 + 6\rho_0 p - 3p^2 - 2(\rho_0 - 3p) \rho_\Lambda \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma. \quad (21.8)$$

Subject to the limitation that this uses the linear Newtonian approximation of the Einstein equation, the special cases described by (21.7) and (21.8) will apply exactly to interactions between dust and pressure densities ρ_0 and p within any region of spacetime over which these densities are constant, because one will have $\rho_{01} = \rho_{02}$ and $p_1 = p_2$ as between densities at distinct events $(t, \mathbf{x})_1$ and $(t, \mathbf{x})_2$ within such a region. This means that (21.7) and (21.8) provide a good approximation to (21.5) and (21.6) for interactions between energy densities in regions of spacetime over which these densities are fairly uniform.

22. Gravitational Lagrangian for dark energy, dark matter, and ordinary matter

As was pointed earlier at (9.3), the overall minus sign in the Lagrangian is what causes gravitation to be an attractive interaction. For positive energy densities ρ_0 and pressure p , and with $\Lambda=0$ so $\rho_\Lambda = 0$, (21.7) is always negative thus attractive, and (21.8) can become repulsive, but only when $\rho_0^2 + 6\rho_0 p - 3p^2 < 0$, which is to say, when $p > \left(1 + \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}\right)\rho_0 = 2.154701 \cdot \rho_0$, as obtained from the solution for this quadratic inequality. But with a nonzero and indeed positive Λ , these two Lagrangian densities can indeed become positive, resulting in a repulsive form of gravity that warrants, and to which we shall give, closer attention.

From here, let us work solely with (21.5) and (21.7) which apply below the Vainshtein length. We begin by studying the circumstance where (21.5), and for the special case of (21.7) that applies to a fairly uniform density, are equal to zero, $\mathcal{L} = 0$. We shall refer to this as the ‘‘Lagrangian vacuum,’’ or ‘‘Lvac’’ for short. Proceeding, the circumstance where $\mathcal{L}(a = -\frac{2}{3}) = 0$ in (21.7) is given by the quadratic:

$$0 = 2\rho_0^2 + 6p\rho_0 - \rho_\Lambda\rho_0 + 3\rho_\Lambda p. \quad (22.1)$$

Now, it is customary to use $\Omega \equiv \rho / \rho_{\text{crit}}$ with suitable subscripts to define dimensionless ratios of various cosmological densities over the critical density of the universe ρ_{crit} . These individualized densities ρ are *average densities* over the entire universe. It is reported in [24] that the dark energy density parameter is $\Omega_\Lambda = \rho_\Lambda / \rho_{\text{crit}} = 0.685(7)$, that the cold dark matter density parameter is $\Omega_c = \rho_c / \rho_{\text{crit}} = 0.265(7)$, and that the baryon density parameter $\Omega_b = \rho_b / \rho_{\text{crit}} = 0.0493(6)$. The 0.7% error bars between Ω_Λ and Ω_c run oppositely; that is, if the former is above median by some amount, then the latter is below by the same amount, and vice versa. Therefore, $\rho_c / \rho_\Lambda = \Omega_c / \Omega_\Lambda = 0.387(14)$.

With this in mind, for reasons that will momentarily become apparent, let us define $\rho_0 \equiv \rho_c$ as the energy density of cold dark matter. Noting that the perfect fluid tensor trace $T = \rho_0 - 3p$ contain thrice the pressure, let us restructure (22.1) to isolate $3p / \rho_\Lambda$, then use the data in the preceding paragraph to calculate:

$$3\frac{p}{\rho_\Lambda} = 3\frac{\Omega_p}{\Omega_\Lambda} = \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_\Lambda} \frac{1 - 2\rho_c / \rho_\Lambda}{1 + 2\rho_c / \rho_\Lambda} = \frac{\Omega_c}{\Omega_\Lambda} \frac{1 - 2\Omega_c / \Omega_\Lambda}{1 + 2\Omega_c / \Omega_\Lambda} = 0.0494_{-0.0054}^{+0.0050} \equiv \Omega_b = \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_{\text{crit}}}. \quad (22.2)$$

Above, the upper error bar corresponds with larger Ω_c and smaller Ω_Λ , and vice versa for the lower error bar. Comparing, we see that the observed $\Omega_b = \rho_b / \rho_{\text{crit}} = 0.0493(6)$ fits entirely within the error bars of (22.2), and that the lesser precision of (22.2) by a factor of just over 10 is attributable to the greater precision of Ω_b reported out to four decimal places, versus that of Ω_Λ and Ω_c out to only three places. This fit of (22.2) with the reported Ω_b is what retrospectively justifies the association $\rho_0 \equiv \rho_c$ at the start of this paragraph, and also, the association $\Omega_b = \rho_b / \rho_{\text{crit}} \equiv 3p / \rho_\Lambda = 3\Omega_p / \Omega_\Lambda$ in (22.2). The latter implies that the perfect fluid pressure is related to the baryon density by $3p = \Omega_\Lambda \rho_b$. Also, (22.2) implies the quadratics:

$$0 = \Omega_b \Omega_\Lambda^2 + (2\Omega_c \Omega_b - \Omega_c) \Omega_\Lambda + 2\Omega_c^2 = 2\Omega_c^2 + (2\Omega_b \Omega_\Lambda - \Omega_\Lambda) \Omega_c + \Omega_b \Omega_\Lambda^2. \quad (22.3)$$

This greater precision of $\Omega_b = 0.0493 \pm 0.0006$ can be used with (22.3) to obtain a more precise dark energy and matter parameters. The result of that calculation, which uses $\Omega_\Lambda + \Omega_c + \Omega_b \equiv 1$ as a very close approximation, is obtained in the + root solutions of (28.4), namely $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.6832 \pm 0.0004$ and $\Omega_c = 0.2675 \mp 0.0010$ (note the opposite error bar direction of Ω_c relative to Ω_Λ and Ω_b). When we use the reported data from [24] with the same error correlations, and also include the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) radiation density of the universe, reported by [24] to be $\Omega_\gamma = \rho_\gamma / \rho_{\text{crit}} = 5.38(15) \times 10^{-5}$ and use this in the error bars, we find a total:

$$\Omega_{\text{tot}} = \rho_{\text{tot}} / \rho_{\text{crit}} = \Omega_\Lambda + \Omega_c + \Omega_b + \Omega_\gamma = (\rho_\Lambda + \rho_c + \rho_b + \rho_\gamma) / \rho_{\text{crit}} = 0.9994(6). \quad (22.4)$$

At the top of this range, to four digit accuracy, (22.4) is equal to the critical density, while at median, the total ρ_{tot} of all energy densities fall ever-so-slightly below the critical ρ_{crit} .

Finally, as pointed out just after (21.1), dark energy only arises by virtue of a non-zero cosmological constant. Moreover, were we to solve for the quadratic Ω_c in (22.3) and then set $\Lambda=0$ and thus $\Omega_\Lambda = 0$ we would obtain $\Omega_c = 0$, meaning there would be no cold dark matter either (in different notations, but fully applicable here, this is seen by setting $\Theta_{\text{DE}} = 0$ in (28.1)). Consequently, dark energy and dark matter would not exist but for a nonzero, positive cosmological constant.

23. Proof using general covariance, of a flat Euclidean spatial curvature for the universe

With the associations contained in (22.2), we now return to the Lagrangian (21.5) for two distinct energy densities 1, 2. We first use the association $\rho_0 = \rho_c$ in (22.2) to take each of ρ_{01} and ρ_{02} to be equal to the densities of cold dark matter. And with $3p_{1,2} = \Omega_\Lambda \rho_{b1,2} = \rho_\Lambda \rho_{b1,2} / \rho_{\text{crit}}$ in (22.2), we also set 3 times each of p_1 and p_2 to be equal to baryon (ordinary) matter densities, times the $\Omega_\Lambda = \rho_\Lambda / \rho_{\text{crit}}$ cold dark matter parameter. So from (21.5), with $a = -\frac{2}{3}$ no longer explicitly shown, we now obtain an Lvac:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{2}{3} \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left(2\rho_{c1}\rho_{c2} + \rho_\Lambda (\rho_{c1}\rho_{b2} + \rho_{b1}\rho_{c2}) / \rho_{\text{crit}} - \rho_\Lambda (\rho_{c1} - \rho_\Lambda \rho_{b1} / \rho_{\text{crit}}) \right) / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma = 0. \quad (23.1)$$

Of course, all of the foregoing dark energy, dark matter, and ordinary (baryonic) matter densities are *average densities* over the entire universe, and will vary both over and under these averages at different locales. So because the associations in (22.2) were all obtained by setting $\mathcal{L} = 0$ in (21.7), the above (23.1) will apply to Lvac regions where the uniform density approximation of (21.7) can be applied. Our goal now, is to generalize (23.1) that we know applies to uniform spacetime regions with $\mathcal{L} = 0$, to spacetime regions where $\mathcal{L} \neq 0$, in which gravitation may become attractive $\mathcal{L} < 0$ or repulsive $\mathcal{L} > 0$. In attractive regions we experience in everyday life on earth, or in our solar system, the total density ρ becomes much larger than ρ_{crit} . In repulsive regions we do not experience at all, the foregoing would have to assume values that bring \mathcal{L} above zero. The only uniform densities to which we cannot generalize (23.1), are those approaching the order of black holes, due to very large curvatures where the Newtonian linear approximation underlying (23.1) no longer comes close to applying and the full nonlinear Einstein equation is needed.

To start, let us simply make a notation change in the density subscripts in (23.1), whereby we replace $\rho_\Lambda = \rho_{\text{DE}}$ (Dark Energy), $\rho_c = \rho_{\text{DM}}$ (Dark Matter), and $\rho_b = \rho_{\text{M}}$ (ordinary Matter), rewriting (23.1) as:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{2}{3} \kappa \hbar^5 c^5 \left[2\rho_{\text{DM1}}\rho_{\text{DM2}} + \frac{\rho_{\text{DE}}}{\rho_{\text{crit}}} (\rho_{\text{DM1}}\rho_{\text{M2}} + \rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{DM2}}) - \rho_{\text{DE}} \left(\rho_{\text{DM1}} - \frac{\rho_{\text{DE}}\rho_{\text{M1}}}{\rho_{\text{crit}}} \right) \right] = 0. \quad (23.2)$$

Again, this still has $\mathcal{L} = 0$ because of the values of the energy densities employed.

Now, the Lagrangian in (23.2) is at bottom a local scalar number which is invariant under general coordinate transformations and boosts and remains valid wherever the Newtonian linear approximation holds. So other than having to stay within the linear realm, there is no limit to how large we can make each of the dark energy, dark matter and ordinary matter densities. All that will happen is that \mathcal{L} will go from being zero, to having either a negative value indicative of gravitational attraction, or a positive value for repulsion. The one feature of (23.2) that we shall now examine closely, is the presence of ρ_{crit} in two of the denominators in (23.2).

First, we see in (22.4) that $\rho_{\text{tot}} = 0.9994(6)\rho_{\text{crit}} \cong \rho_{\text{crit}}$. That is, the total of all average energy density types is very close to the critical density. And, because this relation was obtained from the Newtonian approximation of the Einstein equation, this would not account for additional energies that could arise from extreme spacetime curvatures that exist in very limited regions throughout the universe – such as near or inside a black hole or a body collapsing into a black hole – which could possibly bridge this small gap to bring

about a Euclidean $\rho_{\text{tot}} = \rho_{\text{crit}}$. But without relying on a specific mechanism for this, suppose we increase all the individual densities in (23.2) by a huge factor, say, 10^{27} , to bring them close to the somewhat ordinary density of 1 kg/m^3 . With ρ_{crit} unchanged, the two terms that distribute to $\rho_{\text{DM1}}\rho_{\text{DM2}}$ and $\rho_{\text{DE}}\rho_{\text{DM1}}$ would then enlarge by a factor of 10^{54} , while $\rho_{\text{DE}}\rho_{\text{DM1}}\rho_{\text{M2}}$, $\rho_{\text{DE}}\rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{DM2}}$, and $\rho_{\text{DE}}^2\rho_{\text{M1}}$ terms would scale by 10^{81} . So $\mathcal{L} \cong -\left(\frac{2}{3}\kappa\hbar^5c^5/c^2q_\sigma q^\sigma\right)(\rho_{\text{DE}}/\rho_{\text{crit}})\left(\frac{2}{3}\kappa\hbar^5c^5/c^2q_\sigma q^\sigma\right)[\rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{DM2}} + \rho_{\text{DM1}}\rho_{\text{M2}} + \rho_{\text{DE}}\rho_{\text{M1}}]$ would approximate (23.2) to one part in 10^{27} and the remaining terms would be effectively lost. Further, (23.2) is rooted in (21.5), and this Lagrangian magnitude should clearly grow with the square – not the cube – of the densities it contains, particularly because the growth of gravitation as a function of interacting energies – starting with the $G_N m_1 m_2$ in Newton’s law – is a product of two, not three, interacting energies.

Accordingly, because as it stands in the linear approximation, $\rho_{\text{tot}} \cong \rho_{\text{crit}}$ to better than 1 part per thousand as seen in (22.4), let us for the moment simply define the constant α by $\rho_{\text{tot}} \cong \alpha\rho_{\text{crit}}$, where $\alpha = 1.0006(6)$ to four digits based on (22.4), subject to the possibility of this constant being adjusted when the full nonlinear Einstein field equation is applied. Then, we use this to rewrite (23.2) as:

$$\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x}) = -\frac{\frac{2}{3}\kappa\hbar^5c^5}{c^2q_\sigma q^\sigma} \left[2\rho_{\text{DM1}}\rho_{\text{DM2}} + \alpha\frac{\rho_{\text{DE}}}{\rho_{\text{tot}}}(\rho_{\text{DM1}}\rho_{\text{M2}} + \rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{DM2}}) - \rho_{\text{DE}} \left(\rho_{\text{DM1}} - \alpha\frac{\rho_{\text{DE}}\rho_{\text{M1}}}{\rho_{\text{tot}}} \right) \right]. \quad (23.3)$$

Here, however, after simply changing ρ_{crit} to ρ_{tot}/α , because all parts of this \mathcal{L} will now scale properly, we can release each of the densities from simply being the Lvac densities of (21.2) and (22.2) with the tightened parameters shown prior to (22.4), and can regard them as density fields $\rho(t, \mathbf{x})$ which can vary freely in spacetime. This enables us to remove the $\mathcal{L} = 0$ from (23.1) and (23.2), and have $\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x})$ in (23.3). Particularly, $\rho_{\text{tot}} = \rho_{\text{DE}} + \rho_{\text{DM}} + \rho_{\text{M}} + \rho_{\text{E}}$ will now scale with the individual density increases and thereby grow the Lagrangian magnitude in proportion to the squares of the densities. In contrast, ρ_{crit} in (23.2) is a constant density and so does not scale with other densities. When the individual densities are those of (21.2) and (22.2) as tightened thereafter, ρ_{tot} will drop to $\alpha\rho_{\text{crit}}$ and \mathcal{L} will go to $\mathcal{L} = 0$. Otherwise, taking each of the individual densities and their total as input data, (23.3) enables us to calculate the Lagrangian $\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x})$ no matter what the densities $\rho(t, \mathbf{x})$, and no matter whether $\mathcal{L} < 0$ where gravitation is attractive or $\mathcal{L} > 0$ where gravitation is repulsive. The only restriction is that for extremely large densities that start to veer toward black hole territory, (23.3) must be further generalized using the full nonlinear Einstein equation.

Finally, by the foregoing, *we can actually use the principle of general covariance to prove that the average total density of energy in the universe is exactly equal to its critical density*, whereby the spatial curvature of the universe must be flat, i.e., Euclidean, and is not and cannot be open or closed. Let us now show how this is proved:

1) The Einstein equation $-\kappa T^{\mu\nu} = R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu}R + g^{\mu\nu}\Lambda$ is generally covariant. 2) So too is its linear approximation $-\kappa T^{\mu\nu} = \partial_\sigma \partial^\sigma \phi^{\mu\nu} + g^{\mu\nu}\Lambda$. The latter simply does not apply where curvatures become extremely large. But for densities as small as ρ_Λ in (21.2) and the other extremely tiny densities ρ_c , ρ_b , ρ_γ and ρ_{crit} that are part of (22.4), it certainly applies virtually exactly, and it applies quite fairly for ordinary densities on earth and within the solar system and comparable systems. 3) Therefore, the Lagrangian (21.5) for interacting perfect fluids is generally covariant – and is in fact an invariant scalar field – applicable to all but the very largest densities. 4) Comparing the two covariant equations (21.5) and (23.3), we see that the latter contains the extra constant α while the former does not. Yet, once the associations $\rho_0 = \rho_{\text{DM}}$ and $3p = \rho_{\text{DE}}\rho_{\text{M}}/\rho_{\text{tot}}$ are made based on the data connections of (22.2), and once the generalized notations introduced at (23.2) are used, (21.5) and (23.3) must simply be different expressions of the exact same Lagrangian

density. 5) Yet, there is a mismatch between these two identical versions of the exact same Lagrangian. In (21.5) there is no α . Or, more precisely, it is implicit that $\alpha = 1$. But in (23.3) it is possible to have an $\alpha \neq 1$. 6) If the covariant (21.5) is correct for linear fields – as it is – then (23.3) cannot seamlessly, covariantly express into the special case of (21.5) unless the constant $\alpha = 1$ in (23.3). To hold otherwise would be akin to saying the Einstein equation with κ applies for some densities, but it only applies with a different $\alpha\kappa$ for others. 7) Consequently, because of the general covariance of (21.5), it is required to have $\alpha = 1$ in (23.3).

In this way, we have used the principle of general covariance to prove that *the average total density of the universe must be exactly equal to its critical density, whereby the spatial curvature of the universe as a whole must be neither open nor closed, but is flat i.e., Euclidean.*

24. Attractive, neutral and repulsive gravitation: The gravitational strength parameter

Having used the principle of general covariance to establish that the average $\langle \rho_{\text{tot}} \rangle = \rho_{\text{crit}}$, let us now define $\Theta(t, \mathbf{x}) \equiv \rho(t, \mathbf{x}) / \rho_{\text{tot}}(t, \mathbf{x})$ as a dimensionless ratio of each type of DE, DM, M and E (ordinary Energy) energy density over the total energy density, forming a dimensionless set of fields at each and every event point in spacetime. Then, setting $\alpha = 1$ in (23.3), we multiply (23.3) through by $1 = \rho_{\text{tot}}^2 / \rho_{\text{tot}}^2$, factor out this numerator, and use the denominator to introduce the various $\Theta = \rho / \rho_{\text{tot}}$, thereby obtaining:

$$\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x}) = -\frac{\frac{2}{3}\kappa\hbar^5 c^5 \rho_{\text{tot}}^2}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma} \left[2\Theta_{\text{DM1}}\Theta_{\text{DM2}} + \Theta_{\text{DE}} (\Theta_{\text{DM1}}\Theta_{\text{M2}} + \Theta_{\text{M1}}\Theta_{\text{DM2}}) - \Theta_{\text{DE}} (\Theta_{\text{DM1}} - \Theta_{\text{DE}}\Theta_{\text{M1}}) \right]. \quad (24.1)$$

Then, let us multiply (24.1) through by $1 = \Theta_{\text{M1}}\Theta_{\text{M2}} / \Theta_{\text{M1}}\Theta_{\text{M2}}$, factor out the numerator, set $\Theta_{\text{M1}}\Theta_{\text{M2}}\rho_{\text{tot}}^2 = \rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{M2}}$, and define a new dimensionless parameter P, from which we obtain:

$$\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x}) = -P \frac{\frac{2}{3}\kappa\hbar^5 c^5 \rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{M2}}}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma}; \text{ where } P \equiv 2 \frac{\Theta_{\text{DM1}}}{\Theta_{\text{M1}}} \frac{\Theta_{\text{DM2}}}{\Theta_{\text{M2}}} + \Theta_{\text{DE}} \left(\frac{\Theta_{\text{DM1}}}{\Theta_{\text{M1}}} + \frac{\Theta_{\text{DM2}}}{\Theta_{\text{M2}}} \right) - \frac{\Theta_{\text{DE}}}{\Theta_{\text{M2}}} \left(\frac{\Theta_{\text{DM1}}}{\Theta_{\text{M1}}} - \Theta_{\text{DE}} \right). \quad (24.2)$$

Now, we compare (24.2) with (9.3) written as $\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x}) = -2 \frac{2}{3}\kappa\hbar^5 c^5 \rho_{0(1)}\rho_{0(2)} / c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma$. The energy densities ρ_{M1} and ρ_{M2} which we have factored out in (24.2) are for ordinary matter, and therefore are physically identical to the respective energy densities $\rho_{0(1)}$ and $\rho_{0(2)}$ in (9.3). That is, $\rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{M2}} = \rho_{0(1)}\rho_{0(2)}$. So the only difference is that (24.2) contains P which is variable which depends upon the various dark energy and matter parameters, while in (9.3), which applies to everyday regions of spacetime with densities many orders of magnitude larger than the densities in Lvac, simply P=2, whereby combined with (24.2) we have:

$$P = 2 \frac{\Theta_{\text{DM1}}}{\Theta_{\text{M1}}} \frac{\Theta_{\text{DM2}}}{\Theta_{\text{M2}}} + \Theta_{\text{DE}} \left(\frac{\Theta_{\text{DM1}}}{\Theta_{\text{M1}}} + \frac{\Theta_{\text{DM2}}}{\Theta_{\text{M2}}} \right) - \frac{\Theta_{\text{DE}}}{\Theta_{\text{M2}}} \left(\frac{\Theta_{\text{DM1}}}{\Theta_{\text{M1}}} - \Theta_{\text{DE}} \right) = 2. \quad (24.3)$$

So, depending on the density mix of dark matter and energy in relation to the ordinary matter and energy that is interacting, P can be zero whereby $\mathcal{L} = 0$ and gravitation is neutral as in the Lvac, or we can have P>0 whereby gravitation is attractive as we always experience including the P=2 of (9.3), or we can have P<0 in which event gravitation becomes repulsive in the “subvacuum.” Because P operates independently of the $\rho_{\text{M1}}\rho_{\text{M2}}$ product to establish both the magnitude and sign of \mathcal{L} , including the possibility of $\mathcal{L} = 0$, $\mathcal{L} < 0$ and $\mathcal{L} > 0$ which affects the strength and attractiveness versus repulsiveness of gravitation, we shall refer to P as the “gravitational strength parameter.” And although this strength parameter $P(t, \mathbf{x})$ and the $\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x})$ are fields varying throughout spacetime, they are obtained by holding the Newton and cosmological constants G_N and Λ to being constants throughout spacetime. Particularly, this means that the Newton / Einstein constants do not have to become “not constant” in order for gravitational strength to vary in accordance with changes in the DE, DM and M densities, including as between attraction, neutrality and repulsion. We simply also need to have a constant positive cosmological constant as a supplement to these constants.

25. Dark energy gravitons and dark matter neutrino loops

Now, let us substitute (9.1) into (24.2) and use $g_K = 12/K$ as defined at (9.4) to obtain:

$$\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1}{2} P \pi \hbar^6 c^6 \frac{g_K^4 \langle E_{vi} \rangle^4}{6v^2 (\Delta E)^4} \frac{\rho_{M1} \rho_{M2}}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma}. \quad (25.1)$$

Because $\rho_{M1} \rho_{M2} = \rho_{0(1)} \rho_{0(2)}$, it will be seen that (25.1) is identical to (9.4) with the sole exception of the factor $\frac{1}{2} P$ which, in (9.4), is equal to 1. So, with the same steps used from (9.5) to (9.9), we can turn (25.1) into:

$$\frac{6K_{(1)} K_{(2)} \mathcal{L}}{\pi \hbar^6 c^6} = -\frac{1}{2} P \left[\rho_{M1} g_{(1)} \frac{1}{E_{\Psi(1)}^3} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{c^2 q_\sigma q^\sigma} g_K \langle E_{vi} \rangle \right] \left[\langle E_{vi} \rangle g_K \frac{1}{E_{\Psi(2)}^3} g_{(2)} \rho_{M2} \right]. \quad (25.2)$$

The only difference between (25.2) and (9.9) is that (25.2) contains the gravitational strength parameter P defined in (24.2) which can vary to produce attractive, repulsive and neutral gravitation depending upon the various dark and ordinary energy and matter densities, whereas in (9.9), $P=2$, as shown explicitly in (24.3). So, similarly to what was illustrated in **Figure 1**, but with some additional features to be momentarily reviewed, (25.2) can be represented with the Feynman diagram of **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Feynman diagram illustrating (25.2) for gravitational interactions which can be attractive, repulsive or neutral depending upon dark energy and matter densities

Figure 3, illustrates the long-range gravitational interaction between two elementary particle energy densities $\rho_{M1} = E_{M1} \psi_{M1}^\dagger \psi_{M1}$ and $\rho_{M2} = E_{M2} \psi_{M2}^\dagger \psi_{M2}$, and is identical in all respect to **Figure 1** except for its containing the gravitational strength parameter P which produces attractive gravitation for $P > 0$ including the $P = 2$ gravitation of our common experience (illustrated by the blue lines), repulsive gravitation in spacetime regions where $P < 0$ (red lines), and neutral gravitation in the Lvac where $P = 0$ (green lines). As seen in (24.2) which applies generally in any circumstances where the linear Newtonian approximation of the Einstein equation may be applied, the value of P depends upon the densities of all of the dark matter, dark energy, and ordinary energy in the spacetime region being considered.

Now, when we speak of “dark” matter and energy, we refer to energy densities of rest matter and luminous energy which we do not, and perhaps cannot, directly observe. Yet, we infer their existence from other observations, include the gravitational behaviors of the cosmos in relation to the critical density. But all the matter and energy that we can and do observe is composed of a small number of elementary particles which we can very clearly enumerate: quarks and leptons including neutrinos, massive W and Z bosons, massless photons, gluons which although massless are confined inside hadrons and so detected in the rest energies of these hadrons, and the Higgs boson. The other anticipated elementary particles, not yet detected, are gravitinos and gravitons. So as to dark matter and energy, are compelled to ask: Are dark matter and energy composed of elementary particles just like matter and energy we can and do observe? And if so, do dark matter and energy comprise some of the just-mentioned elementary particles? Or, are there some additional elementary particles involved that we do not presently know about? And at bottom, presuming that

everything “dark” is still composed of elementary particles just like everything that is “not dark,” then we must finally ask: *What are the specific elementary particles which constitute dark matter and energy?*

It was seen in **Figure 1** and now again in **Figure 3**, that neutrino loops which act as “cliffs” responsible for the weakness of long-range gravitation, never interact directly with the interacting ordinary energy densities ρ_{M1} and ρ_{M2} . Similarly, the gravitons do not interact directly with ρ_{M1} and ρ_{M2} . The direct interactions are always channeled through a gravitino “interface.” The neutrino loops consist of matter because neutrinos do have three nonzero rest mass eigenstates, while the gravitons consist of energy because they are massless and luminous. Because these neutrino loops and gravitons never interact directly with ordinary matter, and because the devices and facilities we use to detect physics phenomena, as well as our five human senses, are all constructed from ordinary matter, these neutrino loops and gravitons can never be *directly* detected. While we may infer their existence by other means, their lack of direct detectability renders these neutrino loops and gravitons “dark” with respect to our experimental detection devices and sensory perception. As such, when they are mediating gravitation in this loop form, neutrinos have the necessary features to be the elementary particles of *dark matter*, as highlighted in **Figure 3**. Moreover, gravitons, have the necessary features to be the elementary particles of *dark energy*, also highlighted in **Figure 3**. All of these “dark” elements of the gravitational interactions, have been enclosed within the illustrated “dark gravitation” box in **Figure 3**.

So, as a consequence of the foregoing, we now introduce the following two *hypotheses*:

- 1) The gravitons $\phi^{\mu\nu}$, which mediate long-range gravitational interactions between elementary particles, are the elementary particles of *dark energy* (DE).
- 2) The neutrinos ν are observable in their own right among the elementary particles of ordinary matter (M). But, when they form gravitational cliff loops as seen in **Figures 1 and 3**, they are not observable. There is always a gravitino superpartner interjecting itself between the neutrino loop and the elementary particle. These neutrinos which are involved in gravitational interactions and are responsible for gravitation being extremely weak in relation to all other interactions, which we denote as ν_{DM} to distinguish from ordinary matter neutrinos denoted by ν_M , are the elementary particles of *dark matter* (DM).

Finally, as pointed out following (22.4), the very existence of a nonzero cosmological constant is what gives rise to the very existence of dark energy and matter. So, if these hypotheses are true, then gravitons only exist, physically, because of a $\Lambda > 0$, and the neutrino loops in **Figures 1 and 3** also would not physically exist without this $\Lambda > 0$. In short, *gravitation as we know it requires not only the Einstein equation, but the Einstein equation with a nonzero, positive cosmological constant*. Now, let us examine the specific mechanisms by which these dark energy gravitons and dark matter neutrino loops operate to influence the strength of gravitation.

26. Dark particle energies and densities

With the foregoing two hypotheses, let us return to the Lvac and set out to estimate certain average cosmological densities of interest. First, for the density of ordinary matter neutrinos ν_M , [24] reports that $\Omega_{\nu M} = h^{-2} \Sigma m_{\nu_i} / 93.14 \text{ eV}$ with $h = 0.674(5)$ from CMB anisotropies. So, if we use the mass sum $\Sigma m_{\nu_i} = 0.0785_{-0.0040}^{+0.0043} \text{ eV}$ obtained in (18.2) and match the lowest h^{-2} with the lowest Σm_{ν_i} and highest with highest we obtain $\Omega_{\nu M} = 0.00186_{-0.00012}^{+0.00013}$. Then, with $\rho_{crit} = 8.53(13) \times 10^{-30} \text{ g/cm}^3$ likewise calculated from [24], we calculate that the average cosmological density of ordinary matter neutrinos is:

$$\rho_{\nu M} = 1.58_{-0.12}^{+0.14} \times 10^{-32} \text{ g/cm}^3 = 8.88_{-0.70}^{+0.77} \times 10^{-39} \text{ eV/fm}^3. \quad (26.1)$$

Then, as noted following (9.9), because of the oscillation of neutrinos among their three eigenstates, the neutrino mass expectation value $\langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle$ later shown tightened in (18.3) is the most suitable quantity to use when speaking about observed neutrino masses. So, we can use (26.1) divided by (18.3) to calculate that the numbers (#) density for the neutrinos of ordinary matter neutrinos is:

$$\rho_{\#\nu M} = 339.38_{-9.93}^{+10.23} \nu_M / \text{cm}^3. \quad (26.2)$$

This accords well with [25], which reports a “total density of all neutrinos about 336 per cm^3 .”

Now we turn to dark matter neutrinos ν_{DM} . It was earlier mentioned that the baryon (ordinary matter) density parameter which we now denote as $\Omega_{\text{M}} = 0.0493 \pm 0.0006$ can be used with quadratic solutions of (22.3) to obtain at (28.4), what we now denote as $\Omega_{\text{DE}} = 0.6832 \pm 0.0004$ and $\Omega_{\text{DM}} = 0.2675 \mp 0.0010$ for dark energy and matter, respectively, with error bars, as noted, running oppositely. If the hypothesis following **Figure 3** is correct, that neutrino loops are the elementary field quanta of dark matter, this means that $\Omega_{\nu_{\text{DM}}} = 0.2675 \mp 0.0010$, and therefore, that $\Omega_{\nu_{\text{DM}}} / \Omega_{\nu_{\text{M}}} = 144.17_{-10.03}^{+10.59}$. In other words, for every observable ordinary matter neutrino, on average, at median there are about 144.17 neutrinos involved in gravitational interactions in the nature of **Figure 3**, which are dark matter neutrinos that cannot be directly detected. Using (26.2), we calculate that the average numbers density for *dark matter neutrinos* is

$$\rho_{\#\nu_{\text{DM}}} = 48,929.25_{-4735.62}^{+5178.43} \nu_{\text{DM}} / \text{cm}^3. \quad (26.3)$$

Because the gravitating neutrinos form $\nu\bar{\nu}$ pair loop “cliffs,” the density of these loops is half of the above, that is, at median, there are an average of 24464.63 gravitating neutrino loops per cubic centimeter.

This now gives us an inroad to the dark energy of gravitons. Although it is possible as pointed out at (13.1) for a newly-created neutrino loop to decay right back into a gravitino without ever emitting a graviton, for present purposes let us discount the frequency of occurrence for this sort of interaction, and simply estimate that whenever a dark neutrino loop is created, it decays into a dark graviton. With **Figure 3** informing us that each graviton is “guarded” by a neutrino loop both at its creation and its annihilation, we can divide the number density in (26.3) by 4 to estimate that average numbers density for *dark matter gravitons* is:

$$\rho_{\#\phi_{\text{DE}}} = 12,232.31_{-1183.90}^{+1294.61} \phi_{\text{DE}} / \text{cm}^3 = 1.223_{-0.118}^{+0.130} \times 10^{-35} \phi_{\text{DE}} / \text{fm}^3. \quad (26.4)$$

That is, we can estimate that the average density in the universe of the luminous speed gravitons which according to **Figure 3** constitute dark energy, at median, is about 12,232.31 gravitons per cubic centimeter.

Then, similarly to (26.1) we use $\Omega_{\text{DE}} = 0.6832 \pm 0.0004$ and $\rho_{\text{crit}} = 8.53(13) \times 10^{-30} \text{ g/cm}^3$ to calculate the average cosmological density of dark energy, luminous gravitons, namely:

$$\rho_{\phi_{\text{DE}}} = 5.83(8) \times 10^{-30} \text{ g/cm}^3 = 3.27(5) \times 10^{-36} \text{ eV/fm}^3. \quad (26.5)$$

Then, dividing (26.5) by (26.4) we calculate the average energy of each dark energy graviton in the universe:

$$\langle E_{\phi} \rangle = \hbar \langle \nu_{\phi} \rangle = 0.267_{-0.029}^{+0.033} \text{ eV}. \quad (26.6)$$

Comparing (26.6) with $\langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle = 0.0262_{-0.0013}^{+0.0014} \text{ eV}$ from (18.3), we see that the average dark graviton energy is about 10.22 times as large as the neutrino rest energy.

This final comparison, along with the requirement for energy conservation, gives us a way to determine the average kinetic energy and therefore the average velocity of the dark matter neutrinos that weaken the gravitational interaction as illustrated in **Figure 3**. The first loop on the left of **Figure 3** carries a neutrino and antineutrino which decay into a graviton. The masses of the neutrino and antineutrino will of course be the same, as with any particle and its antiparticle. Because this graviton is massless and can travel over unlimited distances, we must regard this as a real particle for which $q_{\sigma} q^{\sigma} = 0$. At median on average, this graviton carries an energy of about 0.262 eV as seen in (26.6). But the masses of the neutrino and antineutrino only add to $2 \langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle = 0.0523_{-0.0027}^{+0.0029} \text{ eV}$. At median, this leaves the graviton with an extra 0.218 eV of energy above the energy that can be obtained from the rest energy expectation value of what can be supplied by the neutrino and antineutrino in the loop. To conserve energy, this additional energy needs to be come from the kinetic energies K_{ν} of the neutrinos. So, let us now calculate this.

For simplicity, if we regard the kinetic energies and velocities of the neutrino and antineutrino in the first loop to be equal, then in $c=1$ units, with $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-v_{\nu}^2}$, the total energy carried by this loop will $E_{\text{loop}1} = 2\gamma \langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle$. Then, when this loop decays into the graviton, this loop will have to carry enough energy to produce a graviton with the luminous energy (26.6), whereby:

$$2\gamma \langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle = 2 \langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle + 2K_{\nu} = 2 \langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle / \sqrt{1-v_{\nu}^2} = \langle E_{\phi} \rangle. \quad (26.7)$$

Using (26.6) and $\langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle = 0.0262_{-0.0013}^{+0.0014}$ eV to calculate with maximal error bars, this we arrive at:

$$\langle v_\nu \rangle = \sqrt{1 - \left(2 \langle m_{\nu_i} \rangle / \langle E_\phi \rangle \right)^2} = 0.981_{-0.008}^{+0.006} \cdot c; \quad K_\nu = 0.108_{-0.016}^{+0.018} \text{ eV.} \quad (26.8)$$

When the graviton decays, its energy is then passed along to the second neutrino loop. So, on average throughout the cosmos, having used the linear approximation of the Einstein equation, each neutrino participating as dark matter in a gravitational interaction as illustrated by **Figure 3**, travels at about 98% of the speed of light, and carries an average kinetic energy of about 0.108 eV.

27. Quadratic relations among dark energy and matter, and ordinary matter

For another perspective on dark energy gravitons and dark mater neutrino loops, we now return to the gravitational strength parameter defined in (24.2), and restructure this into:

$$P\Theta_{M1}\Theta_{M2} = 2\Theta_{DM1}\Theta_{DM2} + \Theta_{DE}\Theta_{DM1}\Theta_{M2} + \Theta_{DE}\Theta_{M1}\Theta_{DM2} - \Theta_{DE}\Theta_{DM1} + \Theta_{M1}\Theta_{DE}^2. \quad (27.1)$$

Then, if we consider a fairly uniform region of spacetime where we may approximate and define $\Theta_M \equiv \Theta_{M1} = \Theta_{M2}$ and $\Theta_{DM} \equiv \Theta_{DM1} = \Theta_{DM2}$, this converts to the quadratic:

$$0 = \Theta_M\Theta_{DE}^2 + 2\Theta_M\Theta_{DM}\Theta_{DE} - \Theta_{DM}\Theta_{DE} + 2\Theta_{DM}^2 - P\Theta_M^2, \quad (27.2)$$

which can be solved as any of the functions $\Theta_{DE}(\Theta_{DM}, \Theta_{DM})$ or $\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_{DE}, \Theta_M)$ or $\Theta_M(\Theta_{DE}, \Theta_{DM})$.

Now, if we add up the Θ parameters for energy densities of dark energy, dark matter, ordinary matter and ordinary energy, we will of course have $\Theta_{DE} + \Theta_{DM} + \Theta_M + \Theta_E = 1$, because all energies in the universe fall into one of these four classes. But the density Θ_E always remains comparatively small, because the very vast preponderance of ordinary photonic energy arises from the CMB, which is substantially homogeneous and isotropic. So, we may use $\Theta_{DE} + \Theta_{DM} + \Theta_M \cong 1$ as a close approximation which states that virtually all densities at any given spacetime event are those of dark energy, dark matter and ordinary matter.

We then use the very close approximation $\Theta_{DE} + \Theta_{DM} + \Theta_M = 1$ to turn (27.2) into three alternative quadratics that eliminate one of each of these three densities, namely:

$$0 = (2\Theta_{DE} + P - 2)\Theta_{DM}^2 - (-3\Theta_{DE}^2 + \Theta_{DE} - 2P(\Theta_{DE} - 1))\Theta_{DM} - (-\Theta_{DE}^3 + \Theta_{DE}^2 - P(\Theta_{DE}^2 - 2\Theta_{DE} + 1)), \quad (27.3)$$

$$0 = (3 - \Theta_M)\Theta_{DM}^2 - (1 - \Theta_M)\Theta_{DM} - (-\Theta_M^3 + (2 + P)\Theta_M^2 - \Theta_M), \quad (27.4)$$

$$0 = (2\Theta_{DE} + P - 2)\Theta_M^2 - (-\Theta_{DE}^2 + 7\Theta_{DE} - 4)\Theta_M - (3\Theta_{DE}^2 - 5\Theta_{DE} + 2). \quad (27.5)$$

These are readily solved to produce the three respective alternative solutions:

$$\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_{DE}) = \frac{-3\Theta_{DE}^2 + \Theta_{DE} - 2P\Theta_{DE} + 2P \pm \sqrt{\Theta_{DE}^4 + 10\Theta_{DE}^3 - 7\Theta_{DE}^2 + 12P\Theta_{DE}^2 - 20P\Theta_{DE} + 8P}}{4\Theta_{DE} - 4 + 2P}, \quad (27.6)$$

$$\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_M) = \frac{1 - \Theta_M \pm \sqrt{4\Theta_M^4 - 20\Theta_M^3 - 4P\Theta_M^3 + 29\Theta_M^2 + 12P\Theta_M^2 - 14\Theta_M + 1}}{6 - 3\Theta_M}, \quad (27.7)$$

$$\Theta_M(\Theta_{DE}) = \frac{-\Theta_{DE}^2 + 7\Theta_{DE} - 4 \pm \sqrt{\Theta_{DE}^4 + 10\Theta_{DE}^3 - 7\Theta_{DE}^2 + 12P\Theta_{DE}^2 - 20P\Theta_{DE} + 8P}}{4\Theta_{DE} + 2P - 4}. \quad (27.8)$$

We shall now study what these relations (27.6) through (27.8) tell us about gravitation in the three circumstances illustrated in **Figure 3**, where $P > 0$, $P < 0$ and $P = 0$. These correspond respectively to attractive gravitation, repulsive gravitation, and neutral gravitation in the Lvac. For attractive gravitation we shall set $P = 2$, because as we saw at (24.3), this describes gravitation in our everyday experience. And simply to illuminate what happens when gravitation is repulsive, we shall choose to sample $P = -2$. In the following section we examine neutral $P = 0$ and repulsive $P = -2$ gravitation together, because as we shall see, their behaviors are similar. In the following section we examine the $P = 2$ gravitation of our common experience.

28. Neutral P=0 and repulsive P=-2 gravitation in the Lagrangian vacuum and subvacuum, and a tighter cosmological constant

We start in the $P = 0$ thus $\mathcal{L} = 0$ Lagrangian vacuum, where (27.6) through (27.8) simplify to:

$$\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_{DE}, P=0) = \left(-3\Theta_{DE}^2 + \Theta_{DE} \pm \Theta_{DE} \sqrt{\Theta_{DE}^2 + 10\Theta_{DE} - 7} \right) / 4(\Theta_{DE} - 1), \quad (28.1)$$

$$\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_M, P=0) = \left(1 - \Theta_M \pm \sqrt{4\Theta_M^4 - 20\Theta_M^3 + 29\Theta_M^2 - 14\Theta_M + 1} \right) / (6 - 3\Theta_M), \quad (28.2)$$

$$\Theta_M(\Theta_{DE}, P=0) = \left(-\Theta_{DE}^2 + 7\Theta_{DE} - 4 \pm \Theta_{DE} \sqrt{\Theta_{DE}^2 + 10\Theta_{DE} - 7} \right) / 4(\Theta_{DE} - 1). \quad (28.3)$$

Then, because (27.2) with $P=0$ is equivalent to (22.3) with each Ω replaced by Θ , we can use the \pm root solutions of (28.2) along with $\Omega_b = 0.0493(6)$ which is about an order of magnitude tighter than the empirical $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685(7)$ and $\Omega_c = 0.265(7)$ reported by [24], with subscript replacements $DM \rightarrow c$, $DE \rightarrow \Lambda$ and $M \rightarrow b$ and the close approximation $\Theta_{DE} + \Theta_{DM} + \Theta_M = 1$ used to obtain (27.3) through (27.5), to calculate the tightened density parameters first referenced following (22.3):

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_b &= 0.0493 \pm 0.0006; & \Omega_\Lambda^+ &= 0.6832 \pm 0.0004; & \Omega_c^+ &= 0.2675 \mp 0.0010; \\ \Omega_b &= 0.0493 \pm 0.0006; & \Omega_\Lambda^- &= 0.8933 \mp 0.0015; & \Omega_c^- &= 0.0574 \pm 0.0009. \end{aligned} \quad (28.4)$$

The + root solutions fall well within the reported errors bars, and tighten the dark density error bars by about an order of magnitude. The only density neglected in the approximation is $\Omega_\gamma = 5.38(15) \times 10^{-5}$, which only impacts the fifth decimal place by ± 0.00006 . Note also that in the + root solution, the dark matter density run oppositely to the other two, while in the - root solutions, dark energy runs counter to the other two.

Also, the tighter Ω_Λ^+ in (28.4) enables us to compute a cosmological constant:

$$\Lambda = \kappa \Omega_\Lambda \rho_{crit} = 1.088(16) \times 10^{-82} \text{ fm}^{-2} \quad (28.5)$$

with error bars virtually halved in relation to $\Lambda = 1.088(30) \times 10^{-82} \text{ fm}^{-2}$ reported by [24].

Now, we do not observe dark energy and matter. Ordinary matter and energy are all that we can directly detect. Being able to work from what we can and do observe, is one reason we segregated the density product $\rho_{M1}\rho_{M2}$ when going from (24.1) to (24.2) where we first identified the strength parameter P . Similarly, here we will find it useful to work from $\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_M)$ in (28.2) because this contains the parameter Θ_M for ordinary matter we can observe, and obtains the unobservable Θ_{DM} thus $\Theta_{DE} \cong 1 - \Theta_M - \Theta_{DM}$ as a function of this. At the same time, let us set $P=-2$ in (27.7) to obtain the subvacuum function corresponding to (28.2), namely:

$$\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_M, P=-2) = \left(1 - \Theta_M \pm \sqrt{4\Theta_M^4 - 12\Theta_M^3 + 5\Theta_M^2 - 14\Theta_M + 1} \right) / (6 - 3\Theta_M). \quad (28.6)$$

Then, we graph Θ_{DM} of both (28.2) and (28.6), and Θ_{DE} , all together on the same plot as a function of Θ_M , as well as $\Theta_M = \Theta_M$ as a straight line "y=x" function to compare the behavior of Θ_M with Θ_{DM} and Θ_{DE} . Because (28.2) and (28.6) are both quadratic solutions, there are both + and - root plots for each, and these converge to the same solution when the quartic $4\Theta_M^4 - (20 - 4P)\Theta_M^3 + (29 + 12P)\Theta_M^2 - 14\Theta_M + 1$ interior to each root becomes zero. The result is **Figure 4**.

First, each of Θ_{DE} , Θ_{DM} and Θ_M must be a real parameter bounded by $0 \leq \Theta \leq 1$. So as it turns out, for the $P=0$ Lvac, the root interiors drop below zero and the root becomes imaginary whenever $\Theta_M > 0.0858$ to four places. So for $P=0$, the domain of ordinary matter is restricted to $0 \leq \Theta_M \leq 0.0858$. This is also the domain point at which the + and - roots join together. For our $P=-2$ sampling of the subvacuum, we see a very similar set of curves with all the same characteristics, except now, the matter domain is more tightly constrained to $0 \leq \Theta_M \leq 0.073007$. We can readily extrapolate that in regions where gravitation becomes

repulsive, the greater the repulsive strength, the smaller the domain for Θ_M . As in **Figure 3**, in **Figure 4** the plots for Θ_{DE} , Θ_{DM} when $P=0$ are shown in green, and when $P=2$ in they are in red, with the indicated broken line characters. The + and - root solution are marked as such. The straight line $\Theta_M = \Theta_M$ curve is common to both set of other curves, and is shown as a solid, unbroken black line.

Figure 4: Dark energy and matter, and ordinary matter density parameters, for neutral $P=0$ and repulsive $P=-2$ gravitation, plotted from (28.2) and (28.6)

It is also illustrative to look closely at the domain point where $\Theta_M = 0.0493$ and the three stars used for highlighting, because this is the median of the parameter Ω_b in (28.4) reported to be $\Omega_b = 0.0493(6)$ by [24]. On the + root portions of the green $\Omega=0$ curves, we see that the range points are $\Theta_{DM} = 0.2675$ and $\Theta_{DE} = 0.6832$, which also reproduces the reported $\Omega_c = 0.265(7)$ and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685(7)$. In other words, up to the neglected $\Omega_\gamma = 5.38(15) \times 10^{-5}$, at $\Theta_M = 0.0493$, this $P=0$ plot fully reproduces the average cosmological dark energy and matter densities.

Turning to repulsive gravitation sampled at a $P=-2$ subvacuum, this does not differ too much from the $P=0$ Lvac. At the same $\Theta_M = 0.0493$, the dark matter $\Theta_{DM} = 0.2592$ thus slightly below the Lvac value, and the dark energy $\Theta_{DE} = 0.6915$ which is slightly higher than its Lvac level. So as gravitation becomes more repulsive, for the + root solutions, at a given ordinary matter density parameter, the dark matter decreases and the dark energy increases. For the - root solutions, it can be seen that the dark matter increases and the dark energy decreases. And of course, it is notable that there are two sets of solutions because of the fact that these originate in quadratics. Finally, it will be noted that for either strength P , at $\Theta_M = 0$ the dark matter parameter intersects the y axis at 0 and $1/3$, while the dark energy parameter intersects at $2/3$ and 1. This is also true for any other P .

So, in the Lvac where gravitation is neutral, we find that as the dark energy increases over its permitted domain from $\frac{2}{3} \leq \Theta_{DE} \leq 1$, the dark matter decreases over the domain $\frac{1}{3} \geq \Theta_{DM} \geq 0$. And, the ordinary matter starts at zero, and when $\Theta_{DE} \cong 0.757$ whereby $\Theta_{DM} \cong 0.1572$, it reaches a peak at its upper bound $\Theta_M \cong 0.0858$. In all instances, wherever $\mathcal{L}(t, \mathbf{x}) = P(t, \mathbf{x}) = 0$, the dark energy constitutes at least 2/3 of all the energy, the dark matter constitutes no more than 1/3 of all the energy, the ordinary matter can never constitute more than about 8.58% of the total energy, and the dark matter neutrino loop density is always larger than the ordinary matter density except when $\Theta_{DE} = 1$ and all the energy is dark energy gravitons.

If we sample additional $P < 0$ parameters for repulsive gravitation, for example, $P = -4$, we see that the curves qualitatively look the same as those in **Figure 4**, but that the upper limit for Θ_M at the domain point where the + and - solutions join, moves even further to the left. This means that a greater strength of gravitational repulsion goes hand in hand with less ordinary matter and more dark matter and energy. That is, stronger repulsion occurs in spacetime regions where there is comparatively less ordinary matter.

29. Attractive $P=+2$ ordinary gravitation

Now we turn to ordinary $P=+2$ gravitation for which (27.7) becomes:

$$\Theta_{DM}(\Theta_M) = \left(1 - \Theta_M \pm \sqrt{4\Theta_M^4 - 28\Theta_M^3 + 53\Theta_M^2 - 14\Theta_M + 1}\right) / (6 - 3\Theta_M). \quad (29.1)$$

Now with plots in blue corresponding with **Figure 3**, the illustration of **Figure 5** reveals that for attractive $P=2$ gravitation, the density parameter plots have a very different character than the neutral and repulsive plots of **Figure 4**. Although the functions are not linear, over the restricted domain $0 \leq \Theta \leq 1$ for all density parameters, these functions are close to linear. Moreover, $4\Theta_M^4 - 28\Theta_M^3 + 53\Theta_M^2 - 14\Theta_M + 1$ inside the root of descends to zero, and then increases again without over going below zero, at the point (0.1492, 0). So this is where the + and - root solutions meet, and interestingly, the - root curves interchange with the + root curves to precisely continue the "almost lines" of these curves, at the 0.1492 domain point.

Figure 5: Dark energy and matter, and ordinary matter density parameters, for ordinary attractive $P=+2$ gravitation, plotted from (29.1)

The domain point at $\Theta_M = 0.0493$ is marked for comparative purposes with **Figure 4**. Here, the + root produces $\Theta_{DM}^+ = 0.2725$ and $\Theta_{DE}^+ = 0.6755$ which are slightly higher and lower, respectively, than their Lvac values of (28.4) which correspond to the reported average densities. So, for a similar matter density,

attractive gravitation using the + root solution is a sign of an above average dark matter (neutrino loop) and below average (graviton) density. There are also several other especially noteworthy aspects of **Figure 5**.

First, the negatively-sloped dark matter density drops below zero at 0.2679, which sets a maximum domain boundary for the negative root solutions. But the – root line for Θ_{DM} over $0 \leq \Theta_M \leq 0.1492$ which turns uninterrupted into the + root line from $0.1492 \leq \Theta_M \leq 0.4753$, always runs slightly above the truly straight line for $\Theta_M = \Theta_M$ i.e., $y=x$. So, the dark matter density here, for attractive gravitation, is always slightly larger than that for ordinary matter. Meanwhile, the – root dark energy plot which starts at (0, 1) and transitions into the + root at the domain point 0.1492, drops to zero at 0.4753. So, this is what places an absolute upper bound of $\Theta_M \leq 0.4753$ on ordinary matter. At this upper bound where $\Theta_{DE}^+ = 0$, the dark matter $\Theta_{DM}^+ = 0.5247 > \Theta_M = 0.4753$. This is the upper extremum example of how the ordinary matter density is always slightly less than the dark matter density along the positively-sloped dark matter curve.

Comparing **Figures 4 and 5**, we see that attractive gravitation occurs in spacetime regions where the ordinary matter parameter Θ_M can grow all the way up to 0.4753, just shy of $\frac{1}{2}$, while the dark energy parameter Θ_{DE} becomes much smaller and can reach zero. Conversely, as already observed, repulsive gravitation occurs where there is much less ordinary matter, and a much greater share of the total density arises from dark densities. Physically, the regions of spacetime where we observe attractive gravitation are on earth and in our solar system and galaxy, where matter densities are greater than they would be, for example, in intergalactic space where there is a dearth of ordinary matter. So, the gravitational repulsion would be in precisely the lowest-density intergalactic regions where there is little if any ordinary matter.

Additionally, the short-range, strong gravitational variant of (13.2) and (13.3) and **Figure 3** which involves gravitinos alone without any gravitons or neutrinos, and the intermediate range and strength variant of (13.1) which involves only gravitinos and neutrino loops without gravitons, appear to explain the + root solution in **Figure 5** over the domain where the dark energy graviton parameter trends toward zero, and the dark matter neutrino loop and the ordinary matter parameters trend toward 0.5247 and 0.4753 respectively. Regions where $\Theta_M \rightarrow 0.4753$ would be those in which matter is at its densest (in the linear approximation), likely on hadronic scales right near or inside a baryon. This is precisely where the gravitational interaction variant of **Figure 3** will occur with femtometer $c\bar{\tau}$ ranges that can be seen in (12.2) through (12.5) for the heaviest gravitinos. In these interactions, there are no dark energy gravitons, which accounts for the $\Theta_{DE} \rightarrow 0$ domain in **Figure 3**. At the same time, the (13.1) interaction variant will transpire over slightly larger ranges. So this domain for **Figure 5** appears to suggest that on nuclear scales, all of the gravitational interactions are the short or intermediate range and strong or intermediate strength interactions of (13.1) through (13.3). All of the foregoing has two apparent consequences, and raises an additional question:

First, the above appears to validate the hypotheses of **Section 25**, that the gravitons *are* dark energy and neutrino loops *are* dark matter. Specifically, intergalactic regions of spacetime, by definition, are regions where there is the smallest density of ordinary matter. One would expect these regions to be traversed by little more than gravitons that originated eons earlier in denser galactic regions, as well as photons and neutrinos with similar long-ago, distant origins. And indeed, this larger share of gravitons and neutrinos, if these are indeed dark energy and matter respectively, would manifest in these intergalactic regions as the repulsive gravitation illustrated in **Figure 4**. In short: repulsive gravitation occurs in intergalactic regions where there is a dearth of ordinary matter and an excess of the gravitons and neutrinos which constitute dark energy and matter, just as is seen in **Figure 4**. And the hypothesis that gravitons are the dark energy particles also appears validated by the no-graviton gravitational variant summarized in the last paragraph coupled with the trend of dark energy densities toward zero toward the right side of **Figure 5**.

Second, this would mean that as the ordinary energy density Θ_E containing light consisting of photons travels through intergalactic regions where gravitation is repulsive, this repulsion acting between photonic electromagnetic field energy excitations carrying this light will gradually push these excitations further and

further apart, in proportion to the distance this light travels. And this will, in turn, bring about a redshift that varies linearly with distance, and is therefore observationally indistinguishable from the Hubble redshift. Yet, this redshift does not require expansion of the cosmos as a whole. It arises quite naturally from a repulsive gravitational interaction in intergalactic regions of the cosmos. Moreover, if the already-tiny ordinary matter densities in these subvacuum regions should further thin out over time, then this would increase the strength of gravitational repulsion in these intergalactic regions, whereby the redshift would also increase over time and create the impression that the supposed expansion of the universe is also supposedly accelerating. To be sure, it is possible, but not certain, that this gravitational repulsion is also expanding the universe, and accelerating that expansion. But if that is so, this expansion and its acceleration could be no more than secondary, corollary effects arising from gravitational repulsion in intergalactic spacetime.

Additionally, once it is understood that gravitation becomes repulsive in certain physical environments, the question immediately presents whether there is some way that gravitational repulsion might push back on gravitational collapse inside extremely dense spacetime regions such as black holes. Because the development here has only used the linear Newtonian approximation, we cannot presently answer this. We therefore leave this open for future study, of necessity employing the full nonlinear Einstein equation.

PART V: CONCLUSION

30. The connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is genuine new physics, not a numeric accident

In anticipation that one might conclude the connection first established by the numeric match at (8.1) relating ΔE to a neutrino square mass sum using a GST relation $\tan \Theta = \sqrt{v/E_p}$ is simply a numeric accident and not a genuine indicator of new physics, we now review why this would be and is a wrong conclusion.

Statistical probabilities: First, independent of any related physics, let us simply assess the probability that this connection is a statistical accident. The energy shift ΔE tightened at (20.3) has a median on the order of 40.857 MeV. The presently-reported 0.06eV spread [8] of the neutrino mass sum runs from 0.06 eV to 0.12 eV. So, if we use the ratio of 40 MeV to 0.04 eV for estimation, the ratio of these two energies is 10^8 , crossing eight orders of magnitude. Now, the heaviest elementary particle is the top quark, which in [4] has a reported direct measurement mass of 172.69(30) GeV. So, to estimate statistical probabilities, suppose we generate a uniformly-distributed random number with energy dimensions anywhere between 0.02 eV which is 1/3 of the lower bound for the neutrino mass sum, and 200 GeV which a bit larger than the top quark mass. The spread for these random numbers thereby crosses 13 orders of magnitude, $200 \text{ GeV} / 0.02 \text{ eV} = 10^{13}$. The chance that a random number uniformly generated somewhere within these 13 orders of magnitude will happen to land inside this 0.06 eV reported spread for the neutrino mass sum, is one out of $10^{13} / 0.06 = 1.67 \times 10^{15}$, that is, one out of 1.67 quadrillion. Six-sigma statistical confidence for the probability of a result being accidental, is one part per 500 million. So, hitting inside in the neutrino mass sum spread of 0.06 eV with a random number between 0.02 eV and 200 GeV, is more than six orders of magnitude less likely than a six-sigma event. Of course, choosing the top quark mass to set the upper bound of the randomized number generation does minimize the probability of the neutrino connection being accidental. But even if one were to use the 40.857 MeV of ΔE itself as the upper bound whereby $40.857 \text{ MeV} / 0.02 \text{ eV} = 2.04 \times 10^9$, the chance of this connection to the neutrino masses being an accident would still be one part out of 3.4×10^{10} , which is still about 70 times less likely than a six-sigma event. So, while one might choose different variants for framing this analysis, it can be stated with confidence well in excess of six-sigma, merely on a statistical basis, that the connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses obtained here, is no numeric accident.

Neutrino intercession in gravitational interactions: Of course, estimating statistical confidence is only a first step. If this numeric connection between gravitational weakness and neutrino masses is no accident, it becomes imperative to decipher the new physics this reveals. And, if this is no accident, it would make intuitive sense that neutrinos and their small masses would have to be physically involved in gravitational interactions in some fashion. **Figure 1** clearly shows the precise mechanism by which the small neutrino masses are responsible for gravitational weakness. Specifically, in long-range gravitational interactions, massive elementary particles *directly* interact, *only* with their massive gravitino superpartners. And, there is

always a neutrino / antineutrino loop interceding between the gravitino “interface” to elementary particles, and the massless gravitons which carry the gravitational interaction over unlimited distances. Gravitinos and gravitons are both gravitational interaction carriers. As such, the strength of the interactions between gravitinos and neutrinos, and between neutrinos and gravitons, will be proportional to the neutrino masses, i.e., gravitational charges. And because the neutrino mass expectation value in (18.3) is smaller than the electron mass by a factor of almost 20 million, and by even larger factors for all other massive elementary particles, this creates an interaction “cliff” which is the root cause of the physics phenomenology whereby long-range gravitational interactions are very much weaker than all the other interactions.

Renormalizable gravitational interactions, and gravitational unification: One of the most important unsolved problems in theoretical physics, is to uncover a theory in which gravitational interactions become renormalizable, in the same way that the electroweak and strong interactions are known to be renormalizable. The gravitational interaction Lagrangian of (9.9), which arises directly from the disassembly of the Einstein constant at (9.1) coupled with the renormalizable couplings and masses in (9.6) and (9.8), consists entirely of energies and couplings that we know how to renormalize as the result of electroweak and strong interaction theory. The only elements of (9.9) other than these renormalizable quantities, are some dimensionless constants, and the conversion constant $\hbar c$. Indeed, as a result, the Newton / Einstein constants are no longer independent constants, but are assembled from products and ratios of other couplings arising from electroweak and strong interactions. Consequently, *not only does gravitation become renormalizable, but it becomes unified with these other interactions at the quantum particle level.*

Connection of the energy shift ΔE to other physically-meaningful quantities: The energy shift first obtained in (4.7) and later tightened at (20.3) does start out as an arbitrary shift used to produce GST-type relations for the PMNS angles θ_{p12} and θ_{p13} . So, the question does arise whether this energy shift is in some way measurable, and how this energy shift is to be physically understood, in its own right. First, we see at (8.2) that this energy shift directly establishes the Yukawa coupling sum for the neutrino masses, in relation to both the Fermi vev and the Planck vev / energy. This is later connected directly to the neutrino mass sum at (20.7). So, this energy shift is a central component of the Yukawa couplings for neutrinos, and it is inherently measured whenever neutrino masses are measured, similarly to how other Yukawa couplings are measured when other particle masses are measured. Second, as seen in and discussed at (9.8), this energy shift is also a 2/3 power “anchor” energy which establishes the rest energies of the gravitinos, and which provides an empirical rather than conjectural foundation for a supersymmetry between massive gravitinos and massive elementary particles. This would be measurable any time a gravitino mass is measured. Moreover, as reviewed in **Section 14**, it appears quite possible that some of these gravitino masses have in fact already been measured as the mass of the sigma “meson,” misunderstood to be a single strong interaction meson, when in reality it is quite possibly an assemblage of wide-width gravitino superpartners for the W and Z and Higgs bosons and the top quark, as further detailed in [18]. In short, it may well be that this ΔE is already being implicitly but unknowingly measured in experiments that detect the sigma meson.

Predictions affording opportunities for experimental contradiction: If one were to still maintain the view that the connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is a numeric accident and not genuine physics in view of the foregoing, there are also several predictions that have been made here which can be experimentally tested as it becomes possible to measure the neutrino masses and mixing angles with greater precision than at present.

First, the prediction at (18.2), see also (20.2), that the neutrino mass sum has a median at 0.0785, and with 3σ confidence sits within the domain:

$$\text{predicted: } 0.0745 \text{ eV} \leq \Sigma m_{\nu_i} \leq 0.0828 \text{ eV}; \quad \text{reported: } 0.06 \text{ eV} \leq \Sigma m_{\nu_i} \leq 0.12 \text{ eV} \quad (30.1)$$

tightens the presently-reported bounds [8] by a factor of about 7.2. Second, for the real PMNS angles, the tightened 3σ values predicted in (20.4), as compared to the presently-reported 3σ values in (3.4), are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{predicted: } \theta_{p12} &= 32.035^{+0.186\circ}_{-0.224}; & \theta_{p13} &= 8.675^{+0.062\circ}_{-0.074}; & \theta_{p23} &= 42.081^{+0.378\circ}_{-0.453}; \\ \text{reported: } \theta_{p12} &= 33.41^{+2.33\circ}_{-2.10}; & \theta_{p13} &= 8.58^{+0.33\circ}_{-0.35}; & \theta_{p23} &= 42.2^{+8.8\circ}_{-2.5}. \end{aligned} \quad (30.2)$$

Any experiments which tighten this reported data and demonstrate the observed value of any of these angles to be substantially outside these predicted values, would contradict the results presented here. Conversely, if further tightening does not contradict the predicted values above, this would further support

the view that this connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is no numeric accident. The same may be said of any future experimental reporting that enables comparison with the normal ordered neutrino mass predictions in (18.1). But the failure to rule out these predictions as tighter experimental data is reported in the future, would lend empirical support to the view that this connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is, indeed, no numeric accident.

Likewise, if the sigma meson can be shown to be a conflation of the gravitino superpartners of the W , Z , h and t elementary particles, with masses in (11.1) through (11.4), then as discussed in **Section 14** here and detailed in [18], this would further support the view that this connection is no accident. Indeed, clear identification of these gravitino masses would be a direct detection and confirmation of the anchor energy ΔE first obtained at (4.7) to fit the PMNS angles to the charged lepton masses. Finally, the dark matter and energy development leads at (28.4) to a substantial tightening of the cosmological dark energy and matter densities, and at (28.5) to a tightening of the cosmological constant error bars by a factor of 2, offering yet more possibilities for experimental contradiction or support.

Dark energy and matter: Once these nonaccidental connections are made between small neutrino masses and gravitational weakness and then used to obtain (25.2) and **Figure 3**, we are able for the first time to specifically identify gravitons as the elementary particle field quanta of dark energy, and neutrinos in neutrino loops as the field quanta excitations of dark matter. This leads via energy conservation to the definitive physical result in (26.6) that the luminous dark energy gravitons have an average energy of about 0.267 eV, which is just over ten times as massive as the expectation value rest energy of an oscillating neutrino. And it leads to the result in (26.8) that neutrinos in the dark energy neutrino loop cliffs which vastly weaken the strength of the gravitational interaction, propagate on average at about 98% of the speed of light. Further physical insights into dark energy and dark matter in relation to observable matter are provided by **Figures 4 and 5**, including the likelihood that gravitation becomes repulsive under suitable mixes of dark versus ordinary densities such as those in the red line plots of **Figure 4**.

31. Summary and conclusion

It has long been understood that gravitation is very weak in relation to the electroweak and strong interactions. Since the confirmation in 1998 [2] that the neutrinos are massive not massless, it is also known that neutrinos have exceedingly small masses in comparison to all the other massive elementary particles. In the introduction, we previewed the *hypothesis* later formalized in **Section 5**, that the extreme weakness of gravitation relative to all other interactions, is directly interconnected with, and caused by, the extreme smallness of the neutrino masses in relation to all the other elementary particle masses.

So, with a pair of GST relations employed as a pedagogic starting point, after calculating an energy shift $\Delta E \sim 40.86$ MeV at (4.7) by which two of the three real PMNS angles can be fitted to the charged lepton masses, it became essential to determine whether this energy shift has some physical significance, and if so, what that might be, beyond the prospective data match in (4.9). Therefore, as a first test of the foregoing *hypothesis*, to quantify the small size of the neutrino masses, at (5.1) we calculated the ratio of the neutrino mass sum over this ΔE , and to quantify the weakness of gravitation relative to other interactions, at (5.3) we calculated a GST type ratio of the Fermi vev to the Planck energy. Upon comparing, we saw that these ratios differed simply by an approximate square root of 2 factor which could be accounted for by the Yukawa couplings of all fermion masses to the Fermi vev. This motivated us to further advance this *hypothesis*.

After considering that the neutrino mass sum and square mass sum are both pertinent, independent parameters in the neutrino mass variance (6.1), it became possible at (8.1) to formally connect the tiny neutrino masses to the extreme weakness of gravitation via the square mass sum, within experimental errors. Most notably, in the restructured form of (8.3), this connection made it possible to express the Newton constant entirely as a function of the Fermi vev, the foregoing ΔE , and the neutrino mass sum, as well as the two fundamental constants \hbar and c . For reasons elaborated in the preceding section, independent of any additional new physics that might emerge, the statistical confidence is well in excess of six-sigma, that this connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is no numeric accident.

In **PART II** we used this connection in the Newtonian linear approximation of the Einstein equation with a zero cosmological constant and a dust energy tensor, to obtain a Lagrangian (density) (9.9) for the gravitational interaction between the energy densities of two elementary particles, and illustrated this in **Figure 1** using the standard rules for constructing Feynman diagrams. This revealed that at the quantum

level, each massive elementary particle gravitates by first emitting a massive gravitino supersymmetry partner, which then decays into a neutrino loop which creates a “cliff” responsible for gravitational weakness, which then decays into a massless graviton that is the long-range carrier of gravitation. To interact with a second elementary particle, this graviton decays into a second neutrino loop, which then decays into a second gravitino, which is finally absorbed by its elementary particle superpartner. This entire chain of interactions and decays is summarized concisely by (10.1). Beyond the physical importance of simply understanding how gravitation transpires at the quantum particle level, the appearance in (9.9) of nothing other than $\hbar c$ and a set of masses and couplings that are all renormalizable, reveals a long-sought renormalizable theory of gravitation. A short range and strong variant of the gravitational interaction which may be observable in hadronic experiments is also uncovered at (13.1) to (13.3) and **Figure 2**.

The masses of these gravitino interfaces between the elementary particles and the neutrino loops and gravitons, are specified generally by (9.8), and specifically obtained at (11.1) through (11.6), with the ΔE shift operating as an “anchor” energy for these gravitino masses. In view of the strong, short-range gravitational variant of **Figure 2**, and given that the heaviest of these predicted gravitino masses at median are 511.939 MeV, 533.933 MeV, 593.52 MeV and 658.03 MeV with very wide widths, in the same mass and width domain as the historically-challenging $f_0(500)$ a.k.a. sigma meson [22], [23], the prospect is raised that the sigma meson may not be a hadronic meson at all. Rather, it may well be a collection of the four gravitinos which are the superpartners of the W , Z and Higgs bosons and the top quark. If this can be experimentally established by a revisiting of the sigma meson data as explored in detail in [18], this would constitute the very first detection of gravitational interactions at the quantum particle level, and firmly validate many results here.

In **PART III**, we returned to the neutrino masses and mixing angles. At (18.1) through (18.3) we calculated specific values for the individual normal ordered neutrino eigenstate masses, the mass sum, and the mass average which is the expected value of the mass one would register when detecting an oscillating neutrino. As noted at (30.1), this prediction tightens the presently reported mass sum by a factor of just about 7.2, and provides another good data point for contradiction or support from future experimental work. After tightening the energy shift ΔE at (20.3), the PMNS angles are also tightened at (20.4), see also (30.2), providing further opportunity for experimental comparison. If desired, the analysis that led to the foregoing mass data can also be applied to inverted ordering neutrino mass data reported in [10].

Finally, in **PART IV**, we resumed the development of **PART II**, but now using linear approximation with cosmological constant and a perfect fluid tensor. This first provided a point of contact at (21.2) with the reported [24] average density ρ_Λ of dark energy. Then, upon examining the conditions at (22.1) under which the gravitational Lagrangian density of (21.7) becomes zero (the Lagrangian vacuum “Lvac”), we also connected at (22.2) with the average densities ρ_c of cold dark matter and ρ_b of ordinary baryonic matter. And, we showed how dark energy and dark matter would not exist at all, but for a nonzero, positive cosmological constant. Upon generalizing the Lagrangian density to (23.3) so it can be applied to regions of spacetime other than the Lvac where the dark and ordinary densities can and do vary from their averages, we applied the principle of general covariance to prove at the end of **Section 23** that the average total density of the universe must be exactly equal to its critical density, whereby the spatial curvature of the universe as a whole must be neither open nor closed, but is flat i.e., Euclidean.

Working from this result, we were able to develop the gravitational Lagrangian into the more-general form of (24.2) to account for dark energy and matter in addition to ordinary matter, and thereby identified a gravitational strength parameter P which is entirely dependent upon the mixes of dark and ordinary densities, and which can yield gravitational attraction, repulsion, or neutrality depending upon these mixes. This strength variation does not in any way entail the Newton / Einstein gravitational constants being anything other than constant. It simply requires a constant positive cosmological constant to supplement the Newton / Einstein constants. And because it is the cosmological constant which is uniquely responsible for dark densities, *it is really the cosmological constant that underlies this gravitational strength variation.*

This Lagrangian now including dark densities is then used to draw the Feynman diagram of **Figure 3** which illustrates how the gravitational interaction can be attractive, repulsive or neutral depending upon the dark and ordinary density mixes. And because ordinary gravitating matter can never directly interact with

gravitons or the neutrino loops, but only does so indirectly through a gravitino interface, we were able by hypothesis to identify gravitons as the elementary particles of dark energy and neutrinos comprising the neutrino loop as the elementary particles of dark matter. This enabled us to calculate the energies and densities of these dark particles at (26.3) through (26.6), and to determine at (26.8) that the dark matter neutrino loops, on average, travel at about 98% of the speed of light.

Finally, we used the strength parameter P in quadratic form to prepare **Figure 4** which plots the ordinary and dark densities for neutral L_{vac} and repulsive “subvacuum” gravitation, and **Figure 5** which plots the same for ordinary attractive gravitation. A byproduct of the calculations underlying these plots enabled us at (28.4) to tighten the reported [24] dark density parameters by about an order of magnitude, and at (28.5) to halve the error bars for the cosmological constant, providing additional experimental contact points. The comparison of **Figures 4 and 5** at the end of **Section 29** gave further support to the hypothesis that gravitons and the neutrinos forming gravitational neutrino loops are the elementary particles of dark energy and matter. And, it raised the possibility that the cosmological redshift may not indicate that the universe is expanding from a big bang. Rather, it could simply be the observable manifestation of the repulsive variant of gravitation operating to repel photons apart in intergalactic regions of spacetime where ordinary matter densities are very spartan in comparison, particularly, to dark energy densities of gravitons traversing those regions.

To conclude, it must be reiterated that the underlying connection between gravitational weakness and small neutrino masses is not a numeric accident. Even without the new physics that results from this connection, the probability that this is accidental falls well under six sigma, as reviewed. On top of this, the new physics that does emerge is compelling: Neutrino eigenstate masses can be individually calculated, and the neutrino mass sum and PMNS angles can be substantially tightened. Moreover, when the Newton / Einstein constants are expressed in terms of this connection, the result is a long-sought renormalizable theory of gravitation which explicitly demonstrates how elementary particles gravitate with one another at the quantum level. Additionally, when the cosmological constant and perfect fluid tensors are brought to bear, it is revealed that gravitons and the neutrinos in the neutrino “cliff” loops which mediate long-range gravitational interactions, are the elementary particles of dark energy and matter, and that in intergalactic regions where densities of ordinary matter are very small in comparison with those of dark energy and matter, gravitation becomes repulsive. This, as noted, could explain the cosmological redshift without resort to cosmological expansion and acceleration thereof, though it does not rule these out as secondary, corollary effects arising from this gravitational repulsion in intergalactic spacetime regions. When all this new physics is added to the six-sigma-plus confidence of a separate statistical analysis, there can be little doubt that the 1998 discovery [2] that neutrinos are not massless but do have very tiny masses, was a precursor to understanding that the weakness of gravitation is directly interconnected with these very small neutrino masses via a renormalizable theory of gravitation and dark energy and matter, and that in retrospect, Newtonian gravitation itself was the very first predating evidence for neutrinos having nonzero masses.

References

-
- [1] R. Gatto, G. Sartori, M. Tonin, *Weak self-masses, Cabibbo angle, and broken $SU_2 \times SU_2$* , Phys. Lett. B28 128-130 (1968)
 - [2] Y. Fukuda et al., *Measurements of the Solar Neutrino Flux from Super-Kamiokande’s First 300 Days*, Phys. Rev. Lett. 81, 1158, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.81.1158> (1998)
 - [3] G. t’Hooft, *Renormalizable Lagrangians for massive Yang-Mills fields*, Nuclear Physics B 35, 167-188 (1971)
 - [4] R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), Prog.Theor.Exp.Phys., 083C01, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/tables/rpp2023-sum-quarks.pdf> (2022) and 2023 update
 - [5] R.M. Barnett, L.P. Lellouch and A.V. Manohar, *Quark Masses*, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/reviews/rpp2023-rev-quark-masses.pdf> (2023)
 - [6] R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), Prog.Theor.Exp.Phys., 083C01, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/listings/rpp2023-list-c-quark.pdf> (2022) and 2023 update
 - [7] A. Ceccucci, Z. Ligeti, Y. Sakai, *CKM Quark-Mixing Matrix*, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/reviews/rpp2023-rev-ckm-matrix.pdf> (2022)
 - [8] K.A. Olive, *Sum of Neutrino Masses*, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/reviews/rpp2023-rev-sum-neutrino-masses.pdf> (2023)

-
- [9] R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), Prog.Theor.Exp.Phys., 083C01, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/tables/rpp2023-sum-leptons.pdf> (2022) and 2023 update
- [10] nu-fit.org, v5.2, *Three-neutrino fit based on data available in November 2022*, <http://www.nu-fit.org/?q=node/256#label10> (2022)
- [11] <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/reviews/rpp2023-rev-phys-constants.pdf> (2023)
- [12] S. Boyd, *Neutrino Oscillations*, University of Warwick
https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/sci/physics/staff/academic/boyd/warwick_week/neutrino_physics/lec_oscillations.pdf (2016)
- [13] C. Cowan, F. Reines, F. B. Harrison, H. W. Kruse, A. D. McGuire, *Detection of the free neutrino: a confirmation*, Science 124, 103 (1956)
- [14] K.A. Olive, *Sum of Neutrino Masses*, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2022/web/viewer.html?file=../reviews/rpp2022-rev-sum-neutrino-masses.pdf> (2021)
- [15] I. Esteban, M.C. Gonzalez-Garcia, M. Maltoni, T. Schwetz, A. Zhou, *The fate of hints: updated global analysis of three-flavor neutrino oscillations*, JHEP 09 178, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.14792> (2020)
- [16] A. Zee, *Quantum field theory in a nutshell*, Princeton (2003) doi:10.5860/choice.41-0986. Available online: <https://i.4pcdn.org/tg/1459871465465.pdf>.
- [17] A. I. Vainshtein, *To the problem of nonvanishing gravitation mass*, Phys, Lett, 39B:393 (1977)
- [18] J. R. Yablon, *Weak long-range and strong short-range gravitational interactions of elementary particle quanta via gravitinos, neutrinos and gravitons*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30119.32160>, preprint (2023)
- [19] R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), Prog.Theor.Exp.Phys., 083C01, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/tables/rpp2023-sum-gauge-higgs-bosons.pdf> (2022) and 2023 update
- [20] R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), Prog.Theor.Exp.Phys., 083C01, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/tables/rpp2023-sum-quarks.pdf> (2022) and 2023 update
- [21] R. M. Wald, *Introduction to Gravitational Self-Force*, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.0907.0412> (2009)
- [22] S. Eidelman, T. Gutsche, C. Hanhart, R.E. Mitchell, S. Spanier, *Scalar Mesons below 1 GeV*, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/reviews/rpp2022-rev-scalar-mesons.pdf> (2021)
- [23] J.R. Pelaez, *From controversy to precision on the sigma meson: a review on the status of the non-ordinary $f_0(500)$ resonance*, [arXiv:1510.00653v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/1510.00653v2) (2015)
- [24] D.E. Groom and D. Scott, *Astrophysical Constants and Parameters*, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/reviews/rpp2023-rev-astrophysical-constants.pdf> (2023)
- [25] A. Faessler, R. Hodak, S. Kovalenko, F. Simkovic, *Search for the Cosmic Neutrino Background*, J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 580 012040 (2015)